

Species composition of the free living multicellular invertebrate animals (Metazoa: Invertebrata) from the Bulgarian sector of the Black Sea and the coastal brackish basins

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Abstract: A total of 19 types, 39 classes, 123 orders, 470 families and 1537 species are known from the Bulgarian Black Sea. They include 1054 species (68.6%) of marine and marine-brackish forms and 508 species (33.0%) of freshwater-brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms, connected with water. Five types (Nematoda, Rotifera, Annelida, Arthropoda and Mollusca) have a high species richness (over 100 species). Of these, the richest in species are Arthropoda (802 species – 52.2%), Annelida (173 species – 11.2%) and Mollusca (152 species – 9.9%). The remaining 14 types include from 1 to 38 species. There are some well-studied regions (over 200 species recorded): first, the vicinity of Varna (601 species), where investigations continue for more than 100 years. The aquatory of the towns Nesebar, Pomorie, Burgas and Sozopol (220 to 274 species) and the region of Cape Kaliakra (230 species) are well-studied. Of the coastal basins most studied are the lakes Durankulak, Ezerets-Shabla, Beloslav, Varna, Pomorie, Atanasovsko, Burgas, Mandra and the firth of Ropotamo River (up to 100 species known). The vertical distribution has been analyzed for 800 species (75.9%) – marine and marine-brackish forms. The great number of species is found from 0 to 25 m on sand (396 species) and rocky (257 species) bottom. The groups of stenohypo- (52 species – 6.5%), stenoepi- (465 species – 58.1%), meso- (115 species – 14.4%) and eurybathic forms (168 species – 21.0%) are represented. The marine and marine-brackish species are divided into 162 zoogeographical categories, combined into 4 main groups and 16 subgroups. The main portion of the Black Sea fauna has an Atlantic-Mediterranean origin and represents the impoverished Atlantic-Mediterranean fauna (740 species – 70.2%). Cosmopolitan, Atlantic-Indian, Atlantic-Pacific, endemic and Caspian relict forms are represented. The benthic (115 species – 97.5%) and marine (114 species – 96.6%) forms of the Black Sea endemics (118 species – 11.2%) predominate. The brackish endemics (11 species – 9.3%) most often are Caspian relicts. The main portions of the Caspian relicts (41 species – 3.9%) are benthic brackish forms (38 species – 92.7%). The freshwater-brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms, connected with water, are divided into 80 zoogeographical categories, combined into 2 groups and 5 subgroups. Typical for the coast is the prevalence of the species, distributed in Palaearctic and beyond it (296 species – 58.3%). Species, distributed only in Palaearctic but in more than one subregion (79 species – 15.5%) and species, distributed within one Palaearctic subregion (126 species – 24.8%) are represented – Eurosiberian (55 species – 10.8%) and Mediterranean (71 species – 13.9%). A short characteristic of the planktonic and benthic cenoses is done and some coastal basins are scrutinized. An attention is paid to the invasive immigrants that changed the Black Sea communities during the last 60 years. The species of economic and conservation importance are discussed.

Key words: Bulgarian Black Sea coast, invertebrates, species composition, zoogeography, invasive alien species

Introduction

Bulgarian Black Sea fauna has been studied for more than 100 years (CHICHKOFF 1907, 1908, 1912, 1924). A vast material of faunistic data, concerning Bulgarian Black Sea has been accumulated. During the last 50 years, the coast is under a drastic anthropogenic impact and large landscape changes. Considerable changes in the Black Sea cenoses are caused by some invasive species, introduced in the last 100 years (CVETKOV & MARINOV, 1986; KONSULOV, 1998; GOMOIU et al., 2002). The dynamic natures of

the fauna, economic and social importance of wildlife and biodiversity conservation require periodic updating of the faunistic diversity of Bulgaria.

The published catalogues of the Bulgarian Black Sea fauna (VALKANOV, 1957a; VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1964; MARINOV & GOLEMANSKY, 1989; MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993) do not have a systematic character, and taxa of the genus and species group (the families are not presented) are in alphabetical order. These works are published in Bulgarian and the faunistic analyses there are too short. The published generalized studies in English by KONSULOV (1998) and KONSULOV & KONSULOVA (1998) are similar to the works of MARINOV (1990) and KONSULOV & KONSULOVA (1993). Some of the used names are out-of-date and need to be updated. There is a contemporary systematic view for some taxonomic groups, included in the monograph series Fauna of Bulgaria (Polychaeta – MARINOV, 1977; Harpacticoida – APOSTOLOV & MARINOV, 1988), in survey papers (Mollusca – WILKE, 1996; HUBENOV, 2005b, 2007a, 2007b) or in dissertations (Nematoda – STOYKOV, 1980; Crustacea: Malacostraca – UZUNOVA, 2006). There is a lack of zoogeographical characteristic of the fauna except Polychaeta, Harpacticoida, Malacostraca and Mollusca. The submitted zoogeographical analyses of the groups mentioned above are done according to their origin or areography (different principle) and are difficult to compare. Commonly the benthos hydrobionts are scrutinized separately from the plankton forms. A generalized zoogeographical work on the Bulgarian Black Sea fauna lacks.

Approach, material and methods

The aim of this work is to present the Bulgarian marine invertebrate fauna as well as to analyze the taxonomic diversity, the level of study and some zoogeographical and ecological features of the Black Sea invertebrates.

The investigations of the Black Sea territory for the last two centuries are generalized in this work. The paper generalizes the works of CASPERS (1951), VALKANOV (1957a), VALKANOV & MARINOV (1964), MARINOV & GOLEMANSKY (1989), MARINOV (1990), KONSULOV & KONSULOVA (1993, 1998), KONSULOV (1998) and GOLEMANSKY (2007). Data from 832 publications and the dissertations of KONSULOV (1991), KAMBURSKA (2004), TODOROVA (2005), UZUNOVA (2006) and TRAYANOVA (2008) are included. Currently some coastal wetlands have been investigated in connection with their management

plans (Durankulak Lake, Shabla Lake, Pomorie Lake, Atanasovsko Lake and protected area Poda). These investigations are also included in the work.

The categories of type class and order are used (an exception is made for supertype Arthropoda because of the structure of the superior taxonomic categories). All water (marine, brackish and freshwater) and many terrestrial invertebrate animals, connected with the coast and coastal basins are included.

In the numbering of the localities (Table 1), for convenience, the old numbering used in catalogues of VALKANOV (1957a), VALKANOV & MARINOV (1964) and MARINOV & GOLEMANSKY (1989) is presented. In many cases, the information on the coastal basins, given in these publications is outdated (before 1957). Today, a part of the brackish basins along the coast do not exist in its original form. They are converted into bays, harbors, dams, have no connection with the sea or are drained. For most of the smaller basins there is a lack of present-day faunistic investigations. Twenty new localities, which have no equivalent in the previous catalogues, are included. The number of known species in the separate localities is presented as well. It shows mainly their level of study and to a less extent, the actual species diversity.

For the marine species, the depth to which they are established in the Bulgarian Black Sea is given (Table 2). Species, for which there are no data from the Bulgarian coast, data from other regions of the sea are presented. When information in the Bulgarian literature differs significantly from the one, reported for other parts of the sea, the respective foreign data for the Black Sea are presented, after the Bulgarian data. In freshwater Mollusca, the presented depth refers to the whole country.

For species that inhabit both fresh and salt waters, an areographical categorization for seas and freshwater basins is presented. The categorization for the freshwaters is given in brackets (Table 2). Some taxa, distributed both in the sea and freshwaters (Supercosmopolitan) are analyzed both to the marine and freshwater forms. The brackish species are included to marine or freshwater forms according to the fact whether they are marine-brackish or freshwater-brackish. When the reports of species distribution are discrepant, a second categorization is presented. An attention is paid to the immigrants and invasive forms that had changed considerably the Black Sea communities in XX century.

There is no unanimity among the experts about the zoogeographical status of the Black Sea, which is either considered as an independent subregion or is unified with the Mediterranean Sea (and Lusi-

Table 1. Taxa localities (Symbols: * – highly altered habitat to the time of collection of the material; [] – old geographical names and old data, before 1957)

Locality	Number	Old number	Number of species
Sea localities			
Durankulak [Blatnitsa] (Durankulak north – Durankulak Lake – Krapets)	1	1	131
Shabla (Shabla Lake – Shabla Tuzla – Cape Shabla)	2	2	153
Cape Kaliakra (Rusalka – Bolata – Cape Kaliakra)	3	3	230
Kavarna (Cape Chairburun – Cape Chirakman – Cape Kalkanburun)	4	4	138
Balchik (Balchik Tuzla – Balchik)	5	5	172
Batova (Albena – Kranevo)	6	6	141
Varna (Golden Sands – Evksinograd – Varna – Cape Galata – Pasha Dere River)	7	7	601
Kamchiya (Cape Ilandzhik – Camping Ray – Kamchiya River – Shkorpilovtsi)	8	8	139
Byala (Cape Cherni – Byala – Dvoynitsa River – Obzor)	9	9	128
Cape Emine (Irakli – Cape Emine – Cocketrice sandy bank)	10	10	176
Nesebar (Elenite – Sunny Beach – Nesebar – Ravda)	11	11	256
Pomorie (Aheloy – Pomorie – Camping Evropa – Cape Lahna)	12	12	220
Burgas (Saraphovo – Burgas – Kraymorie – Park Rosenets – Cape Chukalya)	13	13	264
Sveta Anastasiya Island [Bolshevik Island]	14	14	136
Chernomorets (Cape Atiya – Chernomorets – Cape Chervenka [Cape Hrisotira])	15	15	134
Sozopol (Camping Gradina – Sozopol – Kavatsite – Dyuni)	16	15	274
Cape Maslen Nos (Alepu Marsh – Ropotamo River – C. Maslen Nos – Stomoplo Marsh)	17	16	184
Primorsko (Stomoplo Marsh – Primorsko – Dyavolska Reka River)	18	17	133
Kiten [Urdoviza] (International Youth Centre – Kiten – Karaagach River – Lozenets)	19	18	133
Tsarevo [Michurin, Vasiliko] (Cape Arapya – Tsarevo – Varvara)	20	19	177
Ahtopol (Varvara – Achtopol – Veleka River)	21	20	143
Sinemorets (Sinemorets – Silistar River – Rezovo)	22	20	140
<i>Zostera</i> overgrowths (0-6 m)	23		45
Rocky sublittoral, <i>Cystoseira</i> and other algae, <i>Mytilus</i> (from 0.5-1 m to 15-25 m)	24		257
Sandy sublittoral (1-25 m); clean sand – to 17 m, with <i>Branchiostoma</i> – to 20 m	25		396
Coastal silt (from 15-20 m to 30-40 m); dominated by <i>Melinna</i> – to 25-30 m	26		115
<i>Mytilus</i> silt (from 15-20 m to 60-80 m)	27		148
<i>Phaseolina</i> silt (from 65 m to 140-180 m)	28		104
Black Sea, pelagic in front of the Bulgarian coast	29		55
Localities along the sea coast			
Lithotelms, Shabla – Cape Kaliakra, Varna	32	21	15
Lithotelms, Ravda, Sozopol – Cape Maslen Nos	33	22	40
Basins of Varna Aquarium	34	25	11
Subterranean (ground) waters of sandy beach, interstitial, mesopsamal	35	26	146
Sunny Beach, coastal zone, sand bottom and floating algae	36	29	4
Arkutino, coastal zone	37	27	4
Camping (Residence) Perla, coastal zone, sand bottom and floating algae	38	30	4
Kiten, coastal zone, sand bottom and floating algae	39	28	5
Lozenets, coastal zone	40	31	4
Small saltwater marshes along the coast	41	72	8
Small freshwater marshes along the coast	42	73	26
Mouths of small streams	43	74	3
Temporary salty puddles and floods around the coastal basins	44	79	4
Rocks along the entire coast, rocky supralittoral	45	76	14
Algae washed ashore along the coast, supralittoral	46	77	23
Salty soils around coastal basins	47	78	28

Table 1. Continued

Locality	Number	Old number	Number of species
Terrestrial coastal zone with halophilic plants (to 50-100 m from the sea)	48	75	24
Sea coastal zone; littoral (medio- or pseudolittoral)	49		24
Rocky littoral (medio- or pseudolittoral, enteromorpha zone)	50		16
Sandy littoral (medio- or pseudolittoral)	51		64
Sandy supralittoral	52		8
Springs and wells with brackish water along the coast, Durakulak – Cape Kaliakra	53		1
Springs along the coast, Sozopol – Cape Maslen Nos	54		2
Coastal basins (lakes, swamps, firths and river floods)			
Durankulak [Blatnitsa] Lake: [0-5‰, 3.4 km ² , depth 4 m], 1-4‰, average salinity – 2‰	58	41	113
Ezerets Lake: [1-2‰, average salinity – 1.6‰], 0.58-0.79‰, 0.72 km ² , depth 9.0 m	59	42	101
Shabla Lake: [0.1-2‰, 0.6-1.6‰], 0.52-0.60‰, 0.79 km ² , depth 9.5 m	60	42	137
*Schabla Tuzla: [10-30‰], 22-200‰, 0.19 km ² , depth 0.6 m	61	43	17
Nanevska Tuzla [Tauk Liman]: 1-90‰ (often about 20‰) 0.10 km ² , depth 0.3 m	62		3
*Bolata River Mouth: 0.1‰	63	44	13
*Balchik Tuzla: [80-150‰], 35-160‰, 0.14 km ² , depth 0.5-0.8 m	64	45	7
Batova River Mouth and Swamp: 0.03-6‰, depth 0.5-1 m,	65	46	9
*Golden Sands Marshes: [0-60‰]	66	47	7
*Sindel [Sultanlar] Swamp: [0‰]	67	48	6
*Beloslav [Devnya, Gebedzhe] Lake: 0.1-15.6‰, 3.90 km ² , depth 3.5 m, sea canal – 1923	68	49	160
*Varna Lake: [5-14‰], 6.5-8-16.8‰, 17.40 km ² , depth 19 m, sea canals – 1909, 1976	69	50	264
Pasha Dere [Chatal Dere, Novata Voda] River Mouth: [0-7‰]	70	51	10
Kamchiya River Mouth – Swamps: [0.4-0.7‰], average 0.1‰	71	52	53
Fandakliyska Reka [Shkorpilova] River Mouth: [0.1‰]	72	53	11
*Dvoynitsa [Cherta, Suha Kamchiya] River Mouth	73		8
*Hadzhiyska River Mouth [Nesebar Marsh]: [1-10‰]	74	54	30
Aheloy River Mouth	75		9
Pomorie Lake: 30-70 to 140‰, 8.50 km ² , depth 1.4 m	76	55	106
Atanasovsko Lake: 1-250‰, average 50-60‰, 16.90 km ² , depth 0.3-0.8 m	77	56	113
*Burgas [Vaya] Lake: [9-20‰], 1.8-45‰, average 10.6‰, 27.60 km ² , depth 1.3 m	78	57	89
*Mandra Dam [Mandra Lake to 1963]: [0.1-12‰, max. 30‰, 14.00 km ² , depth 1.1-5 m]	79	58	94
Uzungeren-Poda Complex: 0.1-32‰, 3.12 km ²	80		80
Tsiganski Skelet Marsh [Chengene Skele Marsh]: [7-20‰]	81	59	11
Alepu Marsh: 4-11-27‰ (usually 3.5-7.2‰), 0.14 km ² , depth 0.6-1 m	82	60	14
Arkutino Marsh: 0.1-1‰, 0.03 km ² , depth 0.5 m	83		24
Ropotamo River Mouth: 5-15‰	84	61	97
Stomoplo Marsh: [2-25‰], 1.5-4‰, 6-14‰, 0.06 km ² , depth 0.5 m	85	62	20
*Dyavolsko Blato Swamp: [1-20‰], 6-14‰, 0.80 km ² , depth 1 m	86	63	78
*Dyavolska Reka River Mouth: depth 4 m	87		10
Karaagachka Reka [Kitsenska, Oryashka] River Mouth and Swamp: [5-15‰]	88	64	68
Tsarevska Reka [Michurinska (small)] River: [3‰]	89	65	10
Izgrevska Dere [Michurinska Reka (great)] River: [5-10‰]	90	66	14
Puddles and mouths of streams between Tsarevo and Ahtopol	91	67	12
Veleka River Mouth: [0-0.5‰]	92	68	59
Butamyata [Potamyata] River Mouth: [12‰]	93	69	22
Silistar River Mouth: [5-15‰]	94	70	25
Rezovska Reka [Rezvaya] River Mouth: [0-1.45‰]	95	71	30
Black Sea coastal lakes and swamps	96		71

tanean Atlantic subregion). The zoogeographical scheme used here (Table 5) is based on the works of GURYANOVA (1964), DE LATTIN (1967), GOLIKOV & STAROBOGATOV (1968, 1972), STAROBOGATOV (1970), MORDUKHAY-BOLTOVSKOY (1972), GOLIKOV (1982), NESIS (1982), RIEDL (1983), BĂNĂRESCU (1990), ABBOTT & DANCE (1991), ELDER & PERNETTA (1991), BRUYNE (2003), HOOK (2008), EARLE & GLOVER (2009). The zoogeographical categorization of species is done on the basis of data of their distribution, taken from the literature and the newest electronic issues (Tables 2, 5 and 6).

The presented ecological data (Table 2) are taken from the Bulgarian literature. Only if there are no data from Bulgaria, foreign data are included for the corresponding species. The conservation value of taxa is determined regarding to their populations inhabiting Bulgaria. For local endemics, 100% of their populations are localized in Bulgaria, therefore they are given the highest conservation category (world importance). This category also includes regional endemics because of their restricted distribution and species from the IUCN Red List. Taxa of European importance include Black Sea endemics as well as the species from Bern Convention and Habitats Directive. Relicts and rare taxa (if not listed under other category) form the group of national importance. The species, included in Black Sea Red Data Book (DUMONT et al., 1999), Red Data Book of Bulgaria (BISERKOV & GOLEMANSKI, 2011), European and IUCN Red List are marked.

The literature references (Table 2) do not include all publications addressed to the corresponding species from the Bulgarian coast (to 9 references quoted). Most often the first record of taxa is given, its inclusion in catalogues and some new or important literature data. Under updating of the names and specifying of the species distribution, some electronic issues are used: Antarctic Invertebrates, CLEMAM (Check List of European Marine Mollusca), DAISIE (Delivering Alien Invasive Species Inventories for Europe), EOL (Encyclopedia of Life), ERMS (European Register of Marine Species), EUNIS biodiversity database, Fauna Europaea, Global Invasive Species Database, Global Names Index, ITIS (Integrated Taxonomic Information System), Marine Planktonic Copepods, Marine Species Identification Portal, MarLIN (The Marine Life Information Network), NARMS (North Atlantic Register for Marine Species), NeMys, NEOBANIS (European Network on Invasive Alien Species), PESI (A Pan-European Species directories Infrastructure), PlanktonNet Image, OBIS (Ocean Biogeographic Information System), The World of

Copepods, World Polychaeta Database, WoRMS (World Register of Marine Species).

Unexplored territories and literature data

Despite the prolonged hydrobiological investigations and good knowledge of the Bulgarian Black Sea fauna as a whole, unexplored areas still remain. The possible reasons for this fact are as follows: lack of specialists on many taxonomic groups; great loading of the specialists with environmental or conservation projects, therefore the time for faunistic research is insufficient; periodic standard surveys of the fixed number of monitoring stations, a relative remoteness of natural science centers; a poor attendance by many zoologists in comparison with other regions or change in coastal communities as a result of anthropogenic impact. Most of the literature data related to these regions are fragmentary, outdated, concern separated systematic groups or are scattered in different works which are not specially referred to them.

Today, the most poorly investigated territories in regard to many groups are the southern coast (south of Cape Maslen Nos) and the coastal zone with a depth less than 10 m, where the oceanographic ships rarely enter. Some of the coastal basins were explored long ago so the investigations do not reflect the recent condition of their fauna.

Weaknesses in the literature data which limit the obtaining of equivalent information for the comparison of the territories include: different levels of study of individual taxa; insufficient research of many groups in the corresponding areas; a lack of exact localities for the part of the recorded species; existence of rich synonymy; outdated data; a lack of generalized investigations for most of the groups; significant differences in the number of taxa in the separate areas; unexplored territories; prolonged periods of data accumulation for most regions; predominance of ecological studies versus those of fauna; independent review of benthos and plankton forms. These weaknesses lead to the following 5 problems:

1. Continuous supplementation of an existing historical list of fauna. As a result, species diversity in a given area is higher than in reality.

2. Incomparability of data in terms of time periods. Data comparisons between two areas very often cover different periods as it is not possible to study all taxonomic groups and territories simultaneously.

3. Incomparability of benthos – plankton data. Many studies are look at either benthos only or

plankton only, despite the fact that most taxa have both a benthic and planktonic stages.

4. Incomplete reporting of anthropogenic influences, successional and landscape changes on the composition of the communities along the coast. A number of well-studied brackish basins in the past no longer exist or have changed.

5. Prioritization of research in areas under monitoring or environmental protection legislation.

Abbreviations used

Taxa: [] – names and synonyms under which the species are recorded for Bulgaria

Distribution: **1-29** – Localities in Black Sea (**1-10** – North Black Sea, **11-22** – South Black Sea), **32-54** – Localities along the coast, **58-96** – Coastal basins, **figures** – numbers of the localities in Table 1 [dash before the figure (-7, -12) indicates the latter as maximum depth, dash after the figure (7-, 12-) indicates the latter as minimum depth], **?** – uncertain data or lack of data, ***** – outdated information and significantly altered habitat versus time of collection of the material

Zoogeographical categories (the abbreviations in brackets refer to the freshwater and terrestrial species): **aam** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean, **aami** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **aamip** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **aaminp** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific, **aamni** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian, **aamswp** – Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific, **aanamp** – Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific, **aanamip** – Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **aannam** – Arctic-Antarctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean, **ab** – Amphiboreal, **abam** – Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean, **abamp** – Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific, **abap** – Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian, **abapbp** – Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Boreal Pacific, **abapnep** – Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Pacific, **ace** – Arctic-CircumEuropean, **acem** – Arctic-CircumEuropean-Mauritanian, **acmnz** – Arctic-Celtic-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **acp** – Arctic-Celtic-Pontian, **adep** – Adriatic-Aegean-Pontian, **adp** – Adriatic-Pontian, **adpc** – Adriatic-Pontian-Caspian, **am (am)** – Atlantic-Mediterranean, **ami** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **aminp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific, **aminwp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Northwest Pacific, **aminz** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand, **amip** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific,

amiswp – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Southwest Pacific, **amiwp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific, **amj** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Japonic, **amnei** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian, **amnep** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific, **amni** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian, **amnp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific, **amnz** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **amp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific, **amrs** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea, **amrsp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea-Pacific, **amswp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific, **amwi** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian, **amwp** – Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Pacific, **anam** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean, **anamip** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific, **anamip** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **anamnep** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific, **anamnp** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific, **anamp** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific, **anamrs** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea, **anap** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Pontian, **anapnep** – Arctic-North Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Pacific, **anclm** – Antarctic-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **anpip** – Antarctic-Pontian-Indo-Pacific, **antami** – Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **antamip** – Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **antamp** – Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific, **ap** – Atlantic-Pontian, **api** – Atlantic-Pontian-Indian, **apswp** – Atlantic-Pontian-Southwest Pacific, **(ase)** – Atlantic-South European, **(atm)** – Afrotropical-Mediterranean, **baap** – Boreal-Antiboreal Atlantic-Pontian, **bam** – Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean, **bamp** – Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific, **bami** – Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **bamp** – Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific, **bamswp** – Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific, **baap** – Boreal Atlantic-Pontian, **baapbp** – Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Boreal Pacific, **bapp** – Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Pacific, **cacpnz** – Carolinian-Celtic-Pontian-New Zealand, **calm** – Carolinian-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **calp** – Carolinian-Lusitanian-Pontian, **cb** – Circumboreal, **cbm** – Circumboreal-Mediterranean, **cbma** – Circumboreal-Mediterranean-Australian, **cclm** – Carolinian-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **ccp** – Carolinian-Celtic-Pontian, **ce** – CircumEuropean, **cem** – CircumEuropean-Mauritanian, **cg** – Circumglobal, **clm** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **clmi** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Indian, **clmm** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian,

clmnei – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian, **clmnwi** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northwest Indian, **clmnz** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **clmrs** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Red Sea, **clmwi** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indian, **clp** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Pontian, **clpnz** – Celtic-Lusitanian-Pontian-New Zealand, **cm** – Celtic-Mediterranean, **cp** – Celtic-Pontian, **cpc** – Celtic-Pontian-Caspian, **cpj** – Celtic-Pontian-Japonic, **cpnei** – Celtic-Pontian-Northeast Indian, **cpnz** – Celtic-Pontian-New Zealand, **cpwp** – Celtic-Pontian-West Pacific, **(cse)** – Central and South European, **(csee)** – Central and Southeast European, **(cseea)** – Central and Southeast European-Anatolian, **(cseeit)** – Central and Southeast European-Iran-Turanian, **(csena)** – Central and South European-North African, **cst** – Circumsubtropical, **(dp)** – Disjunct Palaearctic, **(e)** – European, **(ea)** – European-Australian, **eam** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean, **eami** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **eamip** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **eamiswp** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Southwest Pacific, **eampp** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific, **eamrs** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea, **eamswi** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Indian, **eamwi** – East Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian, **(ean)** – European-Anatolian, **(Eb)** – Balkan endemic, **(Ebg)** – Bulgarian endemic, **(eca)** – European-Central Asian, **(eit)** – European-Iran-Turanian, **(El)** – Local Bulgarian endemic, **em (em)** – East Mediterranean, **(emca)** – East Mediterranean-Central Asian, **(ena)** – European-North African, **(Ep)** – Pontian endemic, **ep** – Aegean-Pontian, **(Er)** – Regional Bulgarian endemic, **(esca)** – Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **(et)** – European-Turanian, **(ewca)** – European-West Central Asian, **(h)** – Holarctic, **(ha)** – Holarctic-Australian, **ham** – Holatlantic-Mediterranean, **(hat)** – Holarctic-Afrotropical, **(hata)** – Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian, **(hn)** – Holarctic-Neotropical, **(hna)** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Australian, **(hnat)** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical, **(hnata)** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical-Australian, **(hno)** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental, **(hnoa)** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental-Australian, **(ho)** – Holarctic-Oriental, **(hoa)** – Holarctic-Oriental-Australian, **(hoes)** – Holoeurosiberian, **hom (hom)** – Holomediterranean, **(hop)** – Holopalaearctic, **(hpt)** – Holarctic-Paleotropical, **(hpta)** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian, **(hptn)** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical, **i** – introduced species (immigrants), **j** – Japanese, **K (k)** – Cosmopolitan, **kclm** – Caribbean-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **klm** – Caribbean-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **kmm** – Caribbean-Mediterranean-Mauritanian, **lm** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean, **lmi** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Indian, **lmm** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian, **lmmg** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian-Guinean, **lmmwi** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian-West Indian, **lmnei** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian, **lmnz** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **lmsa** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-South African, **lmwi** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indian, **lmwiwp** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indo-West Pacific, **lmwp** – Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Pacific, **lp** – Lusitanian-Pontian, **m** – Mediterranean, **(mca)** – Mediterranean-Central Asian, **miwp** – Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific, **mj** – Mediterranean-Japonic, **mmgt** – Mediterranean-Mauritanian-Guinean-Tasmanian, **mni** – Mediterranean-North Indian, **mnz** – Mediterranean-New Zealand, **mrs** – Mediterranean-Red Sea, **(mwca)** – Mediterranean-West Central Asian, **(na)** – North American, **nam** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean, **namep** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-East Pacific, **nami** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian, **namim** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Malayan, **naminz** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand, **namip** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific, **namiwpp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific, **namj** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Japonic, **namnei** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian, **namnep** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific, **namni** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian, **namnp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific, **namnz** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **nampp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific, **namrs** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea, **namrsnep** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea-Northeast Pacific, **namsp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-South Pacific, **namsep** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southeast Pacific, **namswp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific, **namwi** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian, **namwp** – North Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Pacific, **nap** – North Atlantic-Pontian, **napnei** – North Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Indian, **neamal** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Aleutian, **neamep** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-East Pacific, **neaminz** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand, **neamj** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Japonic, **neamnp** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific, **neamnz** –

Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand, **neamswp** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific, **neamwp** – Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Pacific, (**nem**) – Northeast Mediterranean, (**nemit**) – Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian, **nm (nm)** – North Mediterranean, (**nmwca**) – North Mediterranean-West Central Asian, **nz** – New Zealand, (**om**) – Oriental-Mediterranean, (**omca**) – Oriental-Mediterranean-Central Asian, (**omcaa**) – Oriental-Mediterranean-Central Asian-Australian, **p** – Pontian, (**pat**) – Palearctic-Afrotropical, (**pata**) – Palearctic-Afrotropical-Australian, **pc** – Pontian-Caspian, **pca** – Pontian-Caspian-Aral, **pinz** – Pontian-Indo-New Zealand, (**pm**) – Pontomediterranean, **pnep** – Pontian-Northeast Pacific, (**po**) – Palearctic-Oriental, (**poa**) – Palearctic-Oriental-Australian, (**ppt**) – Palearctic-Paleotropical, (**ppta**) – Palearctic-Paleotropical-Australian, (**ptm**) – Paleotropical-Mediterranean, (**ptmca**) – Paleotropical-Mediterranean-Central Asian, (**ptsp**) – Paleotropical-South Palearctic, **R** – relict, **Rc** – Caspian relict, (**se**) – South European, (**see**) – Southeast European, (**seea**) – Southeast European-Anatolian, (**seep**) – Southeast European-Pontian, (**seepc**) – Southeast European-Pontian-Caspian, **Sf** – subfossil, **SK (sk)** – Subcosmopolitan, **tam** – Tropical Atlantic-Mediterranean, (**tp**) – Transpalaeartic, (**tpo**) – Transpalaeartic-Oriental, **vck** – Virginian-Carolinian-Caribbean, **vclm** – Virginian-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean, (**wces**) – West and Central Eurosiberian, (**wcp**) – West and Central Palaeartic, (**wcpo**) – West and Central Palaeartic-Oriental, (**wes**) – West Eurosiberian, (**wesa**) – West Eurosiberian-Anatolian, (**wp**) – West Palearctic, (**wpat**) – West Palearctic-Afrotropical, (**wppt**) – West Palearctic-Paleotropical, + – species known only from shells, • – occurrence of endemic taxa, ? – probable category.

Ecological data: **ar** – argillophilous, **α** – α-mesosaprobic, **α-β** – α-β-mesosaprobic, **β** – β-mesosaprobic, **B** – brackish, **BA** – Barcelona Convention, **BC** – Bern Convention, **bt** – benthos, **co** – commensal, **CR** – critically endangered, **cr** – crenobiont, **cs** – coastal silt, **DD** – data deficient, **E** – European importance, **eb** – eurybathic, **ec** – ectoparasite, **eh** – euryhaline, **EN** – endangered, **ep** – epibathic, **epi** – epibiont, **eppl** – epipelagic, **et** – eurythermal, **eu** – eurybiont, **EX** – Extinct, **gw** – ground-water, **ha** – halophilous or halobiont, **hb** – hypobathic, **HD** – Habitats Directive, **if** – interstitial fauna, **is** – invasive species, **L** – freshwater, **I** – littoral zone (medio-, pseudolittoral, intertidal), **LC** – least concern, **LR** – lower risk, **Ir** – rocky littoral, **ls** – sandy littoral, **It** – rocks

or lithophilous, **M** – marine, **mb** – mesobathic, **mc** – *Mytilus* cenosis, **ms** – *Mytilus* silt, **N** – national importance, **NE** – not evaluated, **NT** – near threatened, **o** – oligosaprobic, **p** – plankton, **pa** – parasite, **pe** – pelophilous, **ph** – algae overgrowth or phytophilous, **phc** – *Phyllophora* coenosis, **phs** – *Phaseolina* silt, **po** – potamophilous, **pp** – pelagic, **ps** – sand or psammophilous, **r** – rare, **rh** – rhithrophilous, **ro** – rocky, **s** – silt, **sb** – stenobathic, **sep** – stenoepibathic, **sg** – shells and sand with shells, **shb** – stenoepibathic, **sl** – sublittoral zone (infra- and circalittoral, subtidal), **slc** – *Cystoseira* sublittoral, **slr** – rocky sublittoral, **sls** – sandy sublittoral, **sp** – supralittoral zone (supratidal), **spr** – rocky supralittoral, **sps** – sandy supralittoral, **sw** – stagnant water, **T** – terrestrial, **th** – thermophile, **TL** – terrestrial forms connected with water, **tx** – troglodyte, **VU** – vulnerable, **W** – world importance, **x** – xenosaprobic, **zc** – *Zostera* cenosis, % – limiting freshwater level for marine and salinity level for the freshwater forms, () – rarely exception, ■ – Black Sea Red Data Book, ▲ – Red Data Book of Bulgaria, ♦ – European and IUCN Red List.

Results and Discussion

A total of 19 types, 39 classes, 123 orders, 470 families and 1537 species have been known from the Bulgarian Black Sea (Table 3). These taxa include 1054 species (68.6%) marine and marine-brackish forms and 508 species (33.0%) freshwater-brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms, connected with water. A small number of supercosmopolitan forms (17 species), inhabitants of the marine, freshwater and terrestrial cenoses are scrutinized to both two groups. Five types (Nematoda, Rotifera, Annelida, Arthropoda and Mollusca) have a high species composition (over 100 species). Of these, the richest in species are Arthropoda (802 species – 52.2%), Annelida (173 species – 11.2%) and Mollusca (152 species – 9.9%). The rest 14 types include from 1 to 38 species. The Bulgarian fauna comprises about 70% of the known 2000-2200 species from the Black Sea and Azov Sea (Tables 2 and 3). For individual taxa this percentage varies considerably and depends on the level of study. The species composition varies depending on whether the authors considered only marine and marine-brackish forms or include freshwater-brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms, related to water. The rich in brackish basins Ukrainian and Russian Black Sea coast is considerably superior to the Bulgarian coast in brackish taxa.

Most marine invertebrates have been established throughout the Bulgarian Black Sea coast.

Table 2. Register of the marine, brackish, freshwater and terrestrial Invertebrate free-living fauna from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
PORIFERA					
DEMOSPONGIAE					
HADROMERIDA					
Clionidae					
<i>Pione vastifica</i> (Hancock, 1849) [<i>Cliona pontica</i> , <i>C. stationis</i> , <i>Vioa grantii</i>]	7-16, 27	-42	namwp	M, bt, mb, mc	32, 249, 389
Suberitidae					
<i>Suberites carnosus</i> (Johnston, 1842) [<i>Halichondria</i> , <i>S. domuncula</i>]	3, 7, 16, 34	6-180	am	M, bt, eb, ms, phs	32, 249, 389
<i>Suberites prototypus</i> Czerniavsky, 1880 [<i>Prosuberites brevispinus</i> , <i>P. epiphytium</i>]	7, 27, 28	3-90	● p	M, bt, eb, ms, phs	32, 84, 249, 389
HALICHONDRIDA					
Halichondriidae					
<i>Halichondria panicea</i> (Pallas, 1766) [<i>H. grossa</i> , <i>Spongia</i>]	7	2-65	K	M, bt, eb, lt, ■	32, 114, 249, 389
POCLOSCLERIDA					
Microcionidae					
<i>Clathria cleistochela</i> (Topsent, 1925) [<i>Microciona</i>]	7	0-5	lmm, ? i	M, bt, ? is	84, 249, 389
Tedaniidae					
<i>Tedania anhelans</i> (Lieberkühn, 1859) [<i>T. nigrescens</i> , <i>Haliclona</i> , <i>Reniera digitata</i>]	5, 6, 23, 24	-22	? amp	M, bt, ep, ph	32, 67, 249, 389
Coelosphaeridae					
<i>Lissodendoryx varisciera</i> (Swartschewsky, 1905) [<i>L. dictyonoides</i>]	7	8-26	● p	M, bt, ep, lt	32, 249, 389
Crellidae					
<i>Crella gracilis</i> (Alander, 1942) [<i>Kowalewskyella</i> , <i>Yvesia</i>]	3	14-60	cp	M, bt, eb, lt	32, 249, 389
Mycalidae					
<i>Mycala syrinx</i> (Schmidt, 1862) [<i>Esperia lorenzii</i> , <i>E. muscoides</i>]	7, 34	0-87	lmm	M, bt, eb, ro, s	32, 249, 389
HAPLOSCLERIDA					
Petrosiidae					
<i>Petrosia ficiformis</i> (Poiret, 1789) [<i>P. clavata</i> , <i>P. dura</i> , <i>Reniera boutschinskii</i>]	3, 5, 24	-40	kmm	M, bt, mb, slc, slr	32, 249, 389
Chalinidae					
<i>Chalinula limbata</i> (Montagu, 1818) [<i>Halichona</i> , <i>Haliclomissa</i> , <i>Pachychalina</i>]	7		clmm	M, bt	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona aqueductus</i> (Schmidt, 1862) [<i>H. alba</i> , <i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera</i>]	5, 11, 12, 13, 34	-100	lm	M, bt, eb, ro	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona cinerea</i> (Grant, 1826) [<i>H. palmata</i> , <i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera</i> , <i>Spongia</i>]	5	-75	aamp	M, bt, eb, phc	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona flavescens</i> (Topsent, 1893) [<i>Reniera</i>]	7	-35	hom	M, bt, ro	84, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona grossa</i> (Schmidt, 1864) [<i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera</i>]	12, 13		em	M, bt	32, 249, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Haliclona implexa</i> (Schmidt, 1868) [<i>H. iniformis</i> , <i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera curiosa</i>]	1, 2, 3, 4, 5	-85	mmgt	M, bt, eb, ro	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona inflata</i> (Schmidt, 1868) [<i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera</i>]	5, 7, 12, 13		adp	M, bt	32, 389
<i>Haliclona irregularis</i> (Czerniavsky, 1880) [? <i>Ulosa stuposa</i> , ? <i>Haliclonissa digitata</i>]	24, 49	-22	? ● p, ? clm	M, bt, zc	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona simulans</i> (Johnston, 1842) [<i>Adocia densa</i> , <i>Isodictya pallida</i> , <i>Reniera</i>]	5		clmm	M, bt	32, 249, 389
<i>Haliclona tubulifera</i> (Swartschewsky, 1905) [<i>Adocia</i> , <i>Reniera</i>]	3		● p	M, bt	32, 249, 389
Spongillidae					
<i>Ephydatia fluviatilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1759)	34, *68		(hpta)	L, 2.5‰, bt	32, 374, 389
DENDROCRATIDA					
Dysideidae					
<i>Dysidea fragilis</i> (Montagu, 1818) [<i>Spongia</i> , <i>Spongelia</i>]	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7	-40	clmm	M, bt, mb, ps, ro	32, 84, 389
CALCAREA					
LEUCOLENIDA					
Sycettidae					
<i>Sycon ciliatum</i> (Fabricius, 1780) [<i>S. coronata</i>]	23, 24, 27, 28, 49, 50	0-180	aamswp	M, bt, eb, ph, ro	198, 249
CNIDARIA					
HYDROZOA					
CAPTATA					
Hydridae					
<i>Hydra viridissima</i> Pallas, 1766 [<i>Chlorohydara</i>]	71, 88, 93		(k)	L, 5‰, bt	374, 389
Cladonematidae					
<i>Cladonema radiatum</i> Dujardin, 1843	12		ampip	M, bt-p	91, 249, 389
Corymorphidae					
<i>Corymorpha nutans</i> Sars, 1835 [<i>C. sarsi</i>]	7	10-100	anam	M, bt-p, eb, r	160, 249, 333, 389
Corynidae					
<i>Coryne pusilla</i> (Gaertner, 1774)	11, 16		namwp	M, bt-p	91, 389
<i>Sarsia tubulosa</i> (Sars, 1835) [<i>S. mirabilis</i> , <i>Coryne</i> , <i>Syncoryne</i>]	7, 16, 49		aanamp	M, bt-p	249, 319, 352, 389
Moerisiidae					
<i>Odessia maeotica</i> (Ostroumoff, 1896) [<i>Ostroumovia</i> , <i>Pontia</i> , <i>Moerisia</i>]	7, 71, 78		lm, ? Rc	M-B, 25‰, bt-p, ■	297, 299, 300, 319, 373, 374, 376, 383
<i>Moerisia inkermanica</i> Paltschikowa-Ostroumowa, 1925 [<i>Ostroumovia</i>]	*69, 71, *79, 84, 88		ampip	M-B-L, 40‰, bt-p	249, 317, 374, 376, 386, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Protohydryidae				
<i>Protohydra leuckarti</i> Greeff, 1870 [<i>P. squamata</i>] LEPTOTHECATA (CONICA)	*79, 96	0-1	cbm	249, 378, 389
Aglaopheniidae				
<i>Aglaophenia pluma</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	7, 16	0-100	amwp	91, 249, 295, 389
Kirchenpaueriidae				
<i>Kirchenpaueria halecioides</i> (Alder, 1859) [<i>Plumularia</i>] Blackfordiidae	7, 24		SK	249, 389
<i>Blackfordia virginica</i> Mayer, 1910 [<i>Campanulina pontica</i>] Campanulinidae	71, *79, 84, *86, 88		nami, i	160, 249, 374, 389
<i>Opercularella lacerata</i> (Johnston, 1847) [<i>Campanulina tenuis</i>] <i>Phiadella quadrata</i> (Forbes, 1848) [<i>Campanulina repens</i>]	7 29, 49	0-20 -10	bam amip, ? SK	249, 295, 389 249
Sertulariidae				
<i>Sertularella polyzonias</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) FILIFERA	3, 7, 12, 16	0-100	SK, ? K	67, 91, 249, 295, 389
Bougainvilliidae				
<i>Garveia franciscana</i> (Torrey, 1902) [<i>Bougainvillia megas, Perigonimus</i>] <i>Bougainvillia muscus</i> (Van Beneden, 1844) [<i>B. ramosa, Perigonimus</i>]	*69, 84 7		cst, amip, i amip, ? SK	102, 249, 252, 295 249, 295, 389
Oceaniidae (Clavidae)				
<i>Clava multicornis</i> (Forskål, 1775) [<i>C. squamata</i>] <i>Cordylophora caspia</i> (Pallas, 1771) [<i>C. lacustris</i>]	7 58, *68, *69, *78, *79, 84, 88, 93, 94, 96		bam namnz, i, Rc, ? SK	295, 389 84, 249, 374, 389
Eudendriidae				
<i>Eudendrium ramosum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Tubularia</i>] <i>Eudendrium</i> cf. <i>merulum</i> Watson, 1985	7 7	-10 0-1, 15	SK amiswp	249, 298, 389 321
Hydractiniidae				
<i>Hydractinia carnea</i> Sars, 1846 [<i>Podocoryna</i>]	5, 7, *69	0-70	amwp	67, 84, 249, 317, 319, 331, 374, 389
Rathkeidae				
<i>Rathkea octopunctata</i> (Sars, 1835) LIMNOMEDUSAE (LIMNOPOLYPAE)	7, 29		cbma, (? i)	160, 249, 319, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Microhydrulidae				
<i>Microhydrula pontica</i> Valkanov, 1965			clm	M, 10-20‰, bt 391, 392
Olindiasidae (Olindiidae)				
<i>Craspedacusta sowerbyi</i> Lankester, 1880 [<i>C. ryderi</i>]	34		(k), i	L, is, bt-p 386, 389
? <i>Olindias phosphorica</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1841)	96		lm	M, p, r 281
? <i>Maeotias marginata</i> (Modeer, 1791) [<i>M. inexpectata</i>]			clm	M-B, p 281
PROBOSCOIDA				
Campanulariidae				
<i>Orthopyxis integra</i> (MacGillivray, 1842) [<i>Campanularia integriformis</i>]	7, *69	1-60	amip, ? K	M, bt, eb, r 249, 295, 374, 389
<i>Campanularia volubilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>C. v. var. urceolata</i> , <i>C. urceolata</i>]	11, 12, 16	5-100	amp	M, bt, eb 91, 249, 389
<i>Clytia hemisphaerica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>C. johnstoni</i> , <i>Campanularia</i>]	3, 11, 12, 16	0-15	amp, ? SK	M, bt-p, ph, ro 67, 91, 249, 389
<i>Gonothyrax loveni</i> (Allman, 1859) [<i>Laomedea</i> , <i>Obelia</i>]	3, 7	0-30	bamswp, ? K	M, bt, ep-mb 68, 249, 295, 389
<i>Hartlaubella gelatinosa</i> (Pallas, 1766) [<i>Laomedea bicuspidata</i> , <i>Obelia</i>]	7		amp	M, bt, r 84, 249, 389
<i>Laomedea angulata</i> Hincks, 1861 [<i>Obelia</i>]	7, *69		am	M, 12‰, bt, r 84, 249, 389
<i>Obelia longissima</i> (Pallas, 1766) [<i>Laomedea</i>]	7	0-100	SK	M, bt-p, eb 84, 160, 249, 389
SCYPHOZOA				
SEMAEOSTOMEAE				
Ulmaridae				
<i>Aurelia aurita</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	1-22, 29, 69, 84, 88	0-100	K	M, p 91, 160, 287, 319, 374, 389
RHIZOSTOMEAE				
Rhizostomatidae				
<i>Rhizostoma pulmo</i> (Macri, 1778)	1-22, 29, *69		namrs	M, p 91, 160, 287, 319, 374, 389
STAUROMEDUSAE				
Kishinouyeidae				
<i>Lucernariopsis campanulata</i> Lamouroux, 1815 [<i>Lucernaria</i>]	12, 21, 24	0-20	clm	M, bt, ep, slc, ph 91, 249, 389
ANTHOZOA: HEXACORALIA				
ACTINIARIA				
Actiniidae				
<i>Actinia equina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>A. e. var. zonata</i>]	1-22, 24, 69	0-38	eamiwp	M, bt, ep, lr, slr, sg 31, 91, 249, 295, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Diadumeniidae					
? <i>Diadumene lineata</i> (Verrill, 1869) [<i>Actinothoe clavata</i>]	24, 49	0-15	SK, i	M-B, bt, 0.5-35‰, is	355
Sagartiidae					
<i>Actinothoe clavata</i> (Ilmoni, 1830) [<i>A. angulicomma</i> , <i>Cyliste viduata</i>]	7, 12, 13, 16, 25, 26, 69	1-20	clm	M, bt, ep, mc, sg, s	84, 91, 249, 295, 389
CERIANTHARIA					
Cerianthidae					
<i>Pachycerianthus solitarius</i> (Rapp, 1829) [<i>Cerianthus vestitus</i>]	2	60-175	lm	M, bt, shb, phs	249
CTENOPHORA					
ATENTACULATA					
BEROIDA					
Beroiidae					
<i>Beroe ovata</i> Bruguère, 1789	1-22, 29		amiwp, i	M, p, is	160, 162, 200
TENTACULATA					
CYDIPPIDA					
Pleurobrachiidae					
<i>Pleurobrachia rhodops</i> Chun, 1879 [<i>P. pileus</i> , <i>P. rhododactyla</i>]	7, 10-17, 29, *69	0-100	• p	M, p, eb	91, 317, 319, 374
LOBATA					
Bolinopsidae					
<i>Bolinopsis vitrea</i> (L. Agassiz, 1860)	3, 7, 29		est, amip, ? i	M, p	292, 355
<i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i> A. Agassiz, 1865 [<i>Leucothoe multicornis</i> , <i>Mnemia maccradyi</i>]	1-22, 29, 69	0-25	vek, ? K, i	M, p, is, sb	65, 160, 194, 195, 196, 197, 199, 201
PLATHELMINTHES					
TURBELLARIA					
ACOELA					
Convolutidae					
<i>Convoluta hypparchia</i> Peryaslavzewa, 1893 [<i>C. festiva</i>]	7, *69, *79		m	M, bt	84, 374
Otocelididae					
<i>Otocelis rubropunctata</i> (Schmidt, 1852) Dising, 1862	7, 25, 26	-18	neamj	M, bt, pe-ps, ep	386
Taurididae					
<i>Taurida fulvomaculata</i> (Ax, 1959) [<i>Convoluta</i>]	7		m	M, bt, ep, ps	392
MACROSTOMIDA					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Macrostomidae					
<i>Macrostomum appendiculatum</i> (O. Fabricius, 1826)	77		clm	? B-L, 50‰, bt, eh	374, 389
POLYCLADIDA					
Leptoplanidae					
<i>Leptoplana tremellaris</i> (Müller, 1774) Örsted, 1843	5, *69, 84, *86		ce	M, bt	67, 374
Prosthiostomidae					
<i>Prosthiostomum siphunculius</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1818) Lang, 1884	3		clm	M, bt	67, 389
Stylochidae					
<i>Stylochus tauricus</i> Jakubova, 1909 [<i>Stycoplana</i>]	5		m	M, bt	67, 389
RHABDOCOELA					
Dalyelliidae					
<i>Gieystoria expedita</i> (von Hofsten, 1907) [<i>Dalyellia</i>]	*68, 71, 76, *86, 88		(pat)	L, 12‰, bt	374, 389
Karkinorhynchidae					
<i>Baltoplana valkanovi</i> Ax, 1959	7		m	M, 12‰, bt	392
Polycystitidae					
<i>Acrorhynchides reprobatus</i> (Pereyaslawzewa, 1892) Strand, 1928 [Graff, 1905]	*69		m	M, bt	374, 389
<i>Gyratrix hermaphroditus</i> Ehrenberg, 1831 [<i>Gyrator</i>]	*68, *69, 71		SK	M-L, 5‰, bt, eh	374, 389
<i>Polycystis naegellii</i> Kölliker, 1845	7, 24		clm	M, bt	203, 252
<i>Rogneda minuta</i> Uljanin, 1870 [<i>Polycystis</i>]	*69		clm	M, 12‰, bt, ph-ps	374, 389
<i>Rogneda polyrhabdota</i> Ax, 1959	7		m	M, bt	392
Promesostomidae					
<i>Promesostoma marmoratum</i> (Schultze, 1851) v. Graff, 1882	*69, *79		bam	M, 8‰, bt	374, 389
SERIATA					
Coelogygnoporidae					
<i>Coelogygnopora biarmata</i> Steinböck, 1924	7, 25, 51	1-2	clm, ? bam	M, bt, sep, sls, ps, eh	203, 249, 388, 389
<i>Coelogygnopora tenuiformis</i> Karling, 1966	7, 25, 51		pnep	M, bt, sls, ps, r	203, 252
Monocelididae					
<i>Archilina endostyla</i> Ax, 1959	7, 25, 51	0.5-2	m	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	203, 252
<i>Monocelis longiceps</i> (Dugès, 1830)	*69		clm	M, 2‰, bt	374, 389
<i>Pseudomonocelis ophiocephala</i> (Schmidt, 1861), Meixner, 1943	7, 25, 51	1-2	m	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	203, 252
Otoplanidae					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Archotoplana holotricha</i> Ax, 1956	6, 7, 51		m, ? cm	M, bt, ep, sls, ps	203, 252	
<i>Otoplana bosporana</i> Ax, 1959	7		m	M, bt, ep, sls, ps	392	
<i>Parotoplanella progermaria</i> Ax, 1956	6, 7, 51	0-1	m, ? lm	M, bt, sep, ls, sls, ps	203, 252	
<i>Postbursoplana fibulata</i> Ax, 1955	6, 7, 25	2	m, ? lm	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	203, 252	
<i>Postbursoplana pontica</i> Ax, 1959	7		● p	M, bt	392	
<i>Pseudosyritys subterranea</i> (Ax, 1951) Ax, 1956 [<i>Otoplana</i>]	7, 35		clm	M-B, bt, sep, ls, ps	389	
<i>Triporoplana synsiphonioides</i> Ax, 1956	7, 25, 51	0.5	lm	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	203, 252	
Dendrocoelidae						
<i>Dendrocoelum lacteum</i> (Müller, 1774)	58, *68		(h)	L, 2‰, bt, ph	206, 374, 389	
Dugesiiidae						
<i>Dugesia polychroa</i> (Schmidt, 1861) [<i>Planaria</i>]	*68		(h)	L, 0.5‰, bt	374, 389	
NEMERTINI						
ANOPLA						
PALAEONEMERTINI						
Cephalothricidae						
<i>Cephalothrix arenaria</i> Hylbon, 1957			clm	M, bt, ps	249	
<i>Cephalothrix linearis</i> (Rathke, 1799) [<i>C. bioculata</i>]	27, 28	40-120	bam	M, bt, shb, s	249	
<i>Cephalothrix ruffronis</i> (Johnston, 1837)	27, 28	40-120	clm	M, bt, shb, s	249	
Tubulanidae						
<i>Carinina heterosoma</i> G. I. Müller, 1965	26, 27	5-70	● p	M, bt, s, ep-mb	249	
HETERONEMERTINI						
Cerebratulidae						
<i>Cerebratulus marginatus</i> Renier, 1804	27, 28	40-120	abamp	M, bt, phs, shb, s	249	
<i>Cerebratulus ventrosulcatus</i> Bürger, 1892	26, 27, 28	6-120	m	M, bt, s, eb	249	
Lineidae						
<i>Lineus bilineatus</i> (Renier, 1804)			bamp	M, bt, sl	249	
<i>Lineus ruber</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	49		nam	M, bt, sl, mc, ro	249	
<i>Ramphogordius lacteus</i> Ratke, 1843 [<i>Lineus</i>]	*69	2-65	clp, ? clm	M, bt, mb-eb	249, 374, 389	
<i>Notospermus geniculatus</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828) [<i>Lineus</i>]			lmnz	M, bt	249	
<i>Micrura fasciolata</i> Ehrenberg, 1828	1-22, 27, 28	18-125	clm	M, bt, mb-eb, s	249	
<i>Pontolineus arenarius</i> Müller et Scripcariu, 1964	25	8-16	● p	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	249	

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Pussylineus gabriellae</i> Corrêa, 1956			m	M, bt 249
ENOPLA				
HOPLONEMERTINI				
Amphiporidae				
<i>Amphiporus bioculatus</i> McIntosh, 1874			bap, ? bam	M, bt 249
<i>Amphiporus lactifloreus</i> (Johnston, 1828)			bam	M, bt, sl 249
<i>Zygonemertes maslovskyi</i> (Czerniavsky, 1880)	50		● p	M, bt, lr 249
Cratenemertidae				
<i>Nippomemertes pulchra</i> (Johnston, 1837) [<i>Amphiporus</i>]			baap	M, bt 249
Emplectonematidae				
<i>Emplectonema gracile</i> (Johnston, 1837) [<i>Eunemertes</i>]	3, 24	0-10	bamp	M, bt, ep, ro 67, 249, 389
Otothyphonemertidae				
<i>Otothyphonemertes antipai</i> G. I. Müller, 1968	51	0.2-1	● p	M, bt, ls, sep 249
Tetrastemmatidae				
<i>Prostoma graecense</i> (Böhlig, 1892) [<i>Tetrastemma</i>]	*68, *69		(sk)	L-B, 1%, bt 374, 389
<i>Tetrastemma baescui</i> G. I. Müller, 1962	5, 24	0.5-8	● p	M, bt, lr, slr, ep 249
<i>Tetrastemma candidum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) [<i>Prostoma</i>]	3, 5	0-55	anamp	M, bt, mb 67, 249, 389
<i>Tetrastemma coronatum</i> (Quantrefages, 1846)	26, 27	4-40-120	clm	M, bt, s, hb-eb 249
<i>Tetrastemma longissimum</i> Bürger, 1895 [? nom. dubium]			clm	M, bt 249
<i>Tetrastemma melanocephalum</i> (Johnston, 1837)	3, 5, 27	40-70	neaminz	M, bt, s, mb-eb 67, 249
<i>Tetrastemma vermiculus</i> (Quantrefages, 1846) [<i>Prostomatella</i>]	24	0-40	nam	M, bt, slr, mb 249
GASTROTRICHA				
CHAETONOTOIDEA				
Chaetonotidae				
<i>Aspidiophorus mediterraneus</i> Remane, 1927	7, 51	0.5-2	namsep	M, bt, sep, ls, eh 315, 389, 390
<i>Chaetonotus maximus</i> Ehrenberg, 1831	24, 35, 49		K	M (B-L), bt, eh, l, ls 249
<i>Chaetonotus similis</i> Zelinka, 1889	96		(k)	L-B, 8-18%, bt 249
<i>Halichaetonotus decipiens</i> Remane, 1829 [<i>Chaetonotus</i>]	7, 35		nam	M, gw, ls 315, 389
<i>Halichaetonotus marinus</i> (Giard, 1904) [<i>Chaetonotus pleuracanthus</i>]	16, 35		clm	M, gw, ls, r 249, 389
<i>Heterolepidoderma marinum</i> Remane, 1926	16, 51		clm	M, bt, l, sl 249, 389
Xenotrichulidae				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Heteroxenotrichula pygmaea</i> Remane, 1934 [<i>Xenotrichula</i>]	7, 35		nap, ? SK	249
<i>Xenotrichula intermedia</i> Remane, 1934 [<i>X. beauchampi</i>]	12, 16, 18, 35		nam, ? SK	249, 389, 390
MACRODASYOIDEA				
Dactylopolodidae				
<i>Dendrodasya ponticus</i> Valkanov, 1957	7, 35		pm	249, 389, 390
Macrodasidae				
<i>Macrodasys africanus</i> Remane, 1950 [<i>M. a. var. ponticus</i> Valkanov, 1957]	7, 25, 35, 51	0-2	api	249, 315
Thaumastodermatidae				
<i>Acanthodasya aculeatus</i> Remane, 1927	16, 25, 51	0-6	namni	315, 389, 390
Turbanellidae				
<i>Turbanella cornuta</i> Remane, 1925	7, 25, 35, 51	0-6	clm	249, 389, 390
<i>Turbanella pontica</i> Valkanov, 1957	7, 35, 51		● p	249, 315, 390
NEMATODA (NEMATA)				
ADENOPHOREA				
ENOPLIDA				
Anoplostomatidae				
<i>Anoplostoma viviparum</i> (Bastian, 1865)	7, 25, 27, 28	10, 120	kelm	121, 344
Anticomidae				
<i>Anticoma acuminata</i> (Eberth, 1863) Stekhoven, 1950	7		aminz	121
Encheliidae				
<i>Symplocostoma ponticum</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 25	12-40-	m	252, 347
<i>Symplocostoma tenuicolle</i> (Eberth, 1863) [<i>S. longocolle</i>]	7, 23, 24, 25, 76		amswp	121, 341, 344
<i>Polygastrophora hexabulba</i> (Filipjev, 1918)	16, 25	8-9	mnz, ? amnz	252, 341, 344
<i>Eurystomina ornata</i> (Eberth, 1863)	7, 16, 24		bam	341, 344
<i>Eurystomina assimilis</i> (de Man, 1876)	7, 23, 24, 25, 27		namrs	121, 341, 344
Enoplidae				
<i>Enoplus littoralis</i> Filipjev, 1918	1-22, 35, 46, 49, 51	0.2-0.4	clm	341, 344
<i>Enoplus maeoticus</i> Filipjev, 1916	1-22, 35, 51		em, ? m	344
<i>Enoplus quadridentatus</i> Berlin, 1853 [<i>E. euxinus</i> , <i>E. hirtus</i>]	7-16, 24, 25	4, 80	clm	121, 344, 389
<i>Enoplus schulzi</i> Gerlach, 1952	7, 13, 35		cp	363
Ironidae				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Trissonchulus benepapillosus</i> (Schulz, 1935) [<i>Dolicholaimus</i> , <i>Syringolaimus</i>]	7, 35		namni	362, 386, 389
<i>Trissonchulus oceanus</i> Cobb, 1920 [<i>Dolicholaimus nudus</i>]	7, 35		cm	362
<i>Dolicholaimus platonovae</i> Stoikov, 1979	7, 35, 51		● p	343, 344
<i>Syringolaimus caspersi</i> Gerlach, 1951	7, 76		cp	121, 344, 389
Leptosomatidae				
<i>Leptosomatides euxinus</i> Filipjev, 1918	3, 28	25-, 200	cp	252, 347
<i>Leptosomatium sabangense</i> Steiner, 1915 [<i>L. bacillatum</i> , <i>Phanoglene</i>]	10, 28	0-10-90	aanamip	252, 338, 344
<i>Leptosomatium punctatum</i> (Eberth, 1863)	3, 28	60-100	m	252, 347
<i>Pseudocella savelfjevi</i> (Filipjev, 1927) [<i>Enoploides</i>]	7, 25, 51		cp	344
Oncholaimidae				
<i>Viscosia cobbi</i> Filipjev, 1918	16, 20, 25	8-10, 150	clm	252, 338, 344
<i>Viscosia glabra</i> (Bastian, 1865)	7, 25	5-10, 120	cclm	121, 344
<i>Viscosia minor</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 25		● p	344
<i>Pontonema zernovi</i> (Filipjev, 1916) [<i>Oncholaimus vulgaris</i> , <i>Parancholaimus</i>]	25, 27	-60, 150	● p	341, 344
<i>Oncholaimellus mediterraneus</i> Stekhoven, 1942	13, 35		cm, ? clm	362
<i>Oncholaimus brevicaudatus</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 35, 51	230	calm	340, 344
<i>Oncholaimus campylocerooides</i> De Koninck & Schuurmans Stekhoven, 1933	2, 35, 51	80-150	cclm	121, 340, 344
<i>Oncholaimus conicauda</i> Filipjev, 1929	7, 35, 51	0.3-1	clmwi	252, 341, 344
<i>Oncholaimus dujardini</i> de Man, 1878	3, 7, 25, 35, 51	0-8, -230	namnz	121, 344
Oxystominidae				
<i>Oxystomina clavicauda</i> (Filipjev, 1918)	16, 25	20	● p	341, 344
<i>Oxystomina elongata</i> (Bütschli, 1874) [<i>Oxystomatina</i>]	7, 25	10-25	cclm	341, 344
<i>Halalaimus ponticus</i> Filipjev, 1922	3, 28	68, -100	● p	252, 347
<i>Nemanema filiforme</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Oxystoma</i>]	10, 27	40	em	252, 347
Rhabdodemanidae				
<i>Rhabdodemanina pontica</i> Platonova, 1965	27, 28	30-150	● p	344
Thoracostomopsidae				
<i>Enoploides amphioxi</i> Filipjev, 1918	25	8-9	em	341, 344
<i>Enoploides alexandrae</i> Uzunov, 1974	6, 7, 35	0.8	● p	344, 361
<i>Enoploides brevis</i> Filipjev, 1918	28	75-120	● p	344
<i>Enoploides cirrhatus</i> Filipjev, 1918 [<i>Brachionus</i>]	7, 12, 16, 25, 27, 28	0-60	cp	341, 344

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Enoploides fluviatilis</i> Mikoletzky, 1923 [<i>Brachionus</i>]	58, 59, 60		? p	338
<i>Enoploides hirsutus</i> Filipjev, 1918	10, 27, 28	4-100	● p	252, 344
<i>Mesacanthion conicum</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Enoplolaimus</i>]	7, 25, 27, 28	80	● p	252, 347
<i>Oxyonchus dubius</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Enoplolaimus</i>]	17, 28		em	252, 347
Tobriliidae				
<i>Tobrillus gracilis</i> (Bastian, 1865) [<i>Trilobus</i>]	*68, *79, 88		(e)	374, 389
Triploidiidae				
<i>Triploides marinus</i> (Bütschli, 1874)	7, 23, 28, 33	0-100	bam	121, 389
<i>Bathylaimus australis</i> Cobb, 1894 [<i>B. assimilis</i> , <i>B. ponticus</i>]	7, 25		am, ? ham	121, 344
<i>Bathylaimus cobbi</i> Filipjev, 1922	10, 25, 27, 28	-100	● p	341, 344
<i>Bathylaimus filipjevi</i> Stoikov, 1976 ?	7, 35	0.4	● p	340, 344
DORYLAIMIDA				
Dorylaimidae (Qudsianematidae)				
<i>Dorylaimus otmaniensis</i> Uzunov, 1974	13		● p	361
<i>Dorylaimus stagnalis</i> Dujardin, 1845	58, 59, 60		(e)	337
<i>Eudorylaimus carteri</i> (Bastian, 1865)	58, 59, 60		(e)	337
<i>Eudorylaimus filipjevi</i> (Gerlach, 1951) [<i>Dorylaimus</i>]	7, 24		● Er, p	121
<i>Crocodylaimus flavomaculatus</i> (von Linstow, 1876) [<i>Laimidorus</i>]	58, 59, 60		(e)	337
CHROMADORIDA				
Ceramonematidae				
<i>Pselonema annulatum</i> (Filipjev, 1922) [<i>Ceratonema</i> , <i>Steineria</i>]	3, 28	80-100	namsp	252, 347
Chromadoridae				
<i>Chromadorina bioculata</i> (Schultze, 1857) [<i>Chromadora</i>]	*68		cp, (csee)	374, 389
<i>Chromadora nudicapitata</i> (Bastian, 1865) [<i>Ch. quadrilineata</i>]	7, 24		amnz	121
<i>Chromadorita demaniana</i> Filipjev, 1922	25	80	cp, ? clp	121, 389
<i>Chromadorita leuckarti</i> (de Man, 1876)	7	-15, -140	cp	121, 344, 389
<i>Dichromadora cephalata</i> (Steiner, 1916) [<i>Chromadora cricophana</i>]	7, 12, 25, 35, 51	0-2	clpnz	252, 338, 344
<i>Hypodontolaimus balticus</i> (Schneider, 1906)	11, 35		bap	252, 362
<i>Neochromadora poecilosomoides</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Chromadora</i> , <i>Dichromadora</i>]	7, 51	-140	clm, ? vclm	252, 347
<i>Neochromadora sabulicola</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Chromadora</i>]	3, 7, 10, 20, 24, 25	120	p, ? cp	252, 342, 344
<i>Ptycholaimellus ponticus</i> (Filipjev, 1922) [<i>Hypodontolaimus</i>]	7, 25, 35, 51	0.6-1, 50	clm, ? cclm	344

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Spilophorella euxina</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 25	150	em	M, bt, sl, ps, eb	121, 389
Cyatholaimidae					
<i>Cyatholaimus gracilis</i> (Ebert, 1863) [C. demani]	7-16, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28	-100, 120	clm	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, s, r	121, 344
<i>Paracanthonchus caecus</i> (Bastian, 1865) [<i>P. abnormis</i> , <i>Cyatholaimus</i>]	3, 7, 10, 13, 20, 27, 35	0-73, 150	namnz	M, bt, eb, eu, ph, ps, s	342, 344, 362
Ethmolaimidae					
<i>Ethmolaimus multipapillatus</i> Paramonov, 1926	76		● p	M, bt, eh-70%,	121, 389
Desmodoridae					
<i>Acanthopharynx similis</i> (Algén, 1932) [<i>Desmodora</i> , ? <i>Sabatieria ornata</i>]	11, 35		pinz	M, bt, l, ps, gw, if	362
<i>Chromaspirina pontica</i> Filipjev, 1918	16, 25		cm	M, bt, sls, slc, ze, ps	252, 341, 344
<i>Desmodora pontica</i> (Filipjev, 1922)	3, 10, 25, 27, 28		clm	M, bt, eb, eu, ps, pe, r	252, 344
<i>Prodesmodora circulata</i> (Micoletzky, 1913)	58, 59, 60		lm, (e)	M-B, bt, 0.5-2%	337
<i>Metachromadora arenaria</i> Stoikov, 1979	25	8-9	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, sls	343
<i>Metachromadora cystoseirae</i> Filipjev, 1918 [? Gerlach et Riemann, 1973]	24		● p	M, bt, sl, slc	252, 347
<i>Metachromadora macroutera</i> Filipjev, 1918	16, 25	8-9, 35	● p	M, bt, ep-mb, sl, sls	252, 338, 344
<i>Onyx perfectus</i> Cobb, 1891	7, 25	15-17	clm	M, bt, ep, sl, sls	252, 347
<i>Spirinia parasitifera</i> (Bastian, 1865) [? <i>S. zosterae</i> Filipjev, 1918]	7, 24	3.5	namim	M, bt, ep, sls, slc, ze	252, 344
<i>Spirinia sabulicola</i> (Filipjev, 1918)	3, 10, 17, 27, 28		● p	M, bt, eu, ms, phs, r	252, 344
Desmoscolecidae					
<i>Desmoscolex laevis</i> Kreis, 1938 [<i>D. minutus</i>]	7, 78	1-100	namim	M, bt, eb, eh, s, phs	252, 344, 347
<i>Tricoma bacescui</i> (Paladian & Andriescu, 1963) [<i>Desmoscolex</i> , <i>Qadricoma</i>]	28	75-120	● p	M, bt, shb, phs, r	252, 344
Epsilonematidae					
<i>Bathypsilonema pustulatum</i> Gerlach, 1952 [<i>Epsilonema pustulatum ponticum</i>]	7, 35, 51	0.2-0.6	cm, ? clm	M, bt, l, ls, gw, r	252, 344
Leptolaimidae					
<i>Camacolaimus pontolittoralis</i> Uzunov, 1977	11, 35		● p	M, bt, ls, gw	362
Meyliidae					
<i>Quadricoma euryricus</i> (Filipjev, 1922) [<i>Desmolorenzenia</i> , <i>Desmoscolex</i>]	10, 11, 25, 28	5-90	● p	M, bt, eb, sls, phs	252, 344, 347
<i>Quadricoma loricata</i> Filipjev, 1922 [<i>Tricoma</i>]	10, 28	50-100	● p	M, bt, hb, phs, s	252, 344
<i>Quadricoma steineri</i> Filipjev, 1922 [<i>Tricoma euxinica</i>]	7, 25	-50	● p	M, bt, mb, ps-pe	252, 347
Monoposthiidae					
<i>Monoposthia costata</i> (Bastian, 1865)	23, 24, 25		ami	M, bt, ep, l, sl, ph	252, 344, 347
<i>Nudora steineri</i> (Steiner, 1921)	13, 35		cp	M, bt, l, gw, if, ps	252, 362

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Selachinematidae				
<i>Choanolaimus psammophilus</i> de Man, 1880	11, 35		clm	M, bt, l, gw, if, ps 252, 362
<i>Halichoanolaimus dolichurus</i> Ssaweljev, 1912 [<i>Hypodentolaimus filicauda</i>]	7, 24	1-4, 140	clm	M, bt, slc, ph, phs, r 252, 344
<i>Halichoanolaimus robustus</i> (Bastian, 1865) [<i>H. clavicauda</i>]	7, 25	6-10, 150	neaminz	M, bt, sep, sls, ps 252, 338, 344
MONHYSTERIDA				
Axonolaimidae				
<i>Axonolaimus ponticus</i> Filipjev, 1918	1-22, *68, 71, *78, *79, 84, 88, 93, 94	0-100	clm	M, bt, eh-1-20%, sl, eb, eu, ps, pe, ph 121, 338, 344, 374, 389
<i>Axonolaimus setosus</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 24, 25	-40	clm	M, bt, mb, ps, pe, slc 252, 344
Comesomatidae				
<i>Comesoma stenocephalum</i> Filipjev, 1918	3, 7, 10, 20, 27, 28		● p	M, bt, ms, phs, sls, eu 252, 344
<i>Sabatieria abyssalis</i> (Filipjev, 1918)	10, 27, 28	50-100	mmi	M, bt, hb, ms, phs, pe 252, 338, 344
<i>Sabatieria celtica</i> Southern, 1914 [<i>S. cupida</i>]	7, 25, 26, 76	8	amnep, ? ce	M, bt, sls, s, ps, pe 252, 338, 344
<i>Sabatieria pulchra</i> (Schneider, 1906) [<i>S. vulgaris</i>]	24, 25	6-10	aam	M, bt, ep, sl, ps, ph 252, 338, 344
Linhomoieidae				
<i>Paralinhomoieus filiformis</i> (Filipjev, 1918) [<i>Linhomoieus</i>]	25, 28	20-100	cp	M, bt, hb, sls, phs 252, 347
<i>Paralinhomoieus tenuicaudatus</i> (Bütschli, 1874) [<i>P. ostracarium</i>]	7, 25, 76		clm	M, bt, sls, ps, phs, r 252, 344
<i>Terschellingia longicaudata</i> de Man, 1907 [<i>T. antonovi</i>]	7, 10, 25, 26		aamni	M, bt, hb, pe, ph, ps 252, 338, 344
<i>Terschellingia pontica</i> Filipjev, 1918	7, 26, 27, 28	15-100	● p	M, bt, eb, sl, s, pe 252, 341, 344
Monhysteridae				
<i>Monhystera ampullocauda</i> Paramonov, 1926	51		● p	M, bt, ps, ls 344
<i>Monhystera collaris</i> Filipjev, 1922	7, 26		p	M, bt, sl, pe, s, (sls), r 252, 344
<i>Monhystera filiformis</i> Bastian, 1865	7, 76		clm, ? K	M, bt, eh-0-70%, eu 3, 121, 344, 389
<i>Monhystera parva</i> (Bastian, 1865) [<i>M. antarctica</i> , <i>M. heteroparva</i> , <i>M. kessinensis</i>]	7		amni	M, bt 121, 389
<i>Monhystera rotundicapitata</i> Filipjev, 1922	7, 24	-10	● p	M, bt, ep, sls, slc 252, 342, 344
Sphaerolaimidae				
<i>Sphaerolaimus macrocirculus</i> Filipjev, 1918	10, 25, 27, 28	59	clm	M, bt, hb, s, pe, (ps) 252, 342, 344
<i>Sphaerolaimus ostreae</i> Filipjev, 1918 [<i>S. maeoticus</i>]	7, 25, 27	59	em, ? cm	M, bt, mb, ps, pe, r 252, 341, 344
Xyalidae				
<i>Daptonema oxycerca</i> (de Man, 1888) [<i>Monhystera, Theristus</i>]	7, 25		bam	M, bt, sep, sls 121, 389
<i>Paramonhystera elliptica</i> Filipjev, 1918 [<i>P. setosa, Leptogastrella</i>]	7, 25		lm, ? clm	M, bt, sl, ps, pe, ph 121, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Theristus littoralis</i> Filipjev, 1922	35, 46		• p	M, bt, l, sp, gw, if	252, 363
<i>Theristus longicaudatus</i> Filipjev, 1922	17, 20, 25		ccp	M, bt, sls, ps	525, 344
MONONCHIDA					
Mononchidae					
<i>Mononchus truncatus</i> Bastian, 1865	58, 59, 60		(e, ? k)	L, 0.5-2%, bt	337
SECERNENTEA					
DIPLOGASTERIDA					
Diplogasteridae					
<i>Diplogaster rivalis</i> (Leyding, 1854)	*68, *69, 93		(e)	L, 3%	374, 375, 389
RHABDITIDA					
Rhabditidae					
<i>Rhabditis marina</i> Bastian, 1865	11, 35		namnz, (e)	M (L), bt, l, gw, if	252, 362
TYLENCHIDA					
Criticonematidae					
<i>Mesocriconema xenoplax</i> (Raski, 1952)	48, 76		(ea, ? ha)	T	119
CEPHALORHYNCHA					
KINORHYNCHA					
CYCLORHAGIDA					
Centroderidae					
<i>Centroderes spinosus</i> (Reinhard, 1881) [<i>Echinoderes</i>]	1-22	-128	lm	M, bt, shb, phs, pe	229, 249
Echinoderidae					
<i>Echinoderes agigens</i> Bacescu, 1968 [<i>E. dujardinii</i>]	1-22, 24, 25, 35	1-8, 80	m	M, bt, ep, gw, if, s, slr	229, 249
HOMALORHAGIDA					
Pycnophyidae					
<i>Pycnophyes kielensis</i> Zelinka, 1928	25, 26	15-	clm	M, bt, sl, ps-pe, s	229, 249
<i>Pycnophyes ponticus</i> (Reinhard, 1881) [<i>Echinoderes</i>]	1-22, 26, 27	10-40	m	M, bt, mb, s, pe	229, 249
ROTIFERA (ROTATORIA)					
EUROTATORIA					
ADINETIDA					
Adinetidae					
<i>Adineta barbata</i> Janson, 1893	96		(sk)	L, l	209, 374

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Adineta vaga</i> (Davis, 1873)	96		(k)	L, 10‰	106, 209, 389
PHILODINIDA					
Habrotrochidae					
<i>Habrotrocha angusticollis</i> (Murray, 1905)	96		(k)	L	209, 373
Philodinidae					
<i>Philodina citrina</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	59, 60, *68		(k)	L, 2.3‰, l, ph	209, 280, 374, 389
<i>Philodina roseola</i> Ehrenberg, 1832 [<i>Ph. cinnabarina</i>]	33, 60, 96		lmnz, (k)	M-L, l, p, ph	106, 209, 389
<i>Rotaria citrina</i> (Ehrenberg, 1838)	96		(sk)	L-B, l	209
<i>Rotaria rotatoria</i> (Pallas, 1766) [<i>Rotifer vulgaris</i>]	*68, *79, *86, 96		(k), ? lmnz	L-B, 10‰, l, ph	209, 374, 389
<i>Rotaria tardigrada</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832)	49		? lm, (k)	L-B, 18‰, p, l, ph	146, 209
PLOIMA					
Asplanchnidae					
<i>Asplanchna girodi</i> de Guerne, 1888	78		(k)	L-B, p	209, 293
<i>Asplanchna priodonita</i> Gosse, 1850	77, 78, 79		? ace, (k)	L, 17.3‰, p, eu, sw	192, 193, 209, 293
<i>Asplanchna sieboldii</i> (Leydig, 1854)	59, 60		(k)	L, 5‰, p	280
Brachionidae					
<i>Anuraeopsis fissa</i> Gosse, 1851 [<i>A. hypelasma</i>]	60, *69, 71		? lmnz, (k)	L-B, 5‰, p	209, 280, 374, 389
<i>Brachionus angularis</i> Gosse, 1851	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 77, 78, 79, 80, 96		ham, (k)	L-B, 5‰, p, sw	193, 209, 280, 293, 374, 389
<i>Brachionus bennini</i> Leissing, 1924	78		(sk)	L, p, sw	209, 293
<i>Brachionus budapestinensis</i> Daday, 1885 [<i>B. similis</i>]	96		(ppta, ? k)	L, sw	209
<i>Brachionus calyciflorus</i> Pallas, 1776 [<i>B. amphicros</i> , <i>B. dorcas</i> , <i>B. pala</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 71, 77, 78, 79, 80, 96		? ham, (k)	L, 5‰, p, sw	160, 190, 193, 209, 278, 293, 374, 389
<i>Brachionus diversicornis</i> (Daday, 1883)	58, 78		clm, (sk)	L, p, sw	209, 278, 293
<i>Brachionus falcatus</i> Zacharias, 1898	59		(? sk)	L, p, sw	280
<i>Brachionus forficula</i> Wierzeyski, 1891	60		(ppta)	L, p, sw	280
<i>Brachionus leydigii</i> Cohn, 1862	59, 60, 96		(ppta)	L, p, sw	209, 280
<i>Brachionus plicatilis</i> Müller, 1786 [<i>B. mülleri</i>]	29, 33, 49, 58, 62, 64, *68, *69, 76, 77-*79, 84, *86, 88		ham, (k)	M-B, 6-20‰, eh, p	105, 106, 190, 207, 374, 389
<i>Brachionus quadridentatus</i> Hermann, 1783 [<i>B. bakeri</i>]	58-60, *68, 77, *86, 92, 96		ham, (k)	L, 3-16‰, l, p	209, 278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Brachionus rubens</i> Ehrenberg, 1838	69, 96		? kelm, (sk)	L, p	160, 209, 373

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Brachionus urceolaris</i> Müller, 1773	58, 60, *68, 77-80, 96		bam, (k)	190, 209, 293, 374, 389
<i>Kellicottia longispina</i> (Kellicott, 1879)	60		ace	279, 280
<i>Keratella cochlearis</i> (Gosse, 1851) [<i>Anuraea</i>]	7, 58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 77, 78, 79, 80		anamnp, (sk)	193, 209, 278, 280, 293, 317, 319, 389
<i>Keratella cruciformis</i> (Thompson, 1892)	29, 96		clip, (h)	209, 212
<i>Keratella hiemalis</i> Carlin, 1943	58, 60, 96		(hmat)	209, 280
<i>Keratella irregularis</i> (Lauterborn, 1898)	60, 96		(hmat, ? h)	209, 280
<i>Keratella quadrata</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Anuraea aculeata</i>]	58-60, *68, 71, 77, 78-80, 92		acc, (k)	190, 252, 278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Keratella tecta</i> (Gosse, 1851)	59, 78		cpwp, (k)	209, 293
<i>Keratella testudo</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832)	60, 96		lm, (hat)	209, 280
<i>Keratella tropica</i> (Apstein, 1907)	58, 59, 60		lm, (k), i	209, 210, 280
<i>Keratella valga</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834)	58, 59, 77, 79, 80, 96		lm, (k)	193, 209, 278
<i>Notholca acuminata</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832) [<i>N. bipalium</i> var. <i>acuminata</i>]	60, *69, 77-79, 85, *86, 88		neamj, (pat)	209, 258, 280, 374
<i>Notholca labis</i> Gosse, 1887	77		neamj, (dp)	258
<i>Notholca squamula</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Brachionus</i>]	58, 60		lmnz, (? k)	209, 252, 278, 280
<i>Notholca striata</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Brachionus</i>]	33, *69, *78		neamwp, (hna)	105, 106, 374, 389
Dicranophoridae				
<i>Dicranophorus bulgaricus</i> Althaus, 1957	16, 35		● p	2, 209, 249, 392
<i>Dicranophorus forcipatus</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Cercaria, Notommata</i>]	60, 96		bam, (k)	209, 280
<i>Dicranophorus rostratus</i> (Dixon-Nuttall & Freeman, 1902) [<i>Diglena coenura</i>]	*69		bam, (h)	374, 389
<i>Encentrum arenarium</i> Althaus, 1957	16, 35		● p	2, 209, 249, 392
<i>Encentrum marinum</i> (Dujardin, 1841) [<i>Furcularia</i>]	13, 32, 33, 35		cacpnz, (h)	106, 188, 209, 249, 389, 392
<i>Encentrum psammophilum</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 35		clip	2, 209, 249, 392
<i>Encentrum striatum</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 34, 35		calp	2, 209, 249, 392
<i>Encentrum valkanovi</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 35		● p	2, 111, 209, 249, 392
Euchlanidae				
<i>Euchlanis dilatata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	59, 60, *68, *79		namep, (k)	209, 374, 389
<i>Euchlanis lyra</i> Hudson, 1886	60		(? hmata)	280

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Euchlanis oropha</i> Gosse, 1887	59		(e, ? k)	L, 0.8‰, p, sw 280
<i>Euchlanis pyriformis</i> Gosse, 1851	77		(e, ? sk)	L, p, sw 258
<i>Tripleuchlanis plicata</i> (Levander, 1894)	59		namnep, (sk)	B-L, 0.8‰, p, sw 280
Lecanidae				
<i>Lecane althausi</i> Rudescu, 1960	35		(? sk)	L-B, l, ps, gw, if 209, 249
<i>Lecane closteroerca</i> (Schmarda, 1859)	58, 59, 60		cpnz, (sk)	L-B, 0.8-2‰, p, sw 209, 280
<i>Lecane copeis</i> (Harring & Myers, 1926) [<i>Monostyla</i>]	96		(hn)	L, p, sw 209, 372, 373
<i>Lecane cornuta</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Monostyla</i>]	*68, *69		(hn)	L, 3‰, l, ph, sw 249, 374, 389
<i>Lecane furcata</i> (Murray, 1913) [<i>Monostyla</i>]	58, 59, 60		(sk)	L, p, sw 209, 280
<i>Lecane lamellata</i> (Daday, 1893) [<i>Monostyla</i>]	76, *86, 88		(h)	L-B, 1-12‰, p 374, 389
<i>Lecane luna</i> (Müller, 1776) [<i>Cathypna</i>]	60, *68, *79		namnz, (? k)	L-B, 2‰, p 209, 280, 374, 389
<i>Lecane lunaris</i> (Ehrenberg, 1832)	59		(k)	L-B, 0.5-2‰, p 280
Lepadellidae				
<i>Lepadella ovalis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1786)	33		nam, (k)	L-B-M, 12‰, l 106, 209, 389
<i>Lepadella patella</i> (O. F. Müller, 1773) [<i>Metopidia oblonga</i> , <i>Squamella</i>]	59, 60, *68, 76, 96		antamp, ? sk	L-B, 2‰, p 209, 280, 374, 389
<i>Lepadella pontica</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 35		• p	M, bt, ps, sls 2, 249
<i>Colurella adriatica</i> Ehrenberg, 1831 [<i>Colurus leptus</i>]	13, 33, 58, 59, 60, *68, *69, *79, *86, 88, 90, 93, 94		namswp, ? SK, (k)	M-B-L, 15‰, p, l 106, 188, 209, 280, 374, 389
<i>Colurella colurus</i> (Ehrenberg, 1831) [<i>Monura loncheres</i> , <i>Colurus</i>]	13, 33, 35, *69, 76, *86, 88, 96		namswp, ? K, SK, (k)	M-B-L, 5-15‰, bt-p, l, gw, if 104, 106, 188, 209, 374, 389
<i>Colurella marinovi</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 16, 34		• p	M, bt, 12‰, l, ps 2, 209, 249, 389
? <i>Colurella monodactilos</i> Althaus, 1957 [? undetermined ciliate]	7, 25		• p	M, bt, 12‰, l, ps 2, 249, 392
<i>Colurella obtusa</i> (Gosse, 1886)	96		climnz, (k)	M-B-L, p, sw 209
<i>Colurella uncinata</i> (Müller, 1773) [<i>Colurus bicuspidatus</i> , <i>Brachionus</i>]			namnz, (k)	M-L, 9‰, p, l, ph 209
<i>Squatinnella longispinata</i> (Tatem, 1867) [<i>Stephanops</i>]	96		(hoa)	L-B, p 209, 373
Lindiidae				
<i>Lindia tecusa</i> Harring & Myers, 1922 [<i>Halodigma</i> , <i>Halolindia</i>]	49, *69		clip	M, 12-13‰, bt, l 111, 209, 249, 374
Microcodidae				
<i>Microcodon clavus</i> Ehrenberg, 1830	96		(h, ? k)	L, p, sw 209, 373, 374, 389
Mytilinidae				
<i>Mytilina ventralis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830) [<i>Salpina</i>]	59, 60, 96		(hno)	L-B, p, 0.8‰, sw, l 209, 280

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Notommatidae					
<i>Notommata aequalis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830) [<i>Notommata</i>]	*68, 96		(hnoa)	L, 1‰, p, sw	209, 372, 373, 389
<i>Cephalodella auriculata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1773) [<i>Diaschiza lacimulata</i>]	*68, 96		(hnoa)	L-B, bt, l, ph, sw	209, 249, 374
<i>Cephalodella catellina</i> (O. F. Müller, 1786)	33, 59, 60, *69, 96		K, (k)	L-B, 12‰, eh, bt, l	105, 107, 209, 249
<i>Cephalodella gibba</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830) [<i>Furcularia</i>]	96		lm, (k)	L, p	209, 389
<i>Cephalodella hoodii</i> (Gosse, 1886) [<i>Diaschiza</i>]	96		(ho)	L, p, ph	209, 372
<i>Cephalodella reitmanni</i> Donner, 1950	79, 96		(hop)	L	209, 373, 374
<i>Cephalodella ventripes</i> (Dixon-Nuttall, 1901)	59, 60		(hna)	L, p, sw	209, 280
Proalidae					
<i>Proales commutata</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 35		● p	M, bt, ps	2, 209, 249
<i>Proales halophila</i> Remane, 1929 [<i>P. globulifera halophilus</i>]	7, 35		clp	M-B, bt, l, ps, gw, if	104, 209, 249
<i>Proales reinhardtii</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834) [<i>Furcularia</i>]	13, 35		clp	M, bt-p, ps, ph, gw, if	188, 209, 212, 314
<i>Proales similis</i> de Beauchamp, 1907	32, 33		p, (hpta)	M-B, 10‰, bt, l	106, 209, 249, 389
Synchaetidae					
<i>Synchaeta baltica</i> Ehrenberg, 1834	*69		namnz	M-B, 12‰, p	317, 389
<i>Synchaeta cecilia</i> Rousset, 1902	59, 60, *69		bamswp	M-B, 0.5-12‰, p	105, 209, 280, 317, 374, 389
<i>Synchaeta gyryna</i> Hood, 1887	33		clp	M-B, 12‰, p	106, 389
<i>Synchaeta neapolitana</i> Rousset, 1902	29		clmz	M, p	109, 194, 201, 209
<i>Synchaeta oblonga</i> Ehrenberg, 1831	77		bam, (k)	L, 1.8‰, p	258
<i>Synchaeta pectinata</i> Ehrenberg, 1832	7, 59, 60, 76, 77, 80		amnz, (sk)	M-B-L, eh, p	209, 280, 319
<i>Synchaeta ponica</i> Rodewald-Rudescu, 1960 ?	29		● p	M, 14‰, p	109, 111, 201, 209
<i>Synchaeta stylata</i> Wierzejski, 1893	*68, *69		namnz, (k)	B-L, 10‰, p, l	105, 209, 374, 389
<i>Synchaeta tavina</i> Hood, 1893	33		clp, (ha)	M-B, 12‰, p, l	106, 389
<i>Synchaeta tremula</i> (O. F. Müller, 1786)	*69		namnz, (k)	M-B-L, p, eh, l	105, 209, 389
<i>Synchaeta vorax</i> Rousset, 1902	7, 13, 29, *69, 76, 77, 78, 80		clm, (h)	M-B, 12‰, p	105, 190, 191, 249, 289, 317, 389, 398
<i>Polyarthra dolichoptera</i> Idelson, 1925 [<i>P. platyptera</i>]	59, 60, *68, 71, 77, *79, 78, 88, 96		clm, (k)	L-B, 0.8‰, p, β	209, 280, 293, 374
<i>Polyarthra longiremis</i> Carlin, 1943	58, 60		(sk)	L, 0.8‰, p	209, 278, 280
<i>Polyarthra major</i> Burckhardt, 1900	78		(sk)	L, p	209, 293
<i>Polyarthra remata</i> Skorikov, 1896	59, 78, 79, 80		clp, (sk)	L-B, 16.8‰, p, β	192, 193, 252, 280

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Polyarthra vulgaris</i> Carlin, 1943	58, 78, 79, 80		clm, (k)	L-B, 0.5%, p, β	192, 209, 278, 293
<i>Ploesoma hudsoni</i> (Imhof, 1891)	77		clm, (e)	B-L, 24-58%, p, eh	258
Trichocercidae					
<i>Trichocerca agnatha</i> Wulfert, 1939	78		(pata)	L, p	209, 293
<i>Trichocerca mucosa</i> (Stokes, 1896) [<i>Mastigocerca</i>]	78, 96		(h)	L, p	209, 293
<i>Trichocerca musculus</i> (Hauer, 1937) [<i>Diurella</i>]	60		(hata)	L, p, sw	209, 280
<i>Trichocerca porcellus</i> (Gosse, 1851)	96		namnz, (k)	B-L, p	209
<i>Trichocerca pusilla</i> (Jennings, 1903) [<i>Rattulus</i>]	58, 78		namnz, (k)	B-L, 2%, p	209, 278, 293
<i>Trichocerca similis</i> (Wierzejski, 1893)	59		neamnz, (k)	L, 0.5-0.8%, p	209, 280
<i>Trichocerca stylata</i> (Gosse, 1851) [<i>Monocerca</i>]	58		K, (k)	L, 2%, p	209
<i>Trichocerca tenuior</i> (Gosse, 1886) [<i>Diurella</i>]	*68		(k)	L, 1%, p	209, 374, 389
Trichotriidae					
<i>Trichotria tetractis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1830) [<i>Dinocharis</i>]	96		namnz, (k)	M-B-L, p	209
<i>Macrochaetus subquadratus</i> (Perty, 1850) [<i>Dinocharis</i> , <i>Polychaetus</i>]	96		(k)	L-B, p	209, 373
FLOSCULARIIDA					
Conochilidae					
<i>Conochilus hippocrepis</i> (Schrank, 1803) [<i>Linza</i>]	96		(k)	L-B, p	209
Trichosphaeridae					
<i>Filinia longiseta</i> (Ehrenberg, 1834) [<i>Triarthra</i>]	58, 59, 60, 77, 79, 80		clm, (k)	L-B, 0.8-15%, p, sw	193, 252, 278, 280
<i>Filinia terminalis</i> (Plate, 1886) [<i>Triarthra</i>]	59, 60		clm, (k)	L-B, 0.8%, p, sw	209, 280
Flosculariidae					
<i>Beauchampia crucigera</i> (Dutrochet, 1812) [<i>Cephalosiphon candidus</i> , <i>Rotifer</i>]	79		(e, ? k)	L-B, p	209, 373
Hexarthridae					
<i>Hexarthra fennica</i> (Levander, 1892) [<i>Pedalia</i>]	33, *69, *74, *78, 88		amswp, (k)	M-B, 5-50%, p, eh	105, 106, 317, 389
<i>Hexarthra mira</i> (Hudson, 1841) [<i>Pedalion</i>]	59, 60, 77, 80, 96		namnz, (k)	M-B-L, p, eh	209, 280
<i>Hexarthra oxyuris</i> (Sernov, 1903) [<i>Pedalia</i>]	7, *69		(k)	L-B, 10-15%, p, eh	317, 319, 389
Testudinellidae					
<i>Testudinella clypeata</i> (Müller, 1786) [<i>Brachionus</i> , <i>Pterodina clypeata</i>]	29, 32, 33, *78, *79		clm, (h)	M-B, 7-19.5%, bt, p	106, 201, 374, 389
<i>Testudinella obscura</i> Althaus, 1957	7, 35		calm	M, bt, ps, gw, if	2, 209, 249
<i>Testudinella patina</i> (Hermann, 1783)	59, 77		amnz, (k)	M-L, 0.8%, p-bt, l, s	280
<i>Pompholyx complanata</i> Gosse, 1851	59, 60, 78		(e, ? k)	L, 0.5-0.8%, p	280, 293

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
ANNELIDA						
POLYCHAETA					plankton larvae	
PHYLLODOCIDA						
Phyllocidae						
<i>Phyllodoce maculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	25, 27, 28	0-100	abamp	M, bt, eb, pe, ms, phs		245, 249
<i>Phyllodoce mucosa</i> Örsted, 1843	3-8, 13, 25, 28, 69	15-100	anamnep	M, bt, eb, ps-pe, ms		219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Genetyllis tuberculata</i> (Bobretzky, 1868) [<i>Phyllodoce rubiginosa</i>]	2, 5, 7, 11, 12, 13, 16, 24, 27	0-70	lm, ? em, ? p	M, bt, eh, mb, slc, ms		67, 91, 84, 219, 389
<i>Nereiphylla rubiginosa</i> (Saint-Joseph, 1888) [<i>Phyllodoce rubiginosa</i>]	69	2.5-10	clm	M, bt, ps-pe		358
<i>Eulalia viridis</i> (Johnston, 1829) [<i>Phyllodoce</i>]	11, 13, 24	0-30	anamip	M, bt, ep, slc, slr, mc		91, 245, 249
<i>Eumida sanguinea</i> (Örsted, 1843) [<i>Eulalia</i>]	6, 7, 24, 25, 69	1-25	amip	M, bt, eh, ep, ps-s-ph		84, 219, 245, 249, 358, 374
<i>Sige macroceros</i> (Grube, 1860) [<i>Eulalia</i> , <i>Pterocirrus</i>]	11, 12, 24	0-23	namnp	M, bt, ep, ph, slr, ps		91, 245, 249, 389
<i>Mysta picta</i> (Quatrefages, 1865) [<i>Eteone armata</i>]	13, *69, 25	1-5, 25	clm	M, bt, sep, ps-pe-mc		84, 91, 219, 235, 245, 249, 389
<i>Pseudomystides limbata</i> (Saint-Joseph, 1888) [<i>Mystides</i>]	6, 25	1	anclm	M, bt, sep, ps, ph, r		219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Hesionura coineaui</i> (Laubier, 1962) [<i>Eteonides</i> , <i>Mystides</i>]	25, 35	-15	namnep	M, bt, sep, ps, gw		180, 226, 245, 249
Polynoidae						
<i>Harmothoe extenuata</i> (Grube, 1840) [<i>Lagisca</i>]	25, 26	0-35, 50	anamnep	M, bt, mb, ps-pe, phc		245, 249
<i>Harmothoe imbricata</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	24, 25, 69, 76	0-25, 70	anaminp, ? K	M, bt, mb, slr, ps, s		84, 180, 245, 358
<i>Harmothoe impar</i> (Johnston, 1839)	7, 69	2.5-18	anam	M, bt, ep		358
<i>Harmothoe reticulata</i> (Claparède, 1870)	7, 12, 24, 25, 27	0-80	clm	M, bt, mb, ph-pe-ps		84, 91, 219, 245
<i>Malmgreniella lunulata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1830) [<i>Harmothoe</i>]	76		amnep	M, bt, eh, s		119, 396
<i>Polynoe scolopendrina</i> Savigny, 1822	11, 12, 13, 23, 24	0-10	clm	M, bt, ep, slr, slz, r		91, 245
Pholoidea						
<i>Phloe inornata</i> Johnston, 1839 [<i>Ph. synophthalmica</i>]	7, 24, 25, 26	5-30, 130	ace	M, bt, eb, slr, sls, s		84, 180, 245, 249
Sigalionidae						
<i>Sthenelais boa</i> (Johnston, 1833) [<i>Sigalion</i>]	13, 23, 24, 25	0-3	amiwp	M, bt, sep, sls, slz		245, 249
Pisionidae						
<i>Pisione remota</i> (Southern, 1914) [<i>Praegeria</i>]	7, 17, 19, 35, 51	0-0.50	namrnp	M, bt, ls, ps, gw		226, 245, 249
Hesionidae						
<i>Hesionites arenaria</i> Friedrich, 1937	7, 11, 25, 35, 51	0-10	aminwp	M, bt, sep, sls, ps, gw, ■		114, 219, 245, 249, 387, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Microphthalmus fragilis</i> Bobretzky, 1870	7, 13, 25, 35, 51	0-10		vclm	M, bt, sep, ls, sls	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Microphthalmus szcelkowi</i> Metschnikow, 1865	7, 25, 27	10-30, 70		namnp	M, bt, ep, sls, ms	234, 245, 252
<i>Microphthalmus similis</i> Bobretzky, 1870	13, 25, 51	0-10		nam	M, bt, sep, l, sls, slr	219, 245, 249, 389
Syllidae						
<i>Haplosyllis spongicola</i> (Grube, 1855) [Syllis]	17, 24, 50			K	M, bt, ep, ph, l, sl, r	221, 245, 249, 392
<i>Syllis gracilis</i> Grube, 1840	7, 24, 25, 50	1-17		K	M, bt, sep, ph, lt, sls	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Syllis hyalina</i> Grube, 1863	7, 24, 25	-30		K	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, r	234, 245, 249, 392
<i>Syllis prolifera</i> Crohn, 1852	7, 11, 13, 24, 25	0-12		K	M, bt, ep, slr, mc, sls	91, 219, 245, 249
<i>Amblyosyllis formosa</i> (Claparède, 1863) [Pterosyllis]	69, 84			aminwp, ? K	M, bt	102, 247, 249, 252
<i>Streptosyllis varians</i> Webster & Benedict, 1887	11, 25	5-10		bap	M, bt, sep, sls, ps	245, 249, 392
<i>Syllis longocirratu</i> s (Ørsted, 1845)	7, 20, 49	0.5-17		namip	M, bt, sep, slr, r	221, 245, 249, 392
<i>Nudisyllis pulligera</i> (Krohn, 1852) [Pionosyllis]	11, 24, 25, 26, 27	0-60		clm	M, bt, mb, ph, ps, s	221, 245, 392
<i>Neopetitia amphophthalma</i> (Siewing, 1956) [Petitia]	7, 16, 17, 35, 51			cst	M, bt, 4-7‰, ls, gw	238, 245, 249, 252
<i>Salvatoria clavata</i> (Claparède, 1863) [Grubea]	2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 24, 69	0-17		amrs, ? K	M, bt, ep, ph, slr	84, 219, 245, 249
<i>Salvatoria limbata</i> (Claparède, 1868) [Grubea]	7, 25, 68			clm, ? clmrs	M, bt, ps-pe, ph	219, 245, 389
<i>Salvatoria tenuicirrata</i> (Claparède, 1864) [Grubea]	13, 24	1-30		klm	M, bt, ep, slr-ph	91, 245, 389
<i>Sphaerosyllis bulbosa</i> Southern, 1914	1-22, 25, 26, 27, 28	5-105		nam	M, bt, eb, ps-pe	221, 245, 249, 392
<i>Sphaerosyllis lysteri</i> Claparède, 1863	10, 13, 17	17-47		SK	M, bt, eb, ps, pe, et	356
<i>Exogone naidina</i> Ørsted, 1845 [E. gemmifera, Paedophylax claviger]	12, 13, 25, 26, 27	0-70, 213		SK	M, bt, eb, ps-s, sg, ph	91, 221, 245, 389
Nereitidae						
<i>Nereis pelagica</i> Linnaeus, 1758	7, 24			aaminp	M, bt, eb, slr, ph	84, 245, 249, 389
<i>Nereis rava</i> Ehlers, 1864	7, 24	8		lm	M, bt, ep, slr, ph	84, 245, 249, 389
<i>Nereis zonata</i> Malmgren, 1867	2, 7, 24, 25, 26, 27, 69	0-60		anamnp, ? K	M, bt, mb, mc-ph-ps	84, 245, 249, 358
<i>Hediste diversicolor</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776) [Nereis]	2, 3, 5-7, 10-13, *68, *69, *74, 77, *78, *79, 84, *86, 88, 92, 93, 94	0-90		anam	M, bt, eh-0.5-36‰, eb, s, pe-ps, eu	67, 84, 91, 219, 245, 358, 374, 389
<i>Alitta succinea</i> (Frey & Leuckart, 1847) [Neanthes, Nereis]	7, 13, 16, 24, 27, 68, 69, 77	0-10, 30		amip	M, bt, eh, ep, mc-s-ps	84, 219, 245, 374
<i>Perinereis cultrifera</i> (Grube, 1840)	7, 16, 23, 24, 25	0-30		amip	M, bt, ep, lt, ps, slz	84, 91, 245, 249
<i>Platynereis dumerilii</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1834)	3, 7, 13, 16, 24, 25, 27, 69	0.5-50		amip	M, bt, mb, ph, lt, s	67, 84, 91, 245, 358

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Nemaneis ponitica</i> (Borbretsky, 1872) [<i>N. quadriticeps</i> , <i>Lycastopsis</i>]	46, 51	0-0.5, 90	nam	M, bt, sps-zc, s-ps	234, 245, 249
Nephtyidae					
<i>Micronephthys stammeri</i> (Augener, 1932)	1-22, 25, 26	0-40, 80	adp	M, bt, mb, ps, ps-pe	226, 245, 249, 392
<i>Nephtys cirrosa</i> (Ehlers, 1868)	7, 9, 25, 76	0-28, 100	clm	M, bt, ep, sls, ps	84, 245, 249, 358
<i>Nephtys hombergii</i> Savigny in Lamarck, 1818	2-8, 13, 17, *69, 76	0-184	clm	M, bt, eh-6%, eb, eu	67, 84, 91, 245, 358
Glyceridae					
<i>Glycera alba</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 25, 26, *69	0-40	namiwip	M, bt, mb, sls, ps-pe	84, 245, 249, 389
<i>Glycera convoluta</i> Keferstein, 1862	5-22, 25, 26, 27, 69	0-40	eamip	M, bt, mb, sls, ps-pe	221, 245, 249, 358
<i>Glycera gigantea</i> Quatrefages, 1866 [<i>G. decorata</i>]	7, 25, *69	0-30	clmi	M, bt, ep, sls, ps	84, 221, 245, 249
<i>Glycera tessellata</i> Grube, 1840	7, 11, 12, 13		amip	M, bt	247, 252, 255, 288
<i>Glycera unicornis</i> Savigny in Lamarck, 1818 [<i>G. rouxii</i>]	7, 11, 12, 13		eamip	M, bt	247, 249, 252, 288
Goniadidae					
<i>Goniadella bobrezkii</i> (Annenkova, 1929) [<i>Goniada</i>]	11, 25	8, 13-26	clm	M, bt, ep, sls, ps	221, 245, 248, 392
EUNICIDA					
Eunicidae					
<i>Eunice vittata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	11, 12, 13, 23, 24, 25	1-25	amip	M, bt, ep, ro, ps, zc, s	91, 245, 249, 389
<i>Lysidice ninetta</i> Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833	6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 24	0-30, 40	amip	M, bt, ep-mb, slr	84, 91, 245, 389
Dorvilleidae					
<i>Protodorvillea kefersteini</i> (McIntosh, 1869) [<i>Staurocephalus</i>]	7, 8, 13, 23, 24, 25	1.5-20	anam	M, bt, sep, zc, ro, ps-s	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Dorvillea rubrovittata</i> (Grube, 1855) [<i>Staurocephalus</i>]	11, 12, 13, 24, 25	0-5, 40	anamrs	M, bt, mb, sls, ro, r	91, 245, 249, 389
<i>Schistomeringos rudolphi</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828) [<i>Staurocephalus</i>]	23, 24, 25	3-25	amp	M, bt, ep, sls, zc, sg	234, 245, 249
ORBINIIDA					
Orbiniidae					
<i>Orbinia latreillii</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833) [<i>Aricia</i>]	11, 25		clm	M, bt, ep, sls, r	221, 245, 249, 392
Paraonidae					
<i>Aricidea claudiae</i> Laubier, 1967 [<i>A. jeffreysii</i>]	1-3, 5, 7, 13, 17, 25, 27, 28, 69	5-92, 200	klm	M, bt, eb, s, ps-pe, sg	178, 180, 219, 226, 230, 245, 358, 389
<i>Paradoneis harpagonea</i> (Storch, 1967) [<i>Cirrophorus. Paraonis fulgens</i>]	11, 25, 27	15-44	ep, ? lm	M, bt, mb, ps, s	178, 180, 221, 230, 245, 249, 392
SPIONIIDA					
Spionidae					
<i>Scolecopsis ciliata</i> (Keferstein, 1862)	7, 16, 17, 51	0.5	clm	M, bt, sep, ps, sls, r	221, 245, 392

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Scolecopsis squamata</i> (Müller, 1806) [<i>Nerine cirratulus</i>]	7, 25, 51	0-20		amip	M, bt, sep, ps, ls, sls	319, 245, 249, 389
<i>Pseudomalacoceros tridentata</i> (Southern, 1914) [<i>Nerimides</i>]	7, 25	3-		klm	M, bt, sep, ps, sls	84, 219, 245, 389
<i>Aonides paucibranchiata</i> Southern, 1914 [<i>A. ornatus</i>]	4, 7-13, 25, 27, 28	5-125		ham	M, bt, eb, ps, sg, s	180, 219, 245, 358
<i>Spio filicornis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	7, 25, 26, 68, 69	0-30		abamp	M, bt, ep, ps-pe	84, 245, 358, 389
<i>Pygospio elegans</i> Claparède, 1863	7, 25, 26, 27, 69	0-70		anamnp	M, bt, eb, ps-pe	219, 245, 358, 389
<i>Polydora ciliata</i> (Johnston, 1838)	7, 68, 69, 76, 84	27		aanamip	M, bt, ep, ro, mc	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Polydora cornuta</i> Bosc, 1802	7, 13, 68, 69	0.1-32		amp, i	M, bt, ep, s, ps, sg, is	358
<i>Dipolydora quadrilobata</i> (Jacobi, 1883)	24, 49			bapbp, i	M, bt, is	355
<i>Prionospio cirrifera</i> Wirén, 1883	7, 9, 13, 25, 26, 27, 69	5-84		aamip	M, bt, eb, sg, s	219, 222, 226, 249
<i>Prionospio malmgreni</i> Claparède, 1868	6, 23, 25	4-20		aamip	M, bt, eb, ps, sg, zc, r	180, 219, 226, 245
<i>Streblospio shrubsolei</i> (Buchanan, 1890)	7, 68, 69, *78, *79	12		clm	M-B, bt, eh, s, ps-pe	219, 245, 358, 389
Magelonidae						
<i>Magelona papillicornis</i> F. Müller, 1858	7, 11, 18, 25, 69	-23		amip	M, bt, ep, ps	221, 226, 245, 249
<i>Magelona rosea</i> Moore, 1907	7, 11, 18, 25	4-28		nam	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	219, 180, 245, 392
Cirratulidae						
<i>Cirriffornia tentaculata</i> (Montagu, 1808) [<i>Audouinia</i>]	23, 25	0-20		amiswp	M, bt, ep, ps, sg, zc, r	245
<i>Caulerthella bioculata</i> (Keferstein, 1862) [<i>Cirratulus viridis</i> , <i>Heterocirrus</i>]	7, 13, 25	5-25		namp	M, bt, ep, ps-sg	91, 226, 245, 389
OPHELIDA						
Opheliidae						
<i>Ophelia bicornis</i> Savigny, 1918	2, 6, 7, 19, 21, 25, 51	0.5-1.5		bam	M, bt, sep, l-sl, ps, ■	236, 245, 249, 389
<i>Ophelia limacina</i> (Rathke, 1843)	7, 11, 12, 25	10-37		abapnep	M, bt, ep, sl, ps	221, 236, 245, 249
<i>Polyophthalmus pictus</i> (Dujardin, 1839)	13, 24, 50	0-10		amip	M, bt-p, sep, ph-lt	91, 222, 245, 389
CAPITELLIDA						
Capitellidae						
<i>Notomastus latericeus</i> M. Sars, 1851				aanamip	M, bt, eu	245, 249
<i>Notomastus profundus</i> (Eisig, 1887)	1-8, 28	65-		clm, ? clmrs	M, bt, shb, phs	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Heteromastus filiformis</i> (Claparède, 1864)	1-8, 13, 17, 25, 27, 28, 59, 69	0-16-200		aamip	M, bt, eb, pe, ms, phs	84, 245, 249, 358
<i>Capitella capitata</i> (Fabricius, 1780)	4-7, 25, 26, *69	0-30, 80		aamip	M, bt, ep, ps-pe	84, 245, 249, 358
<i>Capitella minima</i> Langerhans, 1880 [<i>Capitomastus</i>]	7, 13, 25, 26, 69	5-110		aam	M, bt, eb, ps, pe, sg	245, 349, 358, 389
<i>Capitellides giardi</i> Mesnil, 1897	7, 25			bam	M, bt, sep, ps	177, 219, 245, 249

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Arenicolidae				
<i>Arenicola marina</i> Lamarck, 1801	7, 12, 25, 51, 84		bamnep	M, bt, ep, ps, ls 219, 226, 245, 249
<i>Arenicolides branchialis</i> (Audouin & Milne-Edwards, 1833) [<i>Arenicola grubii</i>]	25	1.5-12	lm	M, bt, sep, sg 245, 249
Maldanidae				
<i>Clymene collaris</i> (Claparède, 1868) [<i>Praxylla</i>]	13, 23, 25	2-30	lm	M, bt, ep, ps-s, sg, zc 91, 226, 245, 249
<i>Leiochone leiopygos</i> (Grube, 1860) [<i>Clymenura clypeata</i>]	7, 25, 26, 69	0-35	clm	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-pe 84, 219, 226, 245, 249, 358, 289
CTENODRILIDA				
Ctenodrilidae				
<i>Zeppelina dentata</i> Monticelli, 1897 [nomen dubium?]	13		lm	M, bt 252
Parergodrilidae				
<i>Stygocapitella subterranea</i> Knöllner, 1934	7, 35		bamswp	M, ls, gw, r 221, 245, 249, 387
TEREBELLIDA				
Sabelliidae				
<i>Sabellaria taurica</i> (Rathke, 1837) [<i>S. spinulosa</i> , <i>Centrocorone</i>]	7, 12, 13, 24	-30	lm, ? clm	M, bt, ep, sl, sg 84, 91, 219, 222, 245, 249, 389
Pectinariidae				
<i>Lagis koreni</i> Malmgren, 1866 [<i>Pectinaria</i>]	7, 11, 13, 25, 26, 27, 69	0-30, 50	clm	M, bt, mb, ps-pe, ms, sg, s 84, 91, 219, 226, 245, 249, 358, 389
Ampharetidae				
<i>Melinna palmata</i> Grube, 1870	2-7, 13, 17, 26, 27, 28, *69	15-200	clmnnwi	M, bt, eh, eb, s, ps-pe, sg 67, 84, 178, 219, 245, 249, 358
<i>Hypania invalida</i> (Grube, 1860)	59, 60	2-5, 40	ep, ? pc, Rc	M-B, bt, 0.5-0.8%, s, sg 206, 245, 249, 252, 320, 386
Trichobranchiidae				
<i>Terebellides stroemii</i> Sars, 1835	2, 3, 7, 10, 11, 13, 16, 17	36-200	aanamp, ? K	M, bt, eb-hb, s, phs 67, 84, 91, 178, 245
Terebellidae				
<i>Polycirrus jubatus</i> Bobretzky, 1869	7, 12, 16, 25, 51	0-30	● p	M, bt, ep, sg, ps-pe 91, 226, 245, 389
SABELLIDA				
Sabellidae				
<i>Fabricia sabella</i> (Ehrenberg, 1836)	7, 25, 34, 69	12	aannam	M, bt, 3-38%, ep, ps 219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Fabricia stellaris</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) [? <i>F. sabella</i>]	7, 68, 69		bam	M, bt, ep 358

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
? <i>Manayunkia caspica</i> Annenkova, 1928			pc, cpc, Rc	M-B-L, bt	245, 249, 320
<i>Oriopsis armandi</i> (Claparède, 1864) [<i>Oridia</i>]	1-22, 27, 28	-130, 200	kclm, ? clmrs	M, bt, hb, ms, pls	234, 245, 249, 358
Serpulidae					
<i>Hydroides norvegicus</i> Gunnerus, 1768	7, 24	0-30	nami	M, bt, ep, lt, r	84, 245, 389
<i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i> (Fauvel, 1923) [<i>Mercierella</i>]	5, 7, 68, 69, 77, *79, 84, 87	0-15	amip, i	M, bt, 0-55%, ep, is	219, 245, 249, 389
<i>Vermilopsis infundibulum</i> (Philippi, 1844)	3, 7, 12, 13	10-15	amrsp	M, bt, ep, lt, ro	67, 84, 91, 245, 249
<i>Spirobranchus triqueter</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Pomatoceros</i> , <i>P. triquetroides</i>]	3, 7, 24, 25, 27	0-70	clm	M, bt, mb, lt, ms, sg	67, 84, 219, 226, 245, 389
<i>Ditrupe arietina</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	7, 26		namip	M, bt, ep, pe	84, 245, 249, 389
<i>Pileolaria militaris</i> Claparède, 1870 [<i>Spirorbis</i>]	24	0-30	neaminz	M, bt, ep-mb, slc, phc	230, 245, 249
Spirorbidae					
<i>Spirorbis pusilla</i> Rathke, 1837	1-22, 24, 50	0-30, 75	neamnp	M, bt, mb, lt, ro, ph, phc, slc, sg, zc	91, 230, 245, 249, 389
ARCHIANNELIDA					
Polygordiidae					
<i>Polygordius lacteus</i> Schneider, 1868 [<i>P. neapolitanus ponticus</i> , <i>P. ponticus</i>]	25	0-25	clm	M, bt, ep, ps, sg, sls	180, 226, 245, 249
Protodrilidae					
<i>Protodrilus flavocapitatus</i> (Uljanin, 1877)	7, 25, 27, 35, 51	0-80	lm, ? clm	M, bt, eb, l-sl, ps, pe	220, 245, 249, 358
Saccocirridae					
<i>Saccocirrus papillocercus</i> Bobretzky, 1872	7, 51	0.5-0.7	lm, ? clm	M, bt, sep, l-sl, ps	220, 245, 249, 389
Nerillidae					
<i>Nerilla antemata</i> Schmidt, 1848	7, 25, 34, 35, 51, *69	80	naminz	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw	220, 239, 245, 386
Dinophilidae					
<i>Dinophilus gyrociliatus</i> O. Schmidt, 1857	25, 34, 51		naminz	M, bt, sep, l-sl, ps	220, 245, 249, 389
<i>Trilobodrilus heideri</i> Remane, 1925	7, 35	0-1	clm	M, bt, sep, ps, if, r	220, 245, 249, 389
APHANONEURA					
AEOLOSOMATIDA					
Aeolosomatidae					
<i>Aeolosoma hemprichi</i> Ehrenberg, 1831	58, *68		(hnata, ? sk)	L, bt, cr, po, sw	88, 249, 365, 389
OLIGOCHAETA					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
OPISTHOPHORA					
Criodrilidae					
<i>Criodrilus lacuum</i> Hoffmeister, 1845	71, 72		(eca, ? h)	L, bt	365
Lumbricidae					
<i>Eiseniella tetraedra</i> (Savigny, 1876)	71, 77		(h, ? k)	L-TL, bt, tx	365
TUBIFICIDA					
Naididae					
<i>Stylaria lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	1-22, 35, 58, 77, 84		nam, (hno)	M, bt, 7‰, ps, gw	42, 84, 88, 249, 365
<i>Slavina appendiculata</i> (Udekem, 1855)	58		amnz, (k)	M, bt, 1-2‰	365
<i>Dero digitata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1773)	78		(k)	L, bt	365
<i>Dero obtusa</i> Udekem, 1855	58		(k)	L, bt, 1-2‰, α	365
<i>Nais barbata</i> O. F. Müller, 1773	58, 71, 77		(hoa)	L, bt	365
<i>Nais bretscheri</i> Michaelsen, 1899	58		(hop, ? hno)	L, bt, 1-2‰, o-β	265
<i>Nais communis</i> Piguët, 1906	88, 90		ham, (k)	M-L, bt, eh-16‰, eu	88, 249, 365, 374
<i>Nais elinguis</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	54, 58, *68, *69, 71, 74, 77, *78, 82, 84, *86-88, 90, 92		aminz, (k)	M-B-L, bt, 18‰, eh, eu, sw-po	84, 87, 88, 249, 365, 374, 389
<i>Nais pardalis</i> Piguët, 1906	58, *69, 84		(hno)	L, bt, 10‰, ph, ps-pe	88, 249, 365, 389
<i>Nais variabilis</i> Piguët, 1906	58, 74, 79, 82		aminz, (k)	M-B, bt, sw-po	365
<i>Ophidonais serpentina</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	58, 79, 84, 92		bap, (hno)	L, bt, sw-po	365
<i>Homochaeta naidina</i> Bretscher, 1896 [<i>Paranais</i>]	7, 58		(po)	L-M, bt, 15‰	84, 249, 365, 389
<i>Paranais frici</i> Hrahe, 1941	84		amp, (hno)	M-B, bt, po	365
<i>Paranais litoralis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1780)	7, 58, 87, 88		namp, (hn)	M-B, bt, 16‰	84, 88, 249, 365
<i>Amphichaeta leydigi</i> Tauber, 1879	58, 87		(h, ? hno)	L, 2‰, sw	365
<i>Chaetogaster cristallinus</i> Vejdovsky, 1883	*68, 84		(hpt, ? hptn)	L-M, bt, 10‰, sw	84, 88, 365, 374
<i>Chaetogaster diaphanus</i> (Gruithuisen, 1828)	58		SK, (sk)	M-L, bt, sw, po	88, 365, 372
Tubificidae					
<i>Tubifex nerthus</i> Michaelsen, 1908	84, 96		clp, ? bap	M-B, bt, sw	107, 249, 364, 365
<i>Tubifex tubifex</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	58, 71, 72, 74, 77, 78, 80, 84, 87, 92		(k)	M-B-L, bt, eu	365
<i>Branchiura sowerbyi</i> Beddard, 1892	59		(h)	L, 0.78‰, bt, ro	365
<i>Aulodrilus plurisetus</i> (Piguët, 1906)	58, 96		(hoa)	L, bt, eu	365

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Limnodrilus claparedeanus</i> Ratzel, 1868	71, 80, 92		(k)	L, bt, eu, sw, po 365
<i>Limnodrilus hoffmeisteri</i> Claparède, 1862	58, *68, 71, 74, 87, 92	0.5-120	SK, (k)	M-L, bt, sw, po, α, s 84, 249, 365, 389
<i>Limnodrilus profundicola</i> (Verrill, 1871)	78		nam, (ho)	L-B, bt, sw, po 365
<i>Limnodrilus udekemianus</i> Claparède, 1862	58, 65, *68, 74, 79, 80, 84, 87		SK, (k)	L-B, 1% ₀ , bt, eu, α 84, 249, 365, 389
<i>Psammoryctides albicola</i> (Michaelsen, 1901) [<i>Psammoryctes</i> , <i>Tubifex</i>]	58, *68		clm, (h)	L-B, 2% ₀ , bt, pe, α 88, 249, 365, 389
<i>Psammoryctides barbatus</i> (Grube, 1861)	58		clm, (h)	M-L, 2% ₀ , bt, ps, α-β 365
<i>Psammoryctides moravicus</i> (Hrabe, 1934)	58		(wpat)	L, 2% ₀ , bt, po, sw, r 365
<i>Potamoithrix bavaricus</i> (Oeschmann, 1913)	58		clmz, (hna)	M-L, 2% ₀ , bt, sw, r 365
<i>Potamoithrix bedoti</i> (Pignet, 1913)	58		(ho)	L, 2% ₀ , bt, po, sw 365
<i>Potamoithrix hammoniensis</i> (Michaelsen, 1901)	58, 78, 84, 88		clm, (ho)	M-L, bt, sw, po, pe 205, 365
<i>Potamoithrix vejšovskyyi</i> (Hrabě, 1941)	58		pc, (eit, ? h)	M-B-L, bt, po, sw 365
<i>Clitellio arenarius</i> (Müller, 1776)	84, 96		bap	M, bt, l-sl, s, ro, ps 249, 364, 365
<i>Aktedrilus monospermathecus</i> Knöllner, 1935	1-22, 35, 49		clm, ? clmnei	M, bt, l-sl, gw, ps 150, 244, 249, 365
<i>Heterochaeta costata</i> Claparède, 1863 [<i>Tubifex</i>]	11, 58, 84, 88, 96		clp	M-B, bt, l, ps, pe-ps 249, 364, 365
<i>Tubificoides benedii</i> (Udekem, 1855) [<i>Pelosciolex</i>]	1-22, 35		bap	M-B, bt, l, ps, gw 43, 249
<i>Tubificoides euxinicus</i> (Hrabě, 1966) [<i>Tubifex euxinus</i> ?]	1-22, 35		? bap	M, bt, l, ps, gw 244, 249, 252
<i>Tubificoides swirencowi</i> Jaroschenko, 1948 [<i>T. heterochaetus</i> , <i>Pristina papillosa</i>]	13, 84		pc, cp	M, bt, 15% ₀ , pe-ps 88, 249, 365, 389
<i>Monopylephorus rubroniveus</i> Levensen, 1884 [<i>Rhizodrilus ponticus</i> , <i>M. r. ponticus</i>]	1-22, 35		? namnp	M, bt, l, pe-ps, gw, ph 43, 249, 252
Enchytraeidae				
<i>Enchytraeus albidus</i> Henle, 1837	11, 35		napnei, (hna)	M-L-TL, l, ps, gw 84, 88, 249, 365
<i>Marionina achaeta</i> (Hagen, 1954)	1-22, 35		cp	M, 15% ₀ , l, ps, gw 244, 249, 252
<i>Marionina elongata</i> Lasserre, 1964	1-22, 35		? nam	M, bt, 15% ₀ , l, ps, gw 244, 249, 252
<i>Marionina spicula</i> (Leuckart, 1847)	1-22, 35		bap	M, bt, 15% ₀ , l, ps, gw 244, 249, 252
<i>Marionina subterranea</i> (Knöllner, 1935)	1-22, 35, 54		bapbp, (h)	M-L, bt, l, ps, gw, cr 244, 249, 252, 365
BRANCHIOBELLEA				
BRANCHIOBELLEIDA				
Branchiobdellidae				
<i>Branchiobdella astaci</i> Odier, 1823	60, ? 61		(csee, ? cse)	L, epi, 0.1-2% ₀ 365, 389
HIRUDINEA				
RHYNCHOBELLEIDA				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Glossiphoniidae					
<i>Glossiphonia complanata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, *68, 94		neamj, (h)	L, bt, ph, 2‰	374, 389
<i>Helobdella stagnalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, *68		(h)	L, bt, ph, 1‰	374, 389
<i>Hemiclepsis marginata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	58, 59		(po)	L, bt, ph, 0.3‰	374, 389
<i>Placobdella costata</i> (Fr. Müller, 1846)	58		(wp)	L, bt, ph, 0.3‰	
<i>Theromyzon tessulatum</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) [Protodepsis]	*67		(? h)	L, bt	372, 389
Piscicolidae					
<i>Piscicola geometra</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	*68		(hn, ? hnat)	L-B-M, bt, 1‰	84, 389
Arhynchobdellida					
Hirudinidae					
<i>Hirudo verbana</i> Carena, 1820 [<i>H. medicinalis</i>]	58, *68, *69, *74		(cse)	L, bt, ph, 10‰, ▲	374, 389
Haemopidae					
<i>Haemopsis sanguisuga</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Aulastoma gulo</i>]	58, *68, *74		(ena)	L, bt, ph, 10‰	374, 389
Erpobdellidae					
<i>Erpobdella ooculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 77		(po)	L, bt, ph, lt, 5-7‰	258
TARDIGRADA					
HETEROTARDIGRADA					
ARTHROTARDIGRADA					
Batillipediidae					
<i>Batillipes mirus</i> Richters, 1909	16, 18, 25, 51	1-8	nami, ? K	M, bt, l-sl, ps, gw, if	249, 388, 389
Halechiniscidae					
<i>Halechiniscus gutteli</i> Richters, 1908	16, 35, 51		lm, ? clim	M, bt, l-sl, ps, s, gw	249, 388, 389
Stygarctidae					
<i>Stygarctus bradyus</i> Schulz, 1951	35		epnei, ? cg	M, bt, l, ps, gw	249, 392
ECHINISCOIDEA					
Echiniscoididae					
<i>Echiniscoides sigismundi</i> Plate, 1889	3-22, 50		anamp	M, bt, eh, eu, l, ph	84, 249, 382, 388
EUTARDIGRADA					
PARACHETA					
Hypsibidae					
<i>Halobiotus stenostomus</i> (Richters, 1908) [<i>Hypsibius</i>]	24, 25, 49	-25	clm	M, bt, sl, ps, ph	249, 316

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
ARTHROPODA				
ARACHNIDA				
ACARINA				
Hydrozetidae				
<i>Hydrozetes lacustris</i> (Michael, 1882)	70, *86, 94		(esee, ? e)	374, 389
Limnozetestidae				
<i>Limnozetes rugosus</i> (Sellnick, 1923)	94		(e)	374, 389
Halacaridae				
<i>Rhombognathus magnirostris</i> Trouessart, 1889	7, 11, 12, 13, 16, 24		clm	84, 89, 275, 389
<i>Rhombognathus notops</i> (Gosse, 1855)	*69		abap	249, 389, 402
<i>Rhombognathides pascens</i> (Lohmann, 1889) [<i>Rhombognathus</i>]	11, 12, 13, 16		nam	89, 249, 389
<i>Halacarellus capuzinus</i> (Lohmann, 1893) [<i>Halacarus</i>]	35		bap	249, 252, 307
<i>Halacarellus phreaticus</i> Petrova, 1972	7, 16		hom	249, 252, 306
<i>Halacarellus procerus</i> (Viets, 1927)	35		bam	114, 249, 252, 307
<i>Halacarellus subterraneus</i> Schulz, 1933	3, 5, 84		abam, ? anam	249, 252, 306
<i>Anomalohalacarus marcandrei</i> Mommiot, 1967 [<i>Halacarus</i> , <i>Halacarellus</i>]	8, 18		clm, ? clmi	249, 252, 307
<i>Thalassarachna affinis</i> (Trouessart, 1896) [<i>Halacarus basteri</i> var. <i>affinis</i>]	11-13, 16, 24, 27, 28	-150	hom	89, 249, 389
? <i>Thalassarachna basteri</i> (Johnston, 1836) ? [<i>Halacarellus</i>]		-46	abam, ? anam	249
<i>Thalassarachna hexacantha</i> (Viets, 1927) [<i>Halacarus</i> , <i>Halacarellus</i>]	7	0.5-28	cp	84, 249, 389
<i>Copidognathus brachystomus</i> Viets, 1940	*69		clm	249, 389, 402
<i>Copidognathus brevis</i> Viets, 1927	7, 24	0-10	clm	84, 249, 389
<i>Copidognathus extensus</i> Viets, 1940	7	12	hom	84, 249, 389
<i>Copidognathus fabricii</i> (Lohmann, 1889)	11, 12, 13, 16, *79		clmi	89, 249, 374, 389
<i>Copidognathus magnipalpus</i> (Police, 1909) [<i>C. m. ponticus</i> , <i>C. m. serratseta</i>]	*86		lmwi, ?R	249, 389, 401
<i>Copidognathus ocellatus</i> (Hodge, 1863) [<i>Copidognathopsis</i> , <i>Halacarus</i>]	11, 12, 13, 16, *69		clm	89, 249, 374, 389
<i>Copidognathus quadricostatus</i> (Trouessart, 1894) [<i>Copidognathopsis</i>]	11, 12, 16		clm	89, 249, 275, 389
<i>Copidognathus rhodostigma</i> (Gosse, 1855)	11, 12, 16, 24		clm	89, 249, 275, 389
<i>Copidognathus tabellio</i> (Trouessart, 1894)	11, 12, 13, 16	9-28	lm	89, 249, 275, 389
<i>Copidognathus tectiporus</i> (Viets, 1935) [<i>Copidognathopsis</i>]	*67, *69		lm, ?R	249, 389, 400, 402
<i>Agave chevreuxi</i> (Trouessart, 1889) [<i>Halacarus</i>]	11, 12, 13, 16, 24	-20	lm, ? clm	89, 249, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Agauopsis brevipalpus</i> (Trouessart, 1889) [<i>A. pontica</i> , <i>Agaue b. var. ponticus</i>]	11, 12, 13, 16, 25, 27	9-28	namnei	M-B, bt, sg, ms, phc	89, 249, 389
<i>Agauopsis marinovi</i> Petrova, 1976	7		ham	M-B, bt, l	249, 252, 308
<i>Actacarus pygmaeus</i> Schulz, 1937	25, 35	-5	lmnei	M-B, bt, gw-if, ps, sl	229, 249, 389
<i>Arhodooporus gracilipes</i> (Trouessart, 1889) [<i>Copidoagnathopsis</i>]	12, 16, 25, 28	-150	clm	M-B, bt, eb, sg, phs	89, 249, 275, 389
<i>Acarochelopodia delamarei</i> Angelier, 1954	7, 35		hom	M-B, bt, ps, gw	229, 249, 392
<i>Lohmannella falcata</i> (Hodge, 1863)	12, 27, 28	45-100	bam	M-B, bt, eb, ms, phs	89, 249, 389
<i>Caspihalacarus lycrcanus</i> Viets, 1928 [<i>C. h. danubialis</i>]	*69	1-2	pc, clm, Rc	B-L, bt, ep, ro, s	252, 389, 402
Hydrachnidae					
<i>Hydrachna cruenta</i> O. F. Müller, 1776	42		(h)	L, bt, l	84, 389
Eylaidae					
<i>Eylais infundibulifera</i> Koenike, 1897	42		(h)	L, bt, l	84, 389
<i>Eylais rimosa</i> Piersig, 1899	42		(h)	L, bt, l	84, 389
Hydryphantidae					
<i>Hydryphantes crassipalpis</i> Koenike, 1914	*68		(wesa)	L, bt, 1‰, l	389, 400
Hydrodromidae					
<i>Hydrodroma despiciens</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	88		(sk, ? k)	L, bt, 1‰	389, 402
Pontarachnidae					
<i>Pontarachna valkanovi</i> Petrova, 1978	11, 12, 25, 35, 51, 92		● p	M, bt, l-sl, ps, gw	249, 252, 309, 392
Limnesidae					
<i>Limnesia koenikei</i> Piersig, 1894	90		(h)	L, bt	389, 402
<i>Limnesia undulata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	*68		(h)	L, bt, l	389, 400
Aturidae					
<i>Brachypoda versicolor</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	*67		(? tp)	L, bt	389, 400
Arrenuridae					
<i>Arrenurus bruzelii</i> Koenike, 1885	93		(wp, ? tp)	L, bt, 3‰	389, 402
PYCNOGONIDA					
PANTOPODA					
Ammonotheidae					
<i>Tanystylum conirostre</i> (Dohrn, 1881)	7, 24	1-2	kclm	M, bt, ep, sl, ph	39, 249, 389
Callipallenidae					
<i>Callipallene phantoma</i> (Dohrn, 1881)	1-22, 28	35-80	anam	M, bt, shb, phs	247, 249, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
CRUSTACEA					
SARSOSTRACA: ANOSTRACA					
Artemiidae					
<i>Artemia parthenogenetica</i> Bowen & Sterling, 1978	76, 77		(omcaa)	B, 20-100-340‰, p	119, 359
<i>Artemia salina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	*64, 76, 77		(sp, ? sk)	B, 20-80-340‰, p	86, 91, 100, 372, 389
Thamnocephalidae					
<i>Branchinella spinosa</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1840)	*64		lm, (atm)	B-M, 30‰, p, ■	100, 114, 389
Phyllopoda: Cladocera					
Sididae					
<i>Penilia avirostris</i> Dana, 1849 [<i>P. schmackeri</i>]	7, 29, *69, 77	0-50	amiwp	M-B-L, p, eh, epp	198, 202, 319, 389
<i>Diaphanosoma brachyurum</i> (Liévin, 1848)	58, *68, *79, 80		amwp, (hat)	M-B-L, p, eh, 6-8‰	97, 278, 374, 389
<i>Diaphanosoma lacustris</i> Korinek, 1981	59, 60		(pat)	L, p, 0.5-0.8‰	279, 280
Macrothricidae					
<i>Macrothrix laticornis</i> (Jurine, 1820)	*68		(sk)	L, 1‰, p-bit, s	97, 279, 389
<i>Ilyocryptus sordidus</i> (Liévin, 1848)	*68		amwp, (pat)	B-L, 1‰, p	279, 374, 389
Bosminidae					
<i>Bosmina coregoni</i> Baird, 1857	59, 60		apswp, (h)	M-B-L, 0.5-0.8‰, p	279, 280
<i>Bosmina longirostris</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776) [<i>B. l. similis</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, 77, 80		anam, (k)	M-B-L, 1-2‰, p, epp	278, 279, 280, 389
Chydoridae (Eurycercidae)					
<i>Acroperus harpae</i> (Baird, 1834)	92		(hmat)	M-B-L, 0.5‰, p	279, 374, 389
<i>Alona guttata</i> Sars, 1862	78		(sk)	L, 0-20‰, p	252, 278, 279
<i>Alona quadrangularis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	58, *68		namp, (sk)	M-B-L, 0.2-2‰, p	278, 279, 374, 389
<i>Alona rectangularis</i> Sars, 1861	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 76, 77, *79, *86, 88, 92, 93		(sk)	B-L, 0.5-6‰, p	277, 279, 280, 374, 389
<i>Alonella excisa</i> (Fischer, 1854)	59, 60		(k)	L, 0.5-0.8‰, p	279, 280
<i>Alonella exigua</i> (Lilljeborg, 1853)	42		(h)	L, p	252, 278, 279
<i>Chydorus piger</i> Sars, 1862	60		(e)	L, p, 0.5-0.8‰	279, 280
<i>Chydorus sphaericus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1785)	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 71, *79, 80, 88, 92		amswp, (k)	M-B-L, 3‰, p, epp	278, 279, 280, 374, 389
<i>Disparalona rostrata</i> (Koch, 1841) [<i>Phrixura, Rhynchotalona</i>]	42, 86		(h, ? sk)	B-L, p	252, 277, 279
<i>Graptoleberis testudinaria</i> (Fischer, 1848)	60		(k)	M-B-L, p, 0.5-0.8‰	279, 280

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Leydigia acanthocercoides</i> (Fischer, 1854)	95		(sk)	B-L, p, 0.5‰	279, 374, 389
<i>Leydigia leydigi</i> (Schoedler, 1863)	*68		(sk)	B-L, p, 1‰	97, 279, 389
<i>Monopilus dispar</i> Sars, 1862	*69		(hata)	B-L, p	279, 374, 389
<i>Oxyurella tenuicaudis</i> (Sars, 1862)	59, 60, *69		(hata)	L, p, 0.5-0.8‰	279, 289, 375, 389
<i>Pleuroxus trigonellus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	59, 60, *68, *86, 88		(hat)	L, p, 1.5‰	279, 280, 374, 389
<i>Pleuroxus uncinatus</i> Baird, 1850	58		(hop, ? h)	L, p, 0.5-2‰	252, 278, 279
Moinidae					
<i>Moina hartwigi</i> Welter, 1898	81		(? atm)	L, p, 1‰, r	279, 374, 389
<i>Moina macrocopa</i> (Straus, 1819)	58		(h, ? hpt)	L, p, 2‰	252, 278, 279
<i>Moina micrura</i> Kurz, 1874 [<i>M. m. dubia</i> , <i>M. propinqua</i>]	58, 59, 60, 78, 79		? SK, (sk)	B-L, p, 0.5-20‰	190, 193, 252, 278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Moina rectirostris</i> (Leydig, 1860)	*69		(hpt)	B-L, p, 4‰	374, 389
Daphniidae					
<i>Daphnia cucullata</i> Sars, 1862 [<i>D. c. apicata</i> , <i>D. c. breviensis</i>]	58, 59, 60, 78, 80		(h)	M-B-L, p, 0.8‰	252, 277, 278, 280
<i>Daphnia curvirostris</i> Eylmann, 1887 [? complex]	60, 82, 88, 92		(hat)	L-B, p, 0.5-15‰	252, 277, 279, 280
<i>Daphnia galeata</i> Sars, 1863	59, 60		(h)	B-L, p, 0.8‰	279, 280
<i>Daphnia hyalina</i> Leydig, 1860	68, 79		(hes)	M-B-L, p, 1-12‰	252, 277, 278, 279
<i>Daphnia longispina</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	13, 71		(hmat)	B-L, p	279, 374, 389
<i>Daphnia magna</i> Straus, 1820	58, 78, 79, 80		(hat, ? hpt)	B-L, p, 0.5-2‰	192, 193, 252, 279
<i>Daphnia pulex</i> (Leydig, 1860)	74, 77, 80		(k)	B-L, p, 5-17‰	258, 279, 374, 389
<i>Ceriodaphnia affinis</i> Liljeborg, 1900	78, 79, 80		(h)	L-B, p	190, 192, 193, 252, 252, 278, 279, 374
<i>Ceriodaphnia dubia</i> Richard, 1894 [<i>Moina</i>]	58, 79		(sk)	L, p, 0.5-8‰	252, 278, 279, 374
<i>Ceriodaphnia pulchella</i> Sars, 1862	58		(sk)	L, p, 0.5-8‰	252, 278, 279
<i>Ceriodaphnia quadrangula</i> (O. F. Müller, 1785)	58, 59, 60, 78		(sk)	B-L, p, 0.5-2‰	277, 278, 279, 280
<i>Ceriodaphnia reticulata</i> (Jurine, 1820)	58, 84		(sk)	M-B-L, p, 0.5-2‰	252, 277, 278, 279
<i>Scapholeberis mucronata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	58, 59, 60, 80, 88		(sk)	B-L, p, 0.5-2‰	278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Simocephalus vetulus</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	58, 59, 60, *68, 77, 80		(sk)	B-L, p, 0.5-2‰	97, 278, 279, 280
Podomidae					
<i>Evadne nordmanni</i> Lovén, 1836	29, 69	0-25	namp	M, p, eh, epp, et	201, 317, 319, 389
<i>Evadne spinifera</i> P. E. Müller, 1867	7, 11, 12, 29		amwp	M, p, epp	91, 198, 319, 389
<i>Pseudevadne tergestina</i> (Claus, 1877) [<i>Evadne</i> , <i>Pleopsis</i>]	7, 11, 12, 16, 29	0-20	amip	M, p	91, 198, 319, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Podon intermedius</i> Lilljeborg, 1853	29		bamswp	M, p, epp	201, 202
<i>Podon leuckartii</i> G. O. Sars, 1862	7, 29, *69		abapbp	M, p, epp, 10% ^{oo}	201, 319, 374, 389
<i>Pleopsis polyphaemoides</i> (Leucart, 1859) [<i>Podon</i>]	7, 13, 29, 69, 72, 77	0-50	amnp	M-B, p, eh	198, 201, 304, 317
<i>Podonevadne trigona</i> (G. O. Sars, 1897) [<i>P. t. ovum</i> , <i>Podon ovum</i>]	*69		pc, Rc	M-B-L, p, 5% ^{oo}	317, 389
Cercopagidae					
<i>Cercopagis pengoi</i> (Ostroumov, 1891)	*68, *69		pc, Rc	M-B-L, p, 3% ^{oo}	317, 385, 389
OSTRACODA: PODOCOPIDA					
Darwinulidae					
<i>Darwinula stevensoni</i> (Brady et Robertson, 1870)	93		(k)	L-B, bt, 1% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
Candonidae					
<i>Paracypris polita</i> G. O. Sars, 1866	11, 25, 27	8, 100	clm	M, bt, eb, ps	233, 249, 252
<i>Candona neglecta</i> G. O. Sars, 1887	*68		(wp)	L-B, bt, 1-5% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Candonopsis kingsleii</i> (Brady et Robertson, 1870)	93		(h)	L-B, bt, 1% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Fabaeformiscandona levandieri</i> (Hirschmann, 1912) [<i>Candona</i>]	*68		(e)	L-B, bt, 1% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Physocypris kraepelini</i> G. W. Müller, 1903 [<i>Physocypris kliei</i>]	*68		(k)	L, bt, 1% ^{oo}	97, 389
Cyprididae					
<i>Cyprinotus salinus</i> (Brady, 1868) [<i>Heterocypris fretensis</i>]	*68, *69, *74, 77, *86, 88, 89, 90, 93, 94		(ean)	M-B-L, bt, 0-20% ^{oo}	185, 249, 374, 389
<i>Eucypris inflata</i> (G. O. Sars, 1903)	61, 64, 76, 77, *79		(mwca)	L-B, bt, eh-150% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Sarscypridopsis aculeata</i> (Costa, 1847) [<i>Cypridopsis</i>]	96		(lmat)	L-B, bt	185, 249, 389
<i>Cypridopsis vidua</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	93		(sk)	L-B, bt, 8% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Plesiocypridopsis newtoni</i> (Brady et Robertson, 1870) [<i>Cypridopsis</i>]	93, 95		(wp)	L-B, bt, 8% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Potamocypris steueri</i> Klie, 1935	94		(hom)	L-B, bt, 10% ^{oo}	185, 249, 389
<i>Heterocypris maura</i> (Masi, 1932)	*68		(pm)	L-B, bt, 1% ^{oo}	185, 389
<i>Heterocypris incongruens</i> (Ramdohr, 1808)	42		(k)	L, bt	84, 389
<i>Trajanocypris serrata</i> G. W. Müller, 1900 [<i>Eucypris</i>]	*68		(eca)	L, bt, 1% ^{oo}	97, 389
Ilyocyprididae					
<i>Ilyocypris buplicata</i> (Koch, 1838)	*68		(h)	L, bt, 1% ^{oo}	97, 389
Cushmaniidae					
<i>Pontocythere bacesoi</i> (Caraión, 1960) [<i>Cytheridea</i>]	11, 12, 25, 71	0.7-10	● p	M, bt, ep, ps	228, 249, 392
<i>Pontocythere tchernijawskii</i> Dubowsky, 1939	26, 27	10-43	ep	M, bt, mb, pe, s-ps	249

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Cytherideidae				
<i>Cyprideis torosa</i> (Jones, 1850) [<i>C. littoralis</i>]	*68, *69, 76, 77, *78, *79, 84, 93, 96		clm, (hat)	M-B-L, bt, ep, 0-30%, eb, ps, pe, ph
<i>Cytheridea acuminata</i> (Bosquet, 1952)	25, 26, 27, 28	20-100	m, ? em	M, bt, eb, pe, s-ps
Leptocytheridae (Cytheridae)				
<i>Amnicythere quinquetuberculata</i> (Schweyer, 1949) [<i>Leptocythere</i>]	3		pc, Sf, Rc	B-M, bt
<i>Amnicythere striatocostata</i> (Schweyer, 1949) [<i>Leptocythere</i>]	3		pc, Sf, Rc	B-M, bt
<i>Euxinocythere lopatici</i> (Schornikov, 1964) [<i>Leptocythere</i>]	3		pc, Sf, Rc	B-M, bt
<i>Leptocythere devexa</i> Schornikov, 1966	3, 7, 10, 25, 26, 27, 28	1-100	hom	M, bt, eb, pe, sg
<i>Leptocythere diffusa</i> G. W. Müller, 1894) [<i>Callistocythere</i>]	1-22, 26, 27	13-70	lm	M, bt, eb, pe
<i>Leptocythere macallana</i> (Brady et Robertson, 1869)	1-22, 25	8-12	ce	M, bt, ep, pe, ps, sg
<i>Leptocythere mediterranea</i> (G. W. Müller, 1894) [<i>Callistocythere</i>]	1-22, 24, 50	0-10	mj	M, bt, ep, pe, ps, ph
<i>Leptocythere multipunctata</i> (Seguenza, 1942)	3, 7, 10, 25, 27, 28, 35	-100	mj	M, bt, hb, pe, s-ps, sg
<i>Leptocythere nitida</i> Schornikov, 1966	1-22, 25, 26	8-15	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, pe
<i>Leptocythere relicta</i> Schornikov, 1964	3		pc, Sf, Rc	M-B, bt
Trachyleberididae				
<i>Carinocythereis carinata</i> (Roemer, 1838) [<i>C. antiquata</i> , <i>Cythereis</i>]	1-22, 25, 26	20-80	clm	M, bt, eb-hb, pe, s-ps
<i>Hiltermannicythere rubra</i> (G. W. Müller, 1894) [<i>H. r. pontica</i> , <i>Carinocythereis</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 27, 28	2-100	m, ? em	M, bt, eb, pe, s, ps
Hemicytheridae				
<i>Aurila dubowskyi</i> Schornikov, 1969	24	0.4-10	● p	M, bt, ep, ph, ro
<i>Hemicythere sicula</i> (Brady, 1902) [<i>Cythere</i>]	*68, *69		pea	M-B, bt, 1-12%
Limnocytheridae				
<i>Limnocythere inopinata</i> (Baird, 1843)	*68		(h)	B-L, bt, 1%
Cytheromatidae (Cytheromidae)				
<i>Cytheroma karadagensis</i> Dubowsky, 1939	7, 24, 25, 26, 27	5-80	m	M, bt, eb, ps, ph, pe
<i>Cytheroma marinovi</i> Schornikov, 1969	24, 25, 26	15-30	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, pe
<i>Cytheroma variabilis</i> G. W. Müller, 1894	26, 27	20-80	adep	M, bt, eb, pe
Cytheridae				
<i>Pontocytheroma arenaria</i> Marinov, 1963	7, 11, 25	10-25	● p	M, bt, ep, ps
<i>Paracytheridea paulii</i> Dubowsky, 1939	8, 11, 12, 25	2-20	● p	M, bt, ep, ps
<i>Parvocythere hartmanni</i> Marinov, 1962	25, 35		● p	M, bt, ps, gw

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Loxococonchidae				
<i>Loxococoncha aestuarii</i> Marinov, 1963	86		● p	M-B, bt, pe, s-ps 228, 249, 392
<i>Loxococoncha bulgarica</i> Caraton, 1961	16, 23, 26	-5	● p	M, bt, ep, pe, zc 80, 249, 392
<i>Loxococoncha elliptica</i> Brady, 1868 [<i>L. gauthieri</i>]	*68, 84, *86, 88		clm	M-B, bt, eh 185, 249, 374, 389
<i>Loxococoncha granulata</i> G. O. Sars, 1866	1-22, 26, 27, 28	20-100	clm	M, bt, eb, pe 225, 249, 392
<i>Loxococoncha impressa</i> (Baird)	7		bam	M, bt, sl 225, 392
<i>Loxococoncha littoralis</i> G. W. Müller, 1894 [<i>L. pennatus</i> , <i>Sagmatocythere</i>]	8, 25		m, ? hom	M, bt, ps 228, 249, 392
<i>Loxococoncha nana</i> Marinov, 1962 [<i>Tuberoxococoncha</i>]	7, 25, 33		● p	M, bt, ps, if 225, 249, 392
<i>Loxococoncha pontica</i> Klie, 1937	7, 16, 24, 77, *86	0-5	clm	M, bt, sep, ph 84, 185, 249, 389
<i>Loxococoncha rhomboidea</i> (Fischer, 1855)	3, 7, 10, 17, 24, 26, 27	5-50	clm, ? bam	M, bt, mb, eh, s-ph-ro 247, 249, 252
<i>Microxococoncha marinovi</i> Schornikov, 1969	7, 21, 22, 25	2-3	● p, Ebg	M, bt, sep, ps 233, 249, 252
Cytheruridae				
<i>Eucytherura bulgarica</i> Klie, 1937 [<i>Hemicytherura</i>]	16, 24, 89	0-15	● p	M, bt, ep, ph 185, 249, 389
<i>Pseudocytherura pontica</i> Dubowsky, 1939	8, 11, 12, 25	5-25	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 228, 249, 392
<i>Semicytherura calamitica</i> Schornikov, 1969	3, 7, 10, 25	-25	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 249, 252
<i>Semicytherura euxinica</i> (Caraton, 1967)	3, 7, 10, 17, 25	-20	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 249, 252
<i>Semicytherura pontica</i> (Marinov, 1962) [<i>Cytherura</i> , <i>Levocytherura</i>]	7, 11, 25	-7	● p, Ebg	M, bt, ep, ps 225, 249, 252
<i>Semicytherura virgata</i> Schornikov, 1969	2, 3, 5, 7, 10, 25	-25	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 249, 252
<i>Levocytherura remanei</i> (Marinov, 1962) [<i>Cytherura</i> , <i>Semicytherura</i>]	8, 11, 12, 25	5-10	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 228, 249, 392
<i>Microcytherura fulvoides</i> Dubowsky, 1939	11, 25		● p	M, bt, ep, ps 225, 249, 392
<i>Microcytherura nigrescens</i> G. W. Müller, 1894	3, 4, 7, 25	1-30	m, ? hom	M, bt, ep-me, ps 247, 249, 252
Xestoleberididae				
<i>Xestoleberis aurantia</i> (Baird, 1838)	24*, 69	-5	namni	M, bt, ep, ph 185, 249, 389
<i>Xestoleberis cornelii</i> Caraton, 1963	24, 25, 27	1.5-90	m	M, bt, eb, ph, pe, ps-s 249
<i>Xestoleberis decipiens</i> (G. W. Müller, 1894)	24, *86	0-25	hom	M, bt, eb, ph 185, 249, 389
Microcytheridae				
<i>Microcythere longiantennata</i> Marinov, 1962	7, 11-22, 25, 51		● p, Ebg	M, bt, eb, ps 225, 249, 392
<i>Microcythere varnensis</i> Marinov, 1962	25, 35, 51		● p, Ebg	M, bt, eb, l, ps, gw 225, 249, 389
Bythocytheridae				
<i>Bythocythere turgida</i> G. O. Sars, 1866	3, 7, 10, 21, 22, 24, 28	-70, 100	abam	M, bt, hb, ph, phs 247, 249, 252
<i>Sclerochilus gewemuelleri</i> Dubowsky, 1939 [<i>S. g. dubowskyi</i>]	7, 23, 24, 27, 28	3-100	clm	M, bt, eb, ph-zc-phs 225, 249, 392

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
Paradoxostomatidae, Cytheridae				
<i>Cytherois carcinitica</i> Marinov, 1964	24, 25	10-20	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, ro 249
<i>Cytherois cepa</i> Klie, 1937	23, 24, *79, *86	-2	● p	M, bt, seb, eh, ph 185, 249, 389
<i>Cytherois messambriensis</i> Marinov, 1964 [C. <i>pseudovitrea messambriensis</i>]	11, 25		● p, Ebg	M, bt, ep, ps 228, 249, 392
<i>Cytherois pontica</i> Marinov, 1966	11, 25	10-15	● p, Ebg	M, bt, ep, ps 234, 249, 392
<i>Cytherois pseudovitrea</i> Dubowsky, 1939 [C. <i>p. pseudovitrea</i>]	24, 25		● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ph 249
<i>Cytherois valkanovi</i> Klie, 1937	23, 24, *69	-25	● p	M, bt, ep, ph, zc 186, 249, 389
<i>Paradoxostoma abbreviata</i> G. O. Sars, 1866	7, 20		clm	M, bt 228, 392
<i>Paradoxostoma convexum</i> Schornikov, 1965	23, 24	-4	● p	M, bt, sep, ph, zc 249
<i>Paradoxostoma guttatum</i> Schornikov, 1965	24	-30	● p	M, bt, ep-mb, ph, ro 249
<i>Paradoxostoma intermedium</i> G. W. Müller, 1894	23, 24, *69, *86	-30	m, ? hom	M, bt, ep, ph, slc, zc 185, 249, 389
<i>Paradoxostoma ponticum</i> Klie et Whittaker, 1942	24, *86	-10	lm	M, bt, ep, ph, lt 185, 186, 249, 392
<i>Paradoxostoma simile</i> G. W. Müller, 1894	20, 24, 27, 28	15-83	m, hom	M, bt, eb, phc-ms-phs 228, 249, 392
COPEPODA: CALANOIDA				
Calanidae				
<i>Calanus euxinus</i> Huusemann, 1991 [? C. <i>helgolandicus</i>]	7, 10-17, 29		● p	M, p 160, 163, 269, 334
? <i>Calanus helgolandicus</i> (Claus, 1863)	3, 7, 10, 17, 29	0-150	amp	M, p, et 120, 198, 319, 389
Paracalanidae				
<i>Paracalanus parvus</i> (Claus, 1863)	7, 10-17, 29, 77	0-150	K	M, p, pp, et 91, 201, 304, 389
Clausocalanidae (Pseudocalanidae)				
<i>Pseudocalanus elongatus</i> (Boeck, 1865)	7, 10-17, 29, 69	0-200	anamnp	M, p 198, 317, 319, 389
Temoridae				
<i>Eurytemora affinis</i> (Poppe, 1880)	7, 29, 58, 80		anapnep, (h)	M-B, p, epp, eh 110, 252, 278, 279
<i>Eurytemora lacustris</i> (Poppe, 1887)	59		cp	M, p, eh, 0.5-0.8‰ 280
<i>Eurytemora velox</i> (Lilljeborg, 1853)	59, 60, 71, 77, 80, 88, 93		cpc, (tp)	M-B, p, eh, 0-10‰ 280, 294, 374, 389
Centropagidae				
? <i>Centropages kroyeri</i> Giesbrecht, 1893	3, 7, 10-17, 76, 77		amip	M, p 91, 304, 319, 374
<i>Centropages ponticus</i> Karavaev, 1895 [C. <i>kroyeri pontica</i> , ? C. <i>kroyeri</i>]	7, 11, 12, 29, *69, 76, 77		mrs	M, p, ■ 114, 198
Diaptomidae				
<i>Arctodiaptomus byzantius</i> Mann, 1940 [A. <i>byzantinicus</i>]	42		(seca)	L 252, 277, 279

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Arctodiaptomus salinus</i> (Daday, 1885) [<i>Diaptomus</i>]			(po)	L, p, 10%	91, 279, 389
<i>Neolovenula alluaudi</i> (Guerne et Richard, 1890) [<i>Lovenula</i> , <i>Paradiaptomus</i>]	78		(hom)	L, p	192, 252, 279
Pseudodiaptomidae					
<i>Calanipeda aquaedulcis</i> Kritchagin, 1873	7, 13, 29, 59, 60, *68-70, *74, 76-80, 83, 85, 88, 90, 92-95		lm, (hom)	B-L, p, eh, et	198, 201, 279, 280, 317, 319, 374, 389
Pontellidae					
<i>Anomalocera patersoni</i> Templeton, 1837	7, 29		amip	M, p, et, ■	198, 201, 319, 389
<i>Labidocera brunescens</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868)	7, 29		Imm	M, p, eh, th, ■	198, 201, 319, 389
<i>Pontella mediterranea</i> (Claus, 1863)	7, 12, 29, *69		Imm	M, p, ■	91, 198, 319, 389
Acartiidae					
<i>Acartia clausi</i> Giesbrecht, 1889	7, 10-17, 29, 68, 69, 76, 77, 80, 84	0-50	K, aamip	M, p, 10%, et	91, 198, 201, 304, 317, 319, 374, 389
<i>Acartia tonsa</i> Dana, 184	29		antamip, K, i	M, p, th	160, 204, 355
<i>Paracartia latisetosa</i> (Kritchagin, 1873) [<i>Acartia</i>]	7, *69, *79, 84		Immwi	M, p, 10%, th	279, 317, 319, 374
Copepoda: Monstrilloida					
Monstrillidae					
<i>Monstrilla grandis</i> Giesbrecht, 1891	7, 11, 29		amrsp	M, p	91, 198, 319, 389
COPEPODA: CYCLOPOIDA					
Oithonidae					
<i>Oithona brevicornis</i> Giesbrecht, 1891	29		amip	M-B-L, p	324
<i>Oithona davisae</i> Ferrari F.D. & Orsi, 1984	2-17		SK, i	M-B-L, p, eh, is	269, 355
<i>Oithona minuta</i> (Kritchagin, 1877; Scott, 1894) [<i>? O. nana</i> , <i>Dioithona</i>]	7, 11, 12, 29, *68, *79, 84, *86, 88	20	amip	M-B-L, p, eh, ■	84, 114, 198, 201, 317, 319, 374, 389
<i>Oithona nana</i> Giesbrecht, 1893 [<i>? = O. minuta</i>]	10-17, 29		K	M-B-L, p, eh	160, 324
<i>Oithona similis</i> Claus, 1866	7, 10-17, 16, 29	20-	K	M-B-L, p, eh, epp	198, 201, 319, 389
Cyclopidae					
<i>Halicyclops rotundipes</i> Kiefer, 1935 [<i>H. r. rotundipes</i>]	*69, 84, 88		(nem)	B, p, 0-10%	279, 374, 389
<i>Macrocyclops albidus</i> (Jurine, 1820)	59, 60		(k)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Macrocyclops fuscus</i> (Jurine, 1820)	59, 60		(hn, ? sk)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Eucyclops macruroides</i> (Lilljeborg, 1901) [<i>E. m. macruroides</i>]	85		(pat)	L, p, 0-30%	252, 277

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Eucyclops serrulatus</i> (Fischer, 1851) [<i>Cyclops</i>]	58-60, *68, 76, 77, *79, 80, 85, *86, 88, 92, 93		(sk, ? k)	L, p, 0.5-8%	252, 277, 278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Eucyclops speratus</i> (Lilljeborg, 1901)	60		(hptn, ? sk)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Euryte longicauda</i> Philippi, 1843	3		nam, ? namnz	M, p, r	160, 355
<i>Paracyclops affinis</i> (G. O. Sars, 1863)	60		(hpt)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Paracyclops fimbriatus</i> (Fischer, 1853)	90		(sk)	L, p, 0-30 %	252, 277
<i>Ectocyclops phaleratus</i> (Koch, 1838)	60		(sk)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Cyclops strenuus</i> Fischer, 1851	58, 60, 78, 79, 80, 84, *86, 92		(h)	L, p, eh	192, 193, 252, 277, 278, 280
<i>Cyclops vicinus</i> Uljanin, 1875 [C. v. <i>vicinus</i>]	7, 13, 29, 58-60, 78, 79, 84, 92		(ho)	L, p, eh	110, 192, 193, 198, 177, 201, 278, 280
<i>Megacyclops latipes</i> (Lowndes, 1927) [<i>Acanthocyclops</i>]	92		(h)	L, p	252, 277
<i>Megacyclops viridis</i> (Jurine, 1820) [M. v. <i>viridis</i> , <i>Cyclops</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, *86, 88		(hptn, ? sk)	L, p, 6%	278, 280, 374, 389
<i>Acanthocyclops robustus</i> (G. O. Sars, 1863) [? A. <i>americanus</i>]	58, 59, 60, 77, 80, *86		(hna, ? sk), i	L, p, is	252, 277, 278, 280
<i>Acanthocyclops vernalis</i> (Fischer, 1853)	78, 79, 85, 92		(sk, ? k)	L, p, epp	192, 193, 252, 277
<i>Diacyclops bicuspidatus</i> (Claus, 1857) [D. b. <i>odessanus</i> , <i>Acanthocyclops</i> , <i>Cyclops</i>]	59, 60, 79, 84, 85, *86, 92		(h, ? hn)	L, p, 20%, eh	252, 277, 280, 374
<i>Diacyclops bisetosus</i> (Rehberg, 1880) [<i>Acanthocyclops</i> , <i>Cyclops</i>]	33		(ha)	L, p, 10%	252, 277, 374, 389
<i>Metacyclops planus</i> (Gurney, 1909) [<i>Microcyclops</i>]	42		(wp)	L, p	252, 278
<i>Microcyclops minutus</i> Claus, 1863 [? <i>Metacyclops</i>]	69		(? pat)	L, p	279, 334
<i>Microcyclops varicans</i> (G. O. Sars, 1863)	76		(sk, ? k)	L, p, eh	119, 259
<i>Mesocyclops leuckartii</i> (Claus, 1857)	59, 60, 76, 92		(tp)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	252, 277, 279, 280
<i>Thermocyclops crassus</i> (Fischer, 1853) [<i>Mesocyclops</i>]	79, 80		(hptn, ? sk)	L, p, 0.5%	193, 252
<i>Thermocyclops dybowskii</i> (Landé, 1890)	60		(wcp, ? hop)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
<i>Thermocyclops oithonoides</i> (G. O. Sars, 1863)	60		(hop, ? h)	L, p, 0.5-0.8%	279, 280
Lernaeidae					
<i>Lernaea cyprinacea</i> Linnaeus, 1758	60		(h)	L, ec	389
COPEPODA: HARPACTICOIDA					
Longipediidae					
<i>Longipedia minor</i> T. Scott et A. Scott, 1893 [<i>L. portica</i>]	7, 10, 12, 24, 25, 27	10-100	cp	M, bt-p, eb, ph-sg-s	13, 17, 31, 249, 252
Canuellidae					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Canuella perplexa</i> T. Scott et A. Scott, 1893	7, 24, 25, 27, 61, 76, 78, 88	-65	nam	M, bt-p, mb, eh, 12-50%, ph-ps-s	185, 249, 252, 304, 389
<i>Canuella furcigera</i> G. O. Sars, 1903	1-22, 25, 26, 76, 96	-50	abam	M, bt, mb, ps, ps-s	17, 18, 31, 43, 240
<i>Canuella pontica</i> Apostolov, 1971	25, 35, 51, 86, 87		● p	M, bt, l, ps, gw	16, 18, 31, 249, 252
<i>Sunaristes paguri</i> Hesse, 1867			cp, ? amip	M, bt, co, ep	17, 31
Ectinosomatidae					
<i>Ectinosoma melaniceps</i> Boeck, 1865	16, 24-27, *69, 76, *86	1-100	amip	M, bt-p, eb, ph, ps, s	31, 84, 185, 249
<i>Ectinosoma normani</i> T. Scott et A. Scott, 1894	24, 25, 27	1-100	clm	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, s-ps	17, 31, 249
<i>Ectinosoma soyeri</i> Apostolov, 1975	19, 20, 35, 51		● p	M, bt, l, ps, gw	24, 31, 249, 252
<i>Halectinosoma abrau</i> (Kritchagin, 1877) [Ectinosoma]	35, 51		abam, (wcp)	M-B, bt, eh, ps, gw	16, 31, 249, 252
<i>Halectinosoma brevirostre</i> (G. O. Sars, 1904) [Ectinosoma]	7, 12, 23, 25, 27, 29	1.5-50	bap	M, bt-p, mb, ze, ps, s	17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Halectinosoma curticorne</i> (Boeck, 1872) [Ectinosoma]	25, 35, 84, 96	0-15	abam, (h)	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, gw	31, 249, 252, 263
<i>Halectinosoma elongatum</i> (G. O. Sars, 1904) [Ectinosoma]	7, 24, 25, 26	-30	bap	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, ps-s	17, 31, 43, 249, 252
<i>Halectinosoma herdmani</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1894) [Ectinosoma]	1-22, 24, 25, 26, 29	5-6, 30	cp, ? clm	M, bt-p, eu, ph, ps, s	13, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Pseudobradya beduina</i> Monard, 1935	7, 17, 24, 25	2-12	cp, ? clm	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, ps-s	26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Pseudobradya minor</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1896)	3, 7, 10, 13, 25, 26	5-25	acp	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	31, 246, 249, 252
<i>Glabrotelson bodini</i> Apostolov, 1974 [Hastigerella]	2, 35, 51		● p	M, bt, ls, ps, gw	23, 31, 249, 252
<i>Noodtiella wellsi</i> Apostolov, 1974	2, 35	0.80	● p	M, bt, ls, ps, gw	23, 31, 249, 252
Darcythompsoniidae					
<i>Leptocaris brevicornis</i> (van Douwe, 1905) [Horsfielda]	25, *78, *79		nam, (wcp)	M, bt, ep, l, eh, ph, ps	31, 249, 386, 389
Tachidiidae					
<i>Microarthridion littorale</i> (Poppe, 1881)	7, 25		abap, (h)	M-B, bt, l, ep, ps, if	31, 240, 246, 249
Harpacticidae					
<i>Harpacticus flexus</i> Brady et D. Robertson, 1873	1-22, 24, 25	1-2	clm, ? cp	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, s, eu	14, 15, 31, 43, 182
<i>Harpacticus gracilis</i> Claus, 1863 [<i>H. nicaeensis</i> var. <i>pontica</i>]	7, 24, 25, 29, 35		namni	M, bt, ep, ph, (p, ps)	31, 249, 304, 319
<i>Harpacticus littoralis</i> G. O. Sars, 1910	13, 16, 24, 25, 29, 76		namni	M, ep, ph, (p, ps), co	14, 15, 31, 249, 252
<i>Harpacticus nicaeensis</i> Claus, 1866	1-5, 11, 12, 13, 24, 25		nam, ? bap	M, bt, ep, ph, (ps)	31, 91, 157, 249
<i>Harpacticus obscurus</i> T. Scott, 1895	7, 24, 29		clp, ? clm	M, bt, ep, ph, (p)	31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Harpacticus uniremis</i> Kröyer, 1842	20, 24, 35, 51		anap, (h)	M, bt, eh, ph, gw, s, r	15, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Tigriopus fulvus</i> (Fischer, 1860) [<i>Harpacticus</i>]	32, 33		neamnp	M, 10-60%, spr	57, 392
Tisbidae					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Tisbe dilatata</i> Klie, 1949	20, 21, 22, 24	2-25	cp,	M, bt, ep, sl, ph-ro	31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Tisbe furcata</i> (Baird, 1837) [Idya]	7, 13, 24, 29, 76		anaminp, ? K	M, bt, p, sl, ph, eu	31, 84, 249, 304
<i>Scutellidium arthuri</i> Poppe, 1884	24		abap	M, bt, ep, ph	17, 31, 249
<i>Scutellidium longicauda</i> (Philippi, 1840) [<i>Machairopus</i> , <i>Psammathe</i>]	7, 11, 12, 24		am	M, bt, ep, ph	31, 91, 157, 249
Porcellidiidae					
<i>Porcellidium viride</i> (Philippi, 1840)	7, 24		clmwi	M, bt, ep, ph	17, 31, 249, 252
Peltidiidae					
<i>Alteutha typica</i> Czerniavski, 1868	1-22, 24		● p	M, bt, ep, ph	20, 31, 243, 249
Tegastidae					
<i>Tegastes longimanus</i> (Claus, 1863)	1-22, 24, 35		clp, ? clim	M, bt, ep, ph, (gw)	17, 25, 31, 249, 252
Thalestridae					
<i>Thalestris longimana</i> Claus, 1863	13, 24, 25, 29	-35, 100	bam, ? bap	M, bt (p), eb, ph, ps, s	16, 31, 249, 252
<i>Thalestris rufoviolascens</i> Claus, 1866	13, 24, 25	-30	clm	M, bt, ep, ph, ps-sg, s	15, 16, 31, 249, 252
<i>Parathalestris clausi</i> (Norman, 1868)	20, 24, 25, 26, 27	25-50	clp	M, bt, mb, ph, ps-s, et	17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Parathalestris dovi</i> Marcus, 1966	13, 24, 25	-12	lp, ? clp	M, bt, ep, sl, ph-lt	17, 31, 182, 249
<i>Parathalestris harpactoides</i> (Claus, 1863)	7, 24, 25, 35	0-50	ep, ? clim	M, mb, ph, ps, s, co	31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Phyllothalestris mysis</i> (Claus, 1863) [<i>Phyllopodopsillus</i>]	11, 12, 24, 25, 27	-90	clmi	M, bt, eb, ps, ph, s, et	31, 91, 249, 389
Rhynchothalestridae					
<i>Ambungipes rufocincta</i> (Brady, 1880) [<i>Rhynchothalestris</i>]	3, 24, 25		nami, ? bami	M, bt, eb, ph, ps-pe	17, 31, 249, 252
Dactylopusiidae					
<i>Diarthrodes assimilis</i> (G. O. Sars, 1906)	24		cpnei	M, bt, ep, sl, ph	17, 31, 249
<i>Diarthrodes minutus</i> (Claus, 1863)	24, *69		bam	M, bt, ep, sl, ph, eh	31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Diarthrodes nobilis</i> (Baird, 1845)	7, 16, 20, 24, 29, 66	-25	amswp	M, bt (p), ep, slc, ps-s	17, 20, 31, 243, 249
<i>Diarthrodes ponticus</i> (Kritchagin, 1873) [<i>D. p. orientalis</i>]	7, 13, 16, 24, 25	-25	clmwi	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, sg	17, 24, 31, 182, 263
<i>Diarthrodes pygmaeus</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1895)	16, 24		ami	M, bt, ep, ph, r	17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Dactylopusia tisburyi</i> (Claus, 1863) [<i>Dactylopodia</i>]	7, 11, 12, 24, 25, 35	-30, 50	aminz, ? SK	M, ph, gw, (sg, s), co	31, 91, 185, 249
<i>Dactylopusia vulgaris</i> G. O. Sars, 1905 [<i>Dactylopodia</i>]	20, 24, 25, 29, 35	-100	abam	M, bt (p), ph, gw (ps)	13, 14, 17, 31, 249
<i>Paradactylopodia brevicornis</i> (Claus, 1866) [<i>Dactylopusia</i>]	1, 11, 12, 24, 25, 35	-40, 100	naminz, ? SK	M, bt, ph, ps, ro, gw	31, 91, 249, 389
<i>Paradactylopodia latipes</i> (Boeck, 1865)	7, 20, 24, 25, 35	-20, 100	namni	M, bt, ph, gw, sg, s, r	14, 15, 17, 20, 31, 182, 249, 252
Pseudotachidiidae					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Dactylopodella flava</i> (Claus, 1866)	7, 24, 25, 26, 27	8-110		acmz	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, s	31, 243, 249, 252
Parasthenheliidae						
<i>Parasthenhelia hornelli</i> I. C. Thompson et A. Scott, 1903	16, 20, 24			anpip	M, bt, ep, ph, r	20, 31, 182, 249
<i>Parasthenhelia reducta</i> Apostolov, 1975	20, 21, 25	5		● p	M, bt, ep, ps, r	24, 31, 249, 252
<i>Parasthenhelia spinosa</i> (Fischer, 1860) [P. s. <i>bulgarica</i> , P. <i>forficula litoralis</i>]	7, 16, 24	-25		naminz, ? SK	M, bt, ep, ph, ps	31, 84, 249, 389
Miraciidae, Diosaccidae						
<i>Stenhelia elisabethae</i> Por, 1960 [Delavalia]	1-22, 25, 26			ep, ? clp	M, bt, sl, pe, co	31, 240, 249, 252
<i>Stenhelia normani</i> (T. Scott, 1905) [Delavalia]	7, 13, 24, 25, 27, 28	6-100		clm	M, bt, eb, ps, pe, ph	16, 18, 31, 43, 249
<i>Stenhelia palustris</i> (Brady, 1868) [Delavalia]	7, 25, 26	10		bam, ? bap	M, bt, ep, eh, ps, pe	17, 31, 43, 249, 252
<i>Stenhelia proxima</i> G. O. Sars, 1907	7, 25, 26, 27	10-30		cp	M, bt, ep, ps, pe, ph	17, 31, 43, 249
<i>Stenhelia reflexa</i> Brady et D. Robertson, 1880 [Delavalia]	10, 25	-25		anam	M, bt, sl, ep, ps	17, 31, 246, 249
<i>Stenhelia tethysensis</i> Monard, 1928 [Delavalia]	7, 12, 25, 27	10-100		m, ? nm	M, bt, eb, pe, ps-s	31, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Diosaccus tenuicornis</i> (Claus, 1863)	7, 17, 18, 24, 25, 35	15-30		nam	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, gw	20, 31, 249, 252
<i>Diosaccus varicolor</i> (Farran, 1913) [D. v. <i>biarticulatus</i>]	24			lm, ? clm	M, bt, ph	26, 31, 249
<i>Robertsonia knoxi</i> (I. C. Thompson et A. Scott, 1903)	7, 16, 20, 25, 27, 28	15-100		nami	M, bt, ps-s, ms, phs	10, 31, 248, 2490
<i>Robertsonia monardi</i> (Klie, 1937) [Varnaia]	24, 25, 69	0.3-3		cp	M, bt, sep, ps-s, ph	31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Sarsamphiascus caudaeosinus</i> (Brian, 1927) [Amphiascus]	24, 27, 28	-150		m, ? nm	M, bt, hb, pe, ph	31, 42
<i>Sarsamphiascus gracilis</i> Lang, 1936 [Amphiascus]	24			ap	M, bt, ph, lt	15, 17, 31
<i>Sarsamphiascus propinquus</i> (G. O. Sars, 1906) [Amphiascus, A. <i>angustipes</i>]	7, 18, 24, 25, 35	0-20		ami	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, gw	31, 242, 249
<i>Sarsamphiascus sinuatus</i> (G. O. Sars, 1906) [Amphiascus]	16, 24, 25, 27, 28, 29	30-150		nam, ? bam	M, bt (p), ph, ps, pe	14, 15, 31, 249, 252
<i>Amphiascopis cinctus</i> (Claus, 1866)	13, 24	6		amip, ? SK	M, bt, sep, ph, lt	17, 26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Amphiascopis minutus</i> (Claus, 1863) [Amphiascus]	11, 13, 20, 24, 25, 35	0-10		annep, SK	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, gw	14, 15, 31, 243, 249
<i>Amphiascopis thalastroides</i> (G. O. Sars, 1911) [Amphiascus <i>latilobus</i>]	7, 24, 25			clm	M, bt, ps, ph	31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Amonardia normani</i> (Brady, 1872)	13, 20, 24, 25, 27, 35	-85		ap	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, pe	15, 17, 31, 243, 249
<i>Amonardia similis</i> (Claus, 1866)	24, 25, 26	-30		lm	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, s	13, 31, 249
<i>Pseudamphiascopis attenuatus</i> (G. O. Sars, 1906)	13, 18, 25	-20		clm, ? nam	M, bt, ep, ps	26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Amphiascus longirostris</i> (Claus, 1863) [Paramphiascopis]	1-22, 24, 25, 27, 28	5-98		ham	M, bt (p), eb, eh, et, eu, ph, ps, s	14, 15, 17, 31, 240, 246, 249, 252
<i>Bulbamphiascus imus</i> (Brady, 1872)	1-22, 25-28	10-200		naminz	M, bt, eb, eu, pe, sg, s, ms, phs, ph	17, 31, 243, 246, 248, 249, 252
<i>Robertgurneya oligochaeta</i> Noodt, 1955	1-22, 25, 35	0-20		lm	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, gw	17, 18, 27, 31, 240, 249, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Robertgurneya rostrata</i> (Gurney, 1927)	25		namnei	M, bt, ps-pe 249
<i>Robertgurneya similis</i> (A. Scott, 1896)	7, 24, 25	8-40	lm	M, bt, mb, ps, sg, ph 18, 31, 246, 249
<i>Robertgurneya soyeri</i> Apostolov, 1974	20, 21, 22, 25	10	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 23, 31, 249, 252
<i>Robertgurneya spinulosa</i> (G. O. Sars, 1911)	13, 14, 25, 27	-40	cp, ? clim	M, bt, mb, ps, pe 27, 31, 249, 252
<i>Typhlamphiascus confusus</i> (T. Scott, 1902)	16, 25, 27	-80	clim	M, bt, eb, ps, pe, rh 31, 246, 249, 252
<i>Typhlamphiascus typhlops</i> (G. O. Sars, 1906)	17, 25, 26, 39	10-15	bam	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, s 17, 19, 31, 249, 252
<i>Amphiascoides brevifurca</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868) [<i>A. speciosus</i>]	24, 25, 26, *86		lm	M, bt, ep, ph, pe, ps 17, 31, 185, 249
<i>Amphiascoides debilis</i> (Giesbrecht, 1881) [<i>Amphiascella</i>]	7, 24, 25, 26		anam	M, bt, ph, ps, s 31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Amphiascoides neglecta</i> (Norman et T. Scott, 1905) [<i>Amphiascella</i>]	24, 25, 26		cp, ? clim	M, bt, ps, ps-s, s 249
<i>Amphiascoides subdebilis</i> (Willey, 1935) [<i>Amphiascella</i>]	7, 24, 25, 26	8	antami	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, s 12, 17, 31, 243, 249
<i>Mesamphiascus junodi</i> (Monard, 1935) [<i>Haloschizopera</i>]	18, 25, 26	30	nam	M, bt, ep, ps, pe 19, 31, 249, 252
<i>Haloschizopera pontarchis</i> Pot, 1959	1-22, 27, 28	25-200	adp	M, bt, hb, ms, phs, s 31, 240, 249, 252
<i>Schizopera brusinae</i> Petkovski, 1954	7, 22, 25, 35, 51, 95		m, ? nm	M, bt, l-sl, ps, gw 22, 30, 31, 242, 249
<i>Schizopera chaetosa</i> Petkovski, 1954	25, 71, 92		m, adp	M, bt, ps, if 15, 18, 30, 31, 249
<i>Schizopera clandestina</i> (Klie, 1924)	25, *86, 88, 96		neamnz, (pa)	M, bt, 3%, ps, eh 14, 31, 185, 249
<i>Schizopera compacta</i> De Lint, 1922	7, 25, 69		clm, (cse)	M, bt, ep, ps, eh 15, 22, 31, 249, 252
<i>Schizopera jugurtha</i> (Blanchard et Richard, 1891)	7, 25, 35	0-5	hom, (atm)	M, bt, l-sl, ep, ps, if 16, 17, 22, 31, 249
<i>Schizopera kunzi</i> Apostolov, 1967	7, 25, 35		● p	M, bt, ps, if 9, 13, 14, 31, 249
<i>Schizopera langi</i> Petkovski, 1954	7, 25, 35		m, adp	M, bt, ep, ps, gw, r 16, 22, 30, 31, 249
<i>Schizopera meridionalis</i> Petkovski, 1954	7, 13, 25, 35		cm, (e)	M, bt, l, ps, gw 22, 30, 31, 240, 249
<i>Schizopera neglecta</i> Akatova, 1935	25, 94		pc, (? wcp)	M, bt, eh, ps 12, 18, 22, 31, 249
<i>Schizopera petkovskii</i> Apostolov, 1971	25, 35, 51, 92		● p	M, bt, l, ps, gw, r 15, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Schizopera pontica</i> Chappuis et Serban, 1953	7, 25, 35		● p	M, bt, l, ps, gw, if 17, 31, 243, 249
<i>Eoschizopera gligici</i> (Petkovski, 1957)	7, 11, 26, 35, 84		m, adp	M, bt, l, ps, if, s, r 17, 22, 31, 249, 261
<i>Schizoperopsis arenicola</i> (Chappuis et Serban, 1953) [<i>Schizopera</i>]	7, 25, 35		● p	M, bt, l, ps, if 17, 22, 30, 31, 249
<i>Schizoperopsis varnensis</i> (Apostolov, 1967)	7, 11, 25, 35		● p	M, bt, l, ps, if 9, 13, 14, 17, 30, 31
Metidae				
<i>Metis ignea</i> Philippi, 1843	7, 16, 24, 25, 35	0-10	namwi, (hat)	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, if, s 17, 19, 31, 182, 249
Ameiridae				
<i>Ameira divagans</i> Nicholls, 1939 [<i>A. d. pontica</i>]	7, 24, 25	8	bap	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, r 31, 241, 246, 249
<i>Ameira longipes</i> Boeck, 1865	20, 24, 25	5-72	annei	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, et 15, 31, 249, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Ameira parvula</i> (Claus, 1866) [<i>A. p. tenuiseta</i> , <i>A. tau</i>]	7, 11-13, 24, 25, 76, *86	0-12	nami	M, bt-p, sep, ph, ps, ps-s, s, co 26, 31, 84, 91, 185, 249, 389
<i>Ameira scotti</i> G. O. Sars, 1911 [<i>A. s. brevicornis</i>]	7, 20, 24, 25, 27	0-70	ham	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, if, s 15, 31, 243, 249
<i>Filexilia attenuata</i> (Thompson, 1893) [<i>Ameira tenella</i>]	20, 25, 35		cp	M, bt, ph, ps, s (gw) 15, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Filexilia brevipes</i> (Kunz, 1954) [<i>Ameira, A. b. pontica</i>]	1, 7, 12, 13, 16, 25, 35	0-10	cp	M, bt, ep, ph, ps, if, r 12, 15, 17, 26, 31
<i>Filexilia pestae</i> (Petkovski, 1955) [<i>Ameira, A. brevipes pestae</i>]	1, 7, 12, 22, 24, 25, 27	10-70	m, adp	M, bt, eb, ph, pe, ps 19, 31, 240, 249
<i>Nitokra affinis</i> Gurney, 1927 [<i>N. a. californica</i>]	7, 13, 25, 35, 95	0-10	amip, (m)	L-eh, bt, ps, gw-if, ph 18, 28, 31, 244, 249
<i>Nitokra divaricata</i> Chappuis, 1923	25, 35, 79		adpc, (cseca)	L-B, bt, gw, ps-s, co 17, 31, 249, 250
<i>Nitokra fallaciosa</i> Klie, 1937	35, *69, 76		clm, (wp)	L-B, 60%, bt, pe, gw 31, 86, 185, 389
<i>Nitokra fragilis</i> G. O. Sars, 1905	24, 69		amiswp, (ha)	B-L, bt, sep, ph 17, 31, 249
<i>Nitokra hibernica</i> (Brady, 1880) [<i>N. h. bulgarica</i> , <i>N. h. hialina</i> , <i>N. inuber</i>]	2, 24, 35, 41, 71, 92		clm, (et)	B-L, bt, ph, ps-if, co 25, 31, 185, 389
<i>Nitokra lacustris</i> (Shmankevich, 1875)	16, 18, 20, 24, 25, 35, 76, 77, 95		SK, (pat)	L-B, eh-0-60%, bt, ps, gw, pe, ct, ph, et 14, 15, 21, 31, 243, 249, 252, 263
<i>Nitokra mediterranea</i> Brian, 1928 [<i>N. m. pontica</i>]	25, 95	10	ep	L, eh, bt, ep, ps 28, 31, 249, 252
<i>Nitokra pontica</i> Jakubisiak, 1938 [<i>N. typica</i> var. <i>pontica</i>]	4, 25		● p	L, eh, bt, ep, ps, r 31, 157, 249, 389
<i>Nitokra pusilla</i> G. O. Sars, 1911	7, 20, 25, 35		cp, ? nap	L, eh, bt, ps, gw 31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Nitokra spinipes</i> Boeck, 1865	7, 20, 22, 24, 25, 35, *69, 76		nami, ? K, (h)	L, eh, bt (p), ph, ps, if 31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Nitokra stygia</i> (Apostolov, 1976)	20, 25		● p, (Ebg)	L-B, eh, ps, cr 25, 31, 249, 252
<i>Nitokra typica</i> Boeck, 1865 [<i>N. t. adriatica</i>]	7, 16, 20, 25, 35	0-35	anam, (h)	L, eh, bt, mb, ps, gw 14, 15, 31, 84, 249
<i>Ameiropsis reducta</i> Apostolov, 1973	11, 17, 24, 25, 85	10	● p	M, bt, ep, ph, ps 20, 31, 182, 249
<i>Sicameira intermedia</i> Marinov, 1973	10, 17, 25	26	● p	M, bt, ep, ps 31, 241, 249, 252
<i>Pseudoleptomesochrella halophila</i> (Noodt, 1952)	16, 17, 19, 22, 25, 35	0.8	cp	M, bt, l, ps, sg, gw-if 12, 14, 31, 249, 263
<i>Leptomesochra africana</i> Kunz, 1951 [<i>Paraleptomesochra</i>]	7, 25, 35	0-25	amimp	M, bt, ep, ps, sg, if 31, 241, 249, 252
<i>Paravansula wellsi</i> (Marinov, 1973) [<i>Philoleptomesochra</i>]	10, 11, 17, 25	-20	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s 31, 241, 244, 249
Paramesochridae				
<i>Paramesochra hegelandica</i> Kunz, 1936	7, 11, 18, 25	10-30	namnei	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s 18, 31, 240, 249
<i>Paramesochra similis</i> Kunz, 1936	7, 11, 25, 35		cp	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw 14, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Kliopsyllus constrictus</i> (Nicholls, 1935)	17, 20, 25, 35, 94	0-10	ccim, ? bam	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw 14, 17, 31, 240, 249
<i>Kliopsyllus holsaticus</i> (Klie, 1929)	25		annei	M, bt, ps, r 31, 249
<i>Scottopsyllus herdmani</i> (I. C. Thompson et A. Scott, 1899) [<i>Paramesochra</i>]	1-22, 25, 35	0-20	bap	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, if 31, 240, 249, 252
<i>Scottopsyllus intermedius</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1895)	7, 25, 26, 35		cp	M, bt, ep, ps, pe, gw 19, 31, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Scotopsyllus minor</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1895)	20, 25, 35		bap	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw 12, 14, 17, 31, 249
<i>Scotopsyllus robertsoni</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1895)	11, 22	0.5-10	cp	M, bt, ep, ps 18, 31, 240, 249
Tetragonicipitidae				
<i>Phyllopodopsyllus briani</i> Petkovski, 1955	7, 22, 25, 35, 95		adp	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw 13, 17, 31, 244, 249
<i>Phyllopodopsyllus pauli</i> Crisafi, 1960 [<i>Ph. ponticus</i>]	7, 22, 25, 35, 95	8-12	hom	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, gw 11, 19, 31, 249, 252
<i>Phyllopodopsyllus thiebaudi</i> Petkovski, 1955	7, 22, 25, 35, 95		lmwp	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, if 17, 18, 31, 249, 252
<i>Diagoniceps kunzi</i> Marinov, 1973	17, 18, 25	20	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, r 31, 242, 249, 252
Canthocamptidae (Orthopsyllidae, Cyliindropsyllidae part)				
<i>Mesochra aestuarii</i> Gurney, 1921 [<i>M. apostolovi</i> , <i>M. pontica</i>]	25, *68, *69, *74, 84, 88, 90, 94, 96		neamj, (tp)	M-B-L, eh, l-16%, bt, ps, ps-s 17, 31, 185, 249, 252, 389
<i>Mesochra heldti</i> Monard, 1935	16, 24, 25, 49, 76		lm, (hom)	B-M, bt, l-sl, ph, ps, s 31, 84, 249, 389
<i>Mesochra liljeborgi</i> Boeck, 1864	24, 25, 35, *86,		ham, (h)	B-M, bt (p), ph, ps-s 31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Mesochra pestai</i> Lang, 1948	24, 25		● p	B, bt, ph, ps 31, 249, 262, 276
<i>Mesochra pygmaea</i> (Claus, 1863)	12, 24, 25, 26, *69, 76	8-120	namip	B, bt-p, eu, ph, ps, pe 31, 91, 185, 249
<i>Mesochra rapiens</i> (Schmeil, 1894)	24, 25, *69, 76		cpj, (h)	B, bt, ph, ps-pe 31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Mesochra xenopoda</i> Monard, 1935	7, 24, 26, 35, *69		ham, (atm)	B, bt, l-sl, ph, pe, gw 31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Orthopsyllus linearis</i> (Claus, 1866)	12, 25, 27, 28	35-200	ami	L, bt, eu, ph, ps, s, et 26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Itunella intermedia</i> Apostolov, 1975	25, 92		● p, (Ebg)	B-L, bt, l, ps, if 24, 31, 249, 252
<i>Itunella muelleri</i> (Gagern, 1923)	7, 25, 35		clm, (e)	B-L, l, ps-gw, if 17, 18, 31, 249, 252
<i>Nannomesochra arupinensis</i> (Brian, 1925)	13, 24, 25, 28	-100	namp	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, phs 26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Stenocaris minor</i> (T. Scott, 1892)	7, 11, 12, 25, 35, 92	0-20	clm, ? bap	L-M, bt, ep, ps, gw 14, 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Verniticaris pontica</i> (Chappuis et Serban, 1953) [<i>Stenocaris</i>]	1-22, 25, 35		cp	L-M, l, ps, gw, if 17, 22, 31, 240, 244, 249, 252
<i>Stenocaris valkanovi</i> Marinov, 1974 [<i>Stenocaropsis</i>]	7, 18, 25, 35	0-25	● p	L-M, bt, ep, ps, (gw) 19, 31, 242, 249
Leptastaciidae (Cyliindropsyllidae part)				
<i>Leptastacus laticaudatus</i> Nicholls, 1935 [<i>L. l. intermedius</i>]	11, 25	10	cp	M, bt, ep, ps, r 18, 31, 249, 252
<i>Leptastacus macronyx</i> (T. Scott, 1892)	10, 11, 21, 25	8-50	nap	M, bt, mb, ps, sg 31, 240, 246, 249
<i>Leptastacus taurica</i> Marinov, 1973	10, 21, 25	-18	cp	M, bt, ep, ps, sg 31, 242, 246, 249
<i>Paraleptastacus holsaticus</i> Kunz, 1937	7, 20, 25, 35, 95		bap, ? nap	M, bt, eh, ps, gw, if 14, 15, 17, 31, 249
<i>Paraleptastacus spinicaudus</i> (T. Scott et A. Scott, 1895)	7, 11, 25, 35		clp	M, bt, eh, ps, gw, if 13, 14, 17, 18, 31
<i>Psammastacus confluens</i> Nicholls, 1935	18, 25, 35		cp, ? nap	M, bt, ph, ps, gw, r 26, 31, 249, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Leptopontiidae (Arenopontiidae)					
<i>Leptopontia curvicauda</i> T. Scott, 1892	7, 11, 16, 25		cp	M, bt, ep, ps	15, 19, 31, 249, 252
<i>Arenopontia subterranea</i> Kunz, 1937 [<i>A. pontica</i>]	1-33, 35		clmi	M, bt, ep, ps, if, gw	13, 14, 31, 240, 249
<i>Psammoleptastacus stygius</i> (Noodt, 1955) [<i>Arenopontia</i>]	17, 25, 35, 84		nap, ? calp	M, bt, ep, ps, (gw), r	31, 240, 249, 252
Cletodidae					
<i>Cletodes limnicola</i> Brady, 1872	1-22, 25, 28	20-100	clm, ? clmi	M, bt, hb, pe, s-ps, sg	31, 246, 249, 252
<i>Cletodes longicaudatus</i> (Boeck, 1872)	1-22, 25, 28	20-100	bam, ? nam	M, bt, hb, pe, s-ps, sg	31, 246, 249, 252
<i>Cletodes tenuipes</i> T. Scott, 1896	3, 10, 17, 25, 27, 28	20-250	nam	M, bt, hb, s-ps, ms, s	31, 246, 249, 252
<i>Enhydrosoma caeni</i> Raibaut, 1965	7, 25, 26, 76		lm	M, bt, pe, s-ps, (ps)	16, 31, 249, 252
<i>Enhydrosoma gariensis</i> Gurney, 1930 [<i>E. gariene</i>]	7, 25		cp	M, bt, eh, ps-s, ps	16, 31, 249, 252
<i>Enhydrosoma longifurcatum</i> G. O. Sars, 1909	25, 26, 27, 76	-50	nam	M, bt, mb, pe, ps-s	31, 249
<i>Enhydrosoma propinquum</i> (Brady et D. Robertson, 1880)	1-22, 25, 27, 28	4-90	nam	M, bt, eb, pe, s-ps, ps, et, eu	18, 31, 43, 240, 246, 249, 252
<i>Enhydrosoma sordidum</i> Monard, 1926	1-22, 25, 27, 28	15-150	ham	M, bt, hb, pe, s-ps, (ps)	16, 19, 31, 43, 240, 249, 252
<i>Cletocamptus confluens</i> (Schmeil, 1894)	25-28, 35, *66, *69		SK, (sk)	M-L, 60‰, ps, s, gw	31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Cletocamptus retrogressus</i> Schmankevitch, 1875	25, 26, 41, *69, 76, 77		nam, (h)	M-B, 60‰, eu, ps, s	31, 185, 249, 389
<i>Limnocyctodes behningi</i> Borutsky, 1926	25, 26, 35, 93		pca, (po), Rc	M, bt (p), eh, ps-s, gw	26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Stylicletodes longicaudatus</i> (Brady et D. Robertson, 1880)	1, 7, 10, 26, 27, 28	12-100	SK, antamip	M, bt, hb, phs, s-ps, s	31, 240, 249, 252
<i>Miroslavia longicaudata</i> Apostolov, 1980	25, 26, 95	-24	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	29, 31, 249, 252
Rhizothricidae					
<i>Rhizothrix pubescens</i> Por, 1959	1-22, 25, 26	20-30	● p	M, bt, ep-mb, pe, s-ps	31, 240, 249, 252
Argestidae					
<i>Eurycletodes latus</i> (T. Scott, 1892)	1-16, 26, 27, 28	20-150	cm	M, bt, eb, phs, pe	31, 240, 246, 249
<i>Pontocletodes ponticus</i> Apostolov, 1980	25, 95	24	adp	M, bt, ep, ps	29, 31, 249, 252
Laophontidae					
<i>Laophonte borecai</i> Jakubisiak, 1938	4		● p	M, bt	31, 157, 389
<i>Laophonte elongata</i> Boeck, 1873 [<i>L. e. triarticulata</i>]	7, 11, 16, 19, 24, 25, 27	3-40, 82	neamep	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, s	17, 31, 182, 249
<i>Laophonte parvula</i> G. O. Sars, 1908	7, 20, 25, 35	10	clm	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, gw	14, 15, 31, 249, 252
<i>Laophonte setosa</i> Boeck, 1865 [<i>L. similis</i>]	7, 11, 16, 24, *69, 76, *79, *86, 96		clm, ? ce	M-B, bt (p), eh, ph, et, co	31, 182, 185, 249, 252, 389
<i>Laophonte thoracica</i> Boeck, 1865	20, 24, 25, 28, 35	0-100	clm	M, bt, eb, ph, ps, s, et	14, 15, 31, 249, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Heterolaophonte curvata</i> (Dauwe, 1929) [<i>H. c. micrarthros</i>]	7, 16, 24		hom	M, bt, ep, ph, slc 31, 84, 240, 249
<i>Heterolaophonte stroemii</i> (Baird, 1834) [<i>H. s. brevicaudata</i> , <i>H. s. paraminuta</i>]	7, 10, 16, 20, 24, 27, 35	0-50	nam, (h)	M, eh, mb, ph, s-ps, if, gw, eu, et, co 14, 15, 16, 17, 31, 84, 182, 243, 249
<i>Heterolaophonte uncinata</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868) [<i>Laophonte</i>]	12, 13, 24, 49, *69		lm	M, bt, ep, eh, l, ph 31, 91, 249, 304
<i>Paralaophonte brevistris</i> (Claus, 1863) [<i>Laophonte</i>]	5, 7, 9, 24		namnei, ? SK	M, bt, ep, ph 31, 157, 282, 249
<i>Paralaophonte congenera</i> (G. O. Sars, 1908) [<i>P. c. mediterranea</i>]	20, 24, 25	-30	clmi	M, bt, ep, ph, slc, s-ps 26, 31, 249, 252
<i>Paralaophonte octavia</i> (Monard, 1935)	20, 21, 24, 35		m, ? hom	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ph, gw 17, 31, 249, 252
<i>Asellopsis duboscqui</i> Monard, 1928	7, 25, 26, 76	0-20	m, hom	M, bt, ep, ps, s-ps, s 18, 31, 240, 252
<i>Onychocamptus mohammed</i> (Blanchard et Richard, 1891) [<i>Laophonte</i>]	42, *68, *69, *74, *79, 82, 83, 84, *86, 88, 90, 92, 94		K, (k)	M-B-L, bt, ep, eh 31, 347, 389
<i>Klieonchocamptus kliei</i> (Monard, 1935) [<i>K. k. adriaticus</i> , <i>Onychocamptus</i>]	6, 7, 10, 16, 25, 35		lm	M, bt, ep, l, ps, gw, if 14, 19, 31, 244, 349
<i>Klieonchocamptus ponticus</i> (Serban et Plesa, 1957) [<i>Onychocamptus</i>]	25, 35		lmnei	M, bt, ep, l, ps, if 31, 17, 244, 249
Normanellidae				
<i>Normanella minuta</i> (Boeck, 1872)	7, 24	10, 100	ham	M, bt, eb, ph, pe, (ps) 12, 31, 249, 252
<i>Normanella mucronata</i> G. O. Sars, 1909	6, 7, 17, 20, 25, 27, 28	10-100	nam	M, bt, eb, ms, phs, ps 12, 31, 246, 249
<i>Normanella serrata</i> Por, 1959	1-22, 25, 27	40-70	m	M, bt, eb, ms, sg, s-ps 31, 243, 246, 249
Latiremidae				
<i>Delamarella karamani</i> Petkovski, 1957	7, 24, 35		adep	M, bt, l, gw, if, ph, r 12, 14, 31, 249, 252
COPEPODA: POECILOSTOMATOIDA				
Nereicolidae				
<i>Vectoriella marinovi</i> Stock, 1968	10, 13		• p	M, ec 252, 336
Ergasilidae				
<i>Ergasilus lizae</i> (Kroyer, 1863) [<i>E. nanus</i>]	*68		namsp. (ha)	M-B, ec 389
<i>Ergasilus sieboldi</i> von Nordmann, 1832	7		nam, (h)	B-L, ec 389, 412
Oncaeidae				
<i>Triconia minuta</i> (Giesbrecht, 1893 [1892]) [<i>Oncaea</i>]	7		K, i	M, p, r 160, 355
COPEPODA: SIPHONOSTOMATOIDA				
Lernaeopodidae				
<i>Clavellisa emarginata</i> (Kroyer, 1837) [<i>Anchorella</i>]	3, 7		cp, ? bap. (h)	M-B-L, ec 389, 412
BRANCHIURA: ARGULOIDEA				
Argulidae				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Argulus foliaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	71, 89, 93		(hno)	B-L, ec, 3%	374, 389
Cirripedia: Thoracica: Verrucomorpha				plankton larvae	
Verrucidae					
<i>Verruca spengleri</i> Darwin, 1854			lm	M, bt, r	249
Cirripedia: Thoracica: Balanomorpha				plankton larvae	
Chthamalidae					
<i>Chthamalus stellatus</i> (Poli, 1795)	3, 7, 16, 21, 22, 45, 50		amip	M, bt, spr, lt, epi	84, 249, 295, 389
<i>Euraphia depressa</i> (Poli, 1795) [<i>Chthamalus</i>]	45, 50		m, em	M, bt, spr, r	294
Chelonibidae					
<i>Chelonibia testudinaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	17		amip	M, bt, epi	379, 389
Balanidae					
<i>Amphibalanus eburneus</i> (Gould, 1841) [<i>Balanus</i>]	49, *68, *69, *78, *79, 84, *86, 88, 96		amip, i	M-B, bt-p, 7%, is, sl	103, 129, 249, 374, 389
<i>Amphibalanus improvisus</i> (Darwin, 1854) [<i>Balanus</i>]	1-22, 49, 68, *69, *79, 96	0-27	amip, ? K, i	M, bt, sl, eu, is, epi	84, 91, 103, 129, 249, 295, 317, 374
Cirripedia: Rhizocephala: Kentrogonida				plankton larvae	
Peltoagaridae					
<i>Septosaccus rodriguezii</i> (Fraisse, 1877) [<i>Peltoaster diogeni</i>]	7, 25		lm	M, pa	71, 84, 389
Sacculinidae					
<i>Sacculina carcini</i> Thompson, 1836 [<i>S. benedeni</i>]	1-22, 23, 24, 50		clmwi	M, pa	71, 72, 389
MALACOSTRACA: MYSIDA (MYSIDACEA)					
Mysidae					
<i>Siriella jaltensis</i> Czerniavsky, 1868 [<i>S. clausi</i>]	2, 3, 5, 7, 17, 20, 24	3, 0-4	ham, amwi	M, bt, ep, lt, mc, ph	35, 36, 370, 389
<i>Gastrosaccus sanctus</i> (van Beneden, 1861) [<i>H. normani</i>]	6, 7, 16, 20, 25, 51, *69	0-10	ami	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps	35, 36, 249, 370
<i>Leptomysis lingvura</i> (G. O. Sars, 1866) [<i>L. pontica</i> , <i>L. sardica</i>]	3, 5, 7, 16, 20, 24, 29	0-50	ace	M, bt-p, me, lt, slc, r	35, 36, 249, 389
<i>Hemimysis anomala</i> G. O. Sars, 1907	7, 24	-20	pc, clm, (h)	B-L, bt, ep, lt, ■	36, 114, 249, 389
<i>Hemimysis lamornae</i> (Couch, 1856) [<i>H. l. pontica</i> , <i>H. l. reducta</i>]	7, 16, 24	0.3-100	clmm	M, bt, eb, slc, ro	33, 36, 249, 389
<i>Diamysis mecznikowi</i> (Czerniavsky, 1882) [<i>D. bahirensis</i> , <i>D. b. mecznikowi</i>]	7, 58, *69, *79, *86, 88, 92, 95		● p	M-B, bt, eh, 0.6%	35, 36, 249, 347
<i>Limnomysis benedeni</i> Czerniavsky, 1882 [<i>Mysidella bulgarica</i>]	58, 59, 65, *68,	-9	pc, (e), Rc	B-L, bt-p, 5%, ep, ph	35, 205, 249, 373
<i>Haplostylus normani</i> (G. O. Sars, 1877) [<i>Gastrosaccus</i> , ? <i>G. sanctus</i>]	5		clmwi	M, bt	35, 249, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Mesopodopsis slabberi</i> (van Beneden, 1861)	1-7, 13, 24, 29, *69, 76, *78, *79	1-20, 50	eami, (e)	M-B, bt-p, ep-mb, eh, 1-40% ^{oo} , l-sl	35, 36, 198, 249, 317, 319, 370, 374
<i>Paramysis agigenis</i> Bacescu, 1940	3, 5, 7, 25, 26, 58, *69	0-4	ep	M, bt, ep, ps, ph, ps-s	35, 36, 249, 389
<i>Paramysis kroyeri</i> (Czerniavsky, 1882) [<i>Mesomysis</i>]	7, 26, *68, *69	1-22	● p	M-B, bt-p, ep, eh, pe	36, 97, 249, 370
<i>Paramysis pontica</i> (Bacescu, 1940)	7, 29	-100	● p	M, p-bt, eb, pe, ps	36, 198, 249, 319
MALACOSTRACA: AMPHIPODA					
Ampeliscidae					
<i>Ampelisca diadema</i> (A. Costa, 1853)	2, 3, 5, 7, 10, 13, 17, *69	1-27, 120	eamwi, ? SK	M, bt, eb, ps, sg, pe	81, 84, 249, 370
Ampithoidae					
<i>Ampithoe gammaroides</i> (Bate, 1856) [<i>Pleonexes</i>]	3, 24		clm	M, bt, ep, ph, slc	81, 249, 389
<i>Ampithoe helleri</i> Karaman, 1975	16	2	clmnei	M, bt, ep	370
<i>Ampithoe ramondi</i> Audouin, 1828 [<i>A. rubricata</i> , <i>A. vaillanti</i>]	1-22, 24	1-20	amip, ? SK	M, bt, ep, mc, slc	81, 91, 368, 370
<i>Cymadusa crassicornis</i> (Costa, 1857) [<i>Grubia</i>]	1-22, 24	1-3	ep	M, bt, seb, ph, mc	91, 249, 370, 389
Aoridae					
<i>Leptocheirus pilosus</i> Zaddach, 1844	13, 25, 26, *69, *79, 84, *86, 88	7	clm	M, bt, ep, ps-pe, r	249, 370, 374, 389
<i>Microdeutopus anomalus</i> (Rathke, 1843)	3	20-	nam	M, bt, hb, pe	81, 249, 389
<i>Microdeutopus damnoniensis</i> (Bate, 1856) [nomen nudum]	3, 7, 12, 16, 20, 25, 27, 69	8-95	bam	M, bt, eb, ps-pe, mc	168, 249, 370, 392
<i>Microdeutopus gryllotalpa</i> Costa, 1853	7, 13, 16, 24, 25, *69	5-20, 40	nam	M, bt-p, mb, mc, ph, ps, sg, s, l-sl	84, 91, 249, 368, 370, 374, 389
<i>Microdeutopus stationis</i> Della Valle, 1893	7, 25	-20	lm	M, bt, ep, ps, sg, r	171, 249, 389
<i>Microdeutopus versiculatus</i> (Bate, 1856) [<i>Coremapus</i>]	3, 13, 25, 26, 27, 68	10-80	clm	M, bt, eb, ps-s, pe, sg	81, 249, 370, 389
Atylidae					
<i>Nototropis guttiatus</i> (A. Costa, 1853) [<i>Atylus</i>]	7, 24, 25, *69,	-5, 100	clm, ? eam	M, bt (p), eb, ph, ps	84, 249, 368, 370
Behningiellidae					
<i>Cardiophilus baeri</i> G. O. Sars, 1896 [<i>C. marisnigrae</i>]	7, 9, 10, *69	10-20, 30	pc, cpc, Rc	M-B-L, bt, ep, co	84, 178, 249, 370
Biancolinidae					
<i>Biancolina algicola</i> Della Valle, 1893 [<i>B. cuniculus</i>]	11, 12, 24	1-3	ep	M, bt, sep, ph, slc	91, 249, 370, 389
Corophiidae					
<i>Monocorophium acherusicum</i> (Costa, 1857) [<i>Corophium</i>]	7, 16, 25, 69	-10	amip, ? SK	M, bt, ep, mc, ps	367, 368, 370

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Monocorophium insidiosum</i> (Crawford, 1937)	5, 16, 23, 24	1-3	amp, ? amip	M, bt, ep, ph, zc 370
<i>Crassicorophium bonellii</i> (Milne Edwards, 1830) [<i>Corophium</i>]	3, 7, 16, 24, 68, *69	0-12	amp	M, bt-p, sep, ph, s 81, 84, 249, 374
<i>Crassicorophium crassicornis</i> (Bruzelius, 1859) [<i>Corophium</i>]	*68, *69, *78, *79, 84, *86		abapbp	M, bt, eh-1%, ep 249, 368, 374, 389
<i>Chelicorophium curvispinum</i> (G. O. Sars, 1895) [<i>Corophium</i>]	59, 60, *68, *69, 76		pc, (e), Rc	B-L, eh, bt, ep 82, 84, 97, 249, 375
<i>Chelicorophium sowinskyi</i> Martynov, 1924 [<i>Corophium curvispinum</i> var. <i>villosus</i>]	58, 59, 60		pc, Rc	B-L, 5-6%, ps-pe, ph 82, 83, 369
<i>Corophium volutator</i> (Pallas, 1766)	7, 13, 26, 58, *68, 77, *79, 84	7	namswp	M, bt, 0.5%, ep, pe 249, 370, 374, 389
<i>Medicorophium runcicorne</i> (Della Valle, 1893) [<i>Corophium</i>]	3, 7, 26, 27, 28	18-100	ep, ? em	M, bt, hb, pe 81, 171, 249, 367
<i>Siphonocetes dellavallei</i> Stebbing, 1899	7, 25, 26, 27	-50	lmsa	M, bt, mb, ps, pe 171, 249, 392
Lysianassidae				
<i>Orchomene humilis</i> (Costa, 1853)	3, 28	80-90	clm	M, bt, shb, phs 81, 249, 389
Cheluridae				
<i>Chelura terebrans</i> Philippi, 1839	7		amip, ? SK	M, bt, ep 252
Dexaminidae				
<i>Dexamine spinosa</i> (Montagu, 1813)	11, 12, 13, 24, *69	1-25, 85	clmm	M, bt-p, eb, mc, ph 84, 91, 249, 370
Gammarellidae				
<i>Gammarellus angulosus</i> (Rathke, 1843) [<i>G. carinatus</i>]	1, 2, 3	0-40	anam	M, bt, ep-mb, l-sl 81, 249, 389
Eusiridae				
<i>Apherusa bispinosa</i> (Bate, 1857)	3, 11, 12, 24, 27, 28, 69	-100	anam, ? abam	M, bt, eb, ph, s 81, 91, 249, 370
Gammaridae				
<i>Gammarus aequicauda</i> (Martynov, 1931)	3, 7, 25, 51, 69, 77, 80, 84		lm	M, eh, bt, ep, ps 102, 252, 370
<i>Gammarus criniticornis</i> Stock, 1966	7	0.5	clm	M, bt, ep, r 270
<i>Gammarus insensibilis</i> Stock, 1966	16, 23, 24, 76	0-15, 30	lm	M, bt, ep, ph, ps-s, ro 252, 346, 370
<i>Gammarus subtypicus</i> Stock, 1966 [<i>G. locusta</i>]	1-22, *66, *68, *69, *74, 76-80, 82, 84, *86, 88	0-20	m, ep, ? em	M, bt, eh-1-50%, ep, mc, ro, l-sl 84, 86, 91, 249, 295, 370, 374, 389
<i>Echinogammarus foxi</i> (Schellenberg, 1928) [<i>Chaetogammarus</i>]	16, 23	2	m, ep, ? nm	M, bt, ep, zc 370
<i>Echinogammarus marinus</i> (Leach, 1815) [<i>Gammarus</i>]	7, 11, 13, 16, 25		bam	M, bt, ep, ps, ro 91, 249, 259, 389
<i>Echinogammarus olivii</i> (Milne Edwards, 1830) [<i>Chaetogammarus, Gammarus</i>]	7, 10, 16, 68, 69, 76	0-10	lm	M, bt, sep, mc, ro 84, 249, 346, 370
<i>Echinogammarus trichiatus</i> (Martynov, 1932) [<i>Chaetogammarus</i>]	58, 59, 60		pc, cpc, Rc	B-L, bt, ph 130

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Chaetogammarus ischnus</i> (Stebbing, 1899) [<i>Ch. i. major</i> , <i>Ch. tenellus behningi</i>]	58, 59, 60, *69		pc, cpc, Rc	M-B, eh, 0-12‰, sep, ro, l-sl, ■	82, 114, 249, 374, 389
<i>Dikergammarus haemobaphes</i> (Eichwald, 1841) [<i>D. h. fluviatilis</i>]	58, 59, 60, *69		pc, cpc, Rc	B, bt, ep, ph, ro	82, 249, 375, 389
<i>Dikergammarus villosus</i> (Sowinsky, 1894)	58-60, *68, 71, 92, 95		pc, cpc, Rc, (ean)	B-L, bt, 0.1-5‰, ep, sg, ro, ph, ■	82, 114, 249, 374, 389
<i>Iphigenella andrussowi</i> (G. O. Sars, 1896) [<i>Gammarus, Lanceogammarus</i>]	59, 60		pc, Rc	B-L, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, ■	82, 114, 174, 249, 389
<i>Shablogammarus shablensis</i> (Carausu, 1943) [<i>Gammarus, Iphigenella</i>]	59, 60		pc, Rc	B-L, bt, ep, ps, ps-s, ■	82, 114, 249, 389
Pontogammaridae					
<i>Pontogammarus borcae</i> Carausu, 1934 [<i>P. abbreviatus borcea</i>]	*63, 65		pc, Rc	B-L, bt, ep	82, 249, 369, 389
<i>Pontogammarus robustoides</i> (G. O. Sars, 1894)	58, 59, 60		pc, cpc, Rc	B-L, ep, eu, ph	82, 249, 369, 389
<i>Euxinia maeoticus</i> (Sowinsky, 1894) [<i>Gammarus, Pontogammarus</i>]	1-22, 51, 58, 59, 60	0.1-0.2	pc, Rc	B-L, eh, l, ps	91, 249, 369, 370
<i>Stenogammarus carausui</i> Derzhavin & Pjatakova, 1962	68		pc, Rc	B-L, ep	358
Hyalidae					
<i>Micropythia carinata</i> (Bate, 1862) [<i>Hyalé</i>]	3, 7, 20		ep	M, bt	178, 392
<i>Hyalé crassipes</i> (Heller, 1866)	24		lm	M, bt, ep-mb, mc	370
<i>Hyalé perieri</i> (Lucas, 1849)	1-22, 24, 26	-19	klm	M, bt, ep, mc	249, 368, 370
<i>Hyalé pontica</i> Rathke, 1837	3, 7, 24	0-50	clm	M, bt, mb, ph, mc	84, 167, 368, 370
<i>Apothyalé prevosti</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1830) [<i>Hyalé</i>]	7, 13, 16, 21, 22, 24	0-30	anam	M, bt, ep, ph, lt	84, 91, 249, 389
Talitridae					
<i>Talitrus saltator</i> (Montagu, 1808)	1-22, 49		clm	M, bt, sep, l-sp	171, 249, 392
<i>Orchestia boftae</i> Milne Edwards, 1840; ? <i>O. cavimana</i> Heller, 1865	7, 49, 52, 59		clm, ep	M-B-TL, bt, l-sp, eh	84, 249, 389
<i>Orchestia gammarellus</i> (Pallas, 1766)	3, 7-16, 46, 49, 52		ham	M-TL, bt, l-sp	81, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Orchestia mediterranea</i> (Pallas, 1766); Costa, 1853	80		clm	M-TL, bt, l-sp	218
<i>Orchestia montagui</i> Audouin, 1826	7, 11, 12, 46, 51, 52		ep, ? em	M-TL, bt, l-sp	84, 91, 249
<i>Pseudorchestoidea brito</i> (Stebbing, 1891) [<i>Talorchestia</i>]	11, 21, 22		clm	M-TL, bt, l-sp	84, 249, 389
<i>Deshayesorchestia deshayesii</i> (Audouin, 1826) [<i>Talorchestia</i>]	7, 11, 16, 46, 49, 52, 76		clm	M-TL, bt, l-sp	84, 91, 249, 389
Isaeidae					
<i>Microprotopus longimanus</i> Chevreux, 1887	2, 20, 21, 23, 24, 27	2-85	clp	M, bt, eb, ze, pe, sg, r	178, 249, 370, 392
Ischyroceridae					
<i>Jassacia</i> (Bate, 1862)	1-22, 24, 27	0-20	clm	M, bt, ep, ph, mc, ms	84, 91, 367, 368
<i>Erichthonius difformis</i> H. Milne Edwards, 1830	1-22, 24		anamnp	M, bt, sep, mc, ph	84, 91, 368, 370

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
Megaluropidae						
? <i>Megaluropus agilis</i> Hoeck, 1889	7, 69		eami		M-B, bt	370
<i>Megaluropus massiliensis</i> Ledoyer, 1976 [? <i>M. Agilis</i>]	7, 25	5-25	m, addep		M-B, bt, ep, ps, r	171, 249, 370, 392
Melittidae						
<i>Melita palmata</i> (Montagu, 1804)	1-22, 24, 27, *69	0-20	aam		M, bt, ep, mc-s, ph-ro	84, 249, 370, 374
<i>Cheirocratus sundevalli</i> (Rathke, 1843)	11, 16, 17, 20		clm		M, bt	173
Oedicerotidae						
<i>Periculodes longimanus</i> (Bate et Westwood, 1868)	1, 2, 3, 7, 13, 25, 69	2-20, 100	aami		M, bt, eb, ps, sls	81, 249, 367, 370
<i>Deflexilodes gibbosus</i> (Chevreux, 1888) [<i>Monoculodes</i>]	13, 16, 23, 25	16-100	clm		M, bt, hb, zc, sg	171, 249, 370
<i>Synchelidium maculatum</i> Stebbing, 1906	1, 2, 7, 13, 16, 27, 28	10-105	clm		M, bt, eb, ps, sg	81, 249, 389
Bathyporeiidae (Pontoporeiidae)						
<i>Bathyporeia guilliamsoniana</i> (Bate, 1857)	1-22, 25	-6, 25	clm		M, bt, ep, ps, sls	84, 249, 367, 370
Stenothoidae						
<i>Stenothoe monoculoides</i> (Montagu, 1815)	24, *69	0-10	clm, ? bam		M, bt, sep, ph, mc, lt	249, 368, 370, 374
Photidae						
<i>Megamphopus cornutus</i> Norman, 1869	3	10-50	clmm		M, bt, mb, pe, sg	81, 249, 389
Caprellidae						
<i>Phitica marina</i> Slabber, 1769 [<i>Ph. acaudata</i> , <i>Proto pedata</i>]	2, 3, 7, 16, 26, 27, 28	15-100	amwi		M, bt-p, hb, ph, sg, pe	91, 295, 351, 370
<i>Pseudoprotella phasma</i> (Montagu, 1804)	3, 24, 27	-98	clm, ? eam		M, bt, eb, ph, pe	178, 249, 389
<i>Caprella acanthifera</i> Leach, 1814 [<i>C. a. ferox</i>]	1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 11, 12, 16, 24, 27, 28	0.2-100	clm		M, bt, eb, ph, slc, pe, epi, eu	41, 66, 81, 84, 87, 89, 249, 351, 370
<i>Caprella danilevskii</i> Czerniavski, 1868	3, 16, 23, 24	0.5-8	tam, ? cst		M, bt, ep, slc, ph, zc	81, 249, 351, 370
<i>Caprella mitis</i> Mayer, 1890	7, 24	1-12	m, ep		M, bt, ep, slc, r	84, 249, 389
Malacostraca: Cumacea						
Pseudocumatidae (Pseudocumatidae)						
<i>Pseudocuma ciliatum</i> G. O. Sars, 1879	5, 7, 25	0.5-10	hom		M, bt, ep, ps	36, 249, 389
<i>Pseudocuma longicorne</i> (Bate, 1858) [<i>P. l. pontica</i>]	7, 21, 25, 69	1-7	clm, ? eamrs		M, bt, ep, ps	36, 169, 249, 370
<i>Pseudocuma tenuicauda</i> G. O. Sars, 1894 [<i>Stenocuma</i>]	7		pc, Rc		B-L, bt, ps, ps-pe, eh	358
Bodotriidae						
<i>Bodotria arenosa</i> Goodsir, 1843 [<i>B. a. mediterranea</i>]	7, 20, 22, 23, 25		clm		M, bt-p, ep, ps, zc	36, 249, 389
? <i>Bodotria scorioides</i> (Montagu, 1804)	3, 5		clmwi		M, bt-p, ep, ps	274, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Iplinoe elisae</i> Bacescu, 1950	1-22, 25, 27, 28, 69	9-95, 125	lm	M, bt, eb, ps, pe, phs	169, 249, 358, 370
<i>Iplinoe maeotica</i> Sowinskyi, 1893 [<i>I. inermis</i>]	7, 25, 26, 69	6-25	ep	M, bt, ep, ps-pe, s, eh	36, 356, 370, 274
<i>Iplinoe tenella</i> G. O. Sars, 1878	7, 10, 13, 25, 28, 69	7-78	clm	M, bt, eb, ps, phs	36, 249, 358, 370
<i>Cumopsis goodsir</i> (van Beneden, 1861) [<i>C. longipes</i>]	7, 25	0-16	clm	M, bt, ep, ps	36, 249, 370, 389
Nannastacidae					
<i>Nannastacus euxinicus</i> Bacescu, 1951	7, 21, 24, 25		m	M, bt, ep, ps, pe-lt	37, 249, 389
<i>Cumella limicola</i> G. O. Sars, 1879	5, 7, 16, 20, 21, 23, 25	0.5-1, 18	lmwiwp	M, bt, ep, ps, zc	249, 274, 370, 389
<i>Cumella pygmaea</i> G. O. Sars, 1865 [<i>C. p. euximica</i>]	1-22, 27, 28, 69	20-, 50-	clm	M, bt, hb, pe, phs	169, 249, 358, 392
Leuconidae					
<i>Eudorella truncatula</i> (Bate, 1856)	1-22, 27, 28	40-150	anamnep	M, bt, shb, pe, phs	169, 249, 358, 392
MALACOSTRACA: TANAIACEA					
Apsseudidae					
<i>Apsseudopsis acutifrons</i> (Sars, 1882) [<i>? Apsseudes ostroumovi</i>]	2, 3, 7, 13, 16, 27, 28	2-120	m, hom	M, bt, hb, ms, phs, zc	41, 249, 370, 389
<i>Apsseudopsis ostroumovi</i> Bacescu & Carausu, 1947	13	27, -100	● p	M, bt, sg, ms, phs, ■	114, 356
Tanaidae					
<i>Tanais dulongii</i> (Audouin, 1826) [<i>T. cavolinii</i>]	7, 14, 15, 23, 24, 69	1	aminwp	M, bt, ep, mc, zc, slc	36, 249, 358, 370
Paratanaidae (Leptocheilidae)					
<i>Heterotanais oerstedii</i> (Kroyer, 1842) [<i>H. gurneyi</i>]	16, 23, *79, 84, 88	1-25	clm	M-B, ep, 6%, zc	249, 370, 374, 389
<i>Leptocheilia savignyi</i> (Kroyer, 1842) [<i>L. dubia</i>]	3, 11, 12, 23, 24, 25	1-2	amip	M, bt, slc, zc, mc, ps	91, 249, 370, 389
MALACOSTRACA: ISOPODA					
Asellidae					
<i>Asellus aquaticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 60, *68, *74, 77, 80, 89		(h)	L-B, bt, 5%	374, 389
Janiridae					
<i>Jaera hopeana</i> Costa, 1853 [<i>J. charrieri</i>]	7		lm	M, bt, co	249, 376, 389
<i>Jaera nordmanni</i> (Rathke, 1837)	3, 7, 11, 16		clm	M-B-L, bt, ep	91, 93, 249, 377
<i>Jaera sarsi</i> Valkanov, 1936	58, 60, *68, *69, 84, 95		cp, Rc	M-B-L, eh, bt, ro	249, 374, 375, 377
Ligiidae					
<i>Ligia italica</i> Fabricius, 1798 [<i>L. brandtii</i>]	45		lmm, (hom)	M-T, spr, lt, ro	34, 84, 91, 249, 389
Tylidae					
<i>Tylos ponticus</i> Grebnitsky, 1874	7, 46, 52, 69		lm, (hom)	M-T, sps	249, 358

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Tylos latreillei</i> Audouin, 1826	7, 16, 46, 52		klm, (hn)	M-T, sps 84, 389
Idoteidae				
<i>Idotea balthica</i> (Pallas, 1772) [<i>I. b. basteri</i> , <i>I. tricuspoidata</i>]	1-22, 24, 25, 36-40, 49, 58-60, *69, 76-78, 84, 86, 88	0-5, 30	ham, ? SK	M, bt, ep, ph, l-sl 84, 91, 249, 370, 374, 389
<i>Idotea ostroumovi</i> Sowinsky, 1895 [<i>I. metalica</i> , <i>I. m. elongata</i>]	7, 10, 11, 29	100-150	em	M, p-bt, hb, r 36, 84, 249, 370
<i>Stenosoma capito</i> (Rathke, 1837) [<i>Idotea pontica</i> , <i>Synisoma</i>]	1-5, 7, 11, 12, 13, 16, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25	1-3, 92	m, hom	M, bt, ep, mc, zc, slc, ps, sg, ms, phs 36, 67, 84, 91, 93, 249, 370, 389
Limnoriidae				
<i>Limnoria tuberculata</i> Sowinsky, 1884	7		amip, ? SK	M, bt, ep 249, 252
Sphaeromatidae				
<i>Dynamene bidentata</i> (Adams, 1800) [<i>Naesa</i>]	1-22, 24, 25, 49	-3	clmi	M, bt, ep, mc, slc, ps 36, 289, 370, 389
<i>Lekanesphaera hookeri</i> (Leach, 1814) [<i>Sphaeroma pulchellum</i>]	7, 16, 23, 24, *69	0-40	clm	M, bt, sp-sl, ph, ro, s 84, 249, 389
<i>Sphaeroma serratum</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	1-5, 7, 12, 13, 15, 16, 24, 25, 46, 49, *69, 77, *78, *86	0-10	amiswp	M, bt, ep, l-sl, ps, slc, mc, ro, ph 91, 93, 249, 370, 374, 389
Gnathiidae				
<i>Gnathia maxillaris</i> (Montagu, 1804)	5		ace	M, bt-p, ec 34, 389
<i>Gnathia oxyurata</i> (Liljeborg, 1855)	7		ace	M, bt-p, ec 167, 249, 389
Cirolanidae				
<i>Eurydice dollfusi</i> Monod, 1930 [<i>E. d. maris-nigri</i>]	7, 10, 20, 22, 25, 51	0-3, 8	m, hom	M, bt (p), sep, ps 36, 249, 358, 370
<i>Eurydice pontica</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868)	7, 51		ep	M, bt (p), sep, l, ps 36, 249, 389
<i>Eurydice racovitzai</i> Bacescu, 1949	24, 25	2-5	● p	M, bt, ep, slc, lt 249
<i>Eurydice spinigera</i> Hansen, 1890	7, 16, 20, 21, 22	-6, 30	clm	M, bt-p, ep, pe 36, 84, 249, 370
<i>Eurydice valkanovi</i> Bacescu, 1949	7, 24, 25	2-14	● p	M, bt, ep, ps, ph 36, 249, 389
Cymothoidea				
<i>Livoneca sinuata</i> Kölbel, 1878 [<i>L. mediterranea</i> , <i>Cymothoa carryensis</i>]	7		lm	M, bt, ec 167, 389
<i>Mothocya taurica</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868) [<i>Livoneca pontica</i> , <i>L. punctata</i> , <i>Cymothoa</i>]	3, 7		● p	M, bt, ec 249, 389, 412
Bopyridae				
<i>Anisarthrus pelseneri</i> Giard, 1907	16		cp, ? clip	M, bt, pa 94, 249, 389
<i>Bopyrissa diogeni</i> (Popov, 1927) [<i>Pseudione</i>]	7		cp, ? clip	M, bt, pa 71, 249, 389
<i>Bopyrus squillarum</i> L'treille, 1802	7		clmi	M, bt, pa 91, 249, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
MALACOSTRACA: DECAPODA				
Palaemonidae				
<i>Palaemon adpersus</i> Rathke, 1837 [<i>Leander rectirostris</i>]	7, 12, 13, 23, 24, *69, *78, *79, 84, 88	-35	eami	72, 249, 358, 370, 374, 389
<i>Palaemon elegans</i> Rathke, 1837 [<i>Leander squilla</i> var. <i>elegans</i>]	1-22, 24, *69, 77, 96	0-30	eam	72, 249, 370, 371, 389
<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i> Rathbun, 1902	69		j, SK, i	355
<i>Palaemon serratus</i> (Pennant, 1777) [<i>Leander triellianus</i>]	3, 7, 13, 20, 77	7	eamrs	40, 91, 214, 249
Alpheidae				
<i>Alpheus dentipes</i> Guérin-Méneville, 1832	16	10-17, 40	lmmg	78, 249, 252
<i>Athanas nitescens</i> (Leach, 1814)	5, 7, 11, 12, 13, 16, 24	3-25, 50	eam	72, 249, 371, 389
Hippolytidae				
<i>Hippolyte leptocerus</i> (Heller, 1863)	16, 24	3	eam	370, 371
<i>Hippolyte sapphica</i> D'Udekem d'Acoz, 1993 [<i>H. gracilis</i> , <i>H. longirostris</i> , <i>Virbius</i>]	7, 11, 13, 16, 20, 23, 24	2-25, 48	lm, ? lmm	36, 72, 91, 249, 371
Processidae				
<i>Processa edulis</i> (Risso, 1816)	5, 7, 16		eamrs	36, 249, 389
Crangonidae				
<i>Crangon crangon</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>C. maculosus</i> , <i>C. vulgaris</i> var. <i>maculosus</i>]	7, 11, 13, 25, 27, 28, 76, 77	5-100	ce, ? namj	36, 72, 249, 371
<i>Philocheirus fasciatus</i> (Risso, 1816) [<i>Pontophilus</i>]	13, 16, 24, 25	1-2, 12	clmm, ? eam	36, 75, 249, 389
<i>Philocheirus trispinosus</i> (Hailstone, 1835) [<i>Pontophilus</i>]	7, 16, 20, 22,	-15	clmm, ? eam	36, 249, 389
Nephropidae (Homaridae)				
<i>Homarus gammarus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>H. vulgaris</i>]	3, 7, 12, 16, 17	40-45	clmm	72, 84, 103, 189, 249, 296, 389, 410
Astacidae				
<i>Astacus leptodactylus</i> Eschscholtz, 1823	58, 59, 60, *67, *68, 71, 79, 84, 92, 95		(e), ? Rc	74, 91, 206, 249, 286, 389
Callinassidae				
<i>Pestarella candida</i> (Olivi, 1792) [<i>Callinassa pestae</i> , <i>C. pontica</i> , <i>C. tyrhena</i>]	4, 7, 11, 16, 20, 25, 26	0.5-15	lm	36, 77, 84, 249, 389
<i>Necallinassa truncata</i> (Giard et Bonnier, 1890) [<i>Callinassa</i>]	24, 25		lm	214
Upogebiidae				
<i>Upogebia pusilla</i> (Petagna, 1792) [<i>U. littoralis</i> , <i>Gebia</i>]	7, 25, 26, 69, *79, 84, *86	-22	clmm	72, 84, 91, 249, 370

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Porcellanidae					
<i>Pisidia longicornis</i> (Risso, 1815) [<i>Porcellanides</i> , <i>Porcellana longimana</i>]	1-22, 24, 50, 69	0-40	eam	M, bt, mb, ph, mc, ro	72, 73, 84, 249, 370
Diogenidae					
<i>Diogenes pugilator</i> (Roux, 1829) [<i>D. varians</i>]	1-22, 25, 36-40, 69	0-15, 40	eam, ? eami	M, bt, mb, ps, sg, ■	72, 84, 91, 358, 371
<i>Clibanarius erythropus</i> (Latreille, 1818) [<i>C. misanthropus</i>]	1-22, 24, 25		lmmg, ? eami	M, bt, ep, lt, ro	72, 73, 84, 249, 389
Majidae, Inachidae					
<i>Macropodia longirostris</i> (Fabricius, 1775) [<i>Stenorhynchus egyptius</i>]	3, 5, 7, 11, 12, 16, 21, 23, 24	0-20	clmm	M, bt, ep, ph, zc, slc	34, 72, 86, 249, 389
Portunidae					
<i>Callinectes sapidus</i> Rathbun, 1896	3, 5, 7, 13	5-22	amj, i	M, bt, ep, ps, s, r	76, 103, 249, 371
<i>Portunus latipes</i> (Pennant, 1777)	7, 16, 21	3	clm	M, bt, ep, ps	36, 72, 75, 249, 389
<i>Carcinus aestuarii</i> Nardo, 1847 [<i>C. maenas</i> , <i>C. mediterraneus</i>]	1-22, 23, 24, 25, *69,	0-70	lm, ? amp	M, bt, ps, zc, ro, r, ■	72, 73, 84, 370, 371
<i>Liocarcinus depurator</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Macropipus</i> , <i>Portunus</i>]	7		cem, ? eam	M, bt, r	84, 249, 370, 371
<i>Liocarcinus navigator</i> (Herbst, 1794) [<i>L. arcuatus</i> , <i>Macropipus</i> , <i>Portunus</i>]	7, 11, 16, 25, *69	3-80	acem	M, bt, eb, ps, sg, s, ■	72, 73, 84, 249, 389
<i>Liocarcinus vernalis</i> (Risso, 1827) [<i>Portunus holsatus</i> , <i>Macropipus</i>]	7, 11-13, 16, 25, 36-40, *69, *78, *79, 84, *86, 88	-80	clmm, ? eam	M, bt, eb, eh, ps, sg	72, 73, 91, 249, 370, 371, 389
Xanthidae (Eriphiidae, Panopeidae, Pilumnidae)					
<i>Eriphia verrucosa</i> (Forskål, 1775) [<i>E. spinifrons</i>]	1-22, 24, 45, 50	0-30	lmm, ? lmmg	M, bt, ep, sp-l-sl, lt, ro, ■, ▲	72, 73, 91, 114, 249, 370, 371, 389
<i>Pilumnus hirtellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1761) [<i>P. h. var. villosus</i> , <i>P. villosus</i>]	1-22, 24, *69	0-40	clmm	M, bt, mb, ph, mc, lt, ro, slc, ■	72, 73, 84, 91, 249, 358, 370, 371, 389
<i>Xantho poressa</i> (Olivier, 1792) [<i>X. hydrophilus</i> , <i>X. rivulosus</i>]	1-22, 24, 69	1-15, 100	lmm	M, bt, eb, ro, ■	72, 84, 91, 249, 371
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i> (Gould, 1841) [<i>R. h. tridentatus</i>]	7, *68, *69, 87, 96	-10	nam, i	M-B, bt, ps, ps-s	95, 164, 371, 386
Potamidae (Potamonidae)					
<i>Potamon ibericum</i> (Bieberstein, 1808) [<i>P. fluviatile</i> , <i>P. potamios</i> , <i>P. tauricum</i>]	43, 74, 87, 92, 94		(nmwca)	L, eu, ro, ph, ■	69, 114, 214
Grapsidae (Varunidae)					
<i>Brachynotus gemmellari</i> (Rizza, 1839) [<i>Cleistostoma</i>]	7	15	m, hom	M, bt, r	370, 371
<i>Brachynotus sexdentatus</i> (Risso, 1827) [<i>Heterograpsus (Brachynotus) lucasi</i>]	7, 13, 25, 26, *69	1, 9-40	hom, lm, clm	M, bt, mb, ps-pe, s, ph	72, 73, 84, 249, 358, 370, 371, 389
<i>Pachygrapsus marmoratus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	1-22, 24, 45, 50	0-7	clmm	M, bt, sep, spr-sl-r, lt, ro, ■	72, 84, 91, 114, 249, 370, 371, 389
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1854)	? 96		(esca, sk - i)	L-B, eu, is	214

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
HEXAPODA: ENTOGNATHA					
COLLEMBOLA					
Neanuridae					
? <i>Anurida maritima</i> (Guérin-Méneville, 1836)	45, 46, 49, 52		nam, (hnat)	M-TL, l, sp	47, 84, 249
<i>Friezea acuminata</i> (Denis, 1925)	1-22, 59, 60		lm, (nm)	M-TL, l	247, 249, 252
Onychiuridae					
<i>Protaphorura finata</i> (Gisin, 1952) [<i>Onychiurus</i>]	1-22		(e)	TL, sp-l	247, 249, 252
Isotomidae					
<i>Archisotoma besselsi</i> (Packard, 1877)	1-22, 51, 52		acc, (h)	M-TL, sp-l, ps	247, 249, 252
Entomobryidae					
<i>Seira ferrarii</i> Parona, 1888	1-20, 25, 51		(m, hom)	M-TL, l-sl, ps	247, 249, 252
HEXAPODA: INSECTA					
EPHEMEROPTERA					
Siphonuridae					
<i>Siphonurus lacustris</i> (Eaton, 1870)	80		(tp)	L-TL	218
Baetidae					
<i>Cloeon dipterum</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	58, 77, 80		(h)	L-TL, bt, ph	218, 258
<i>Centroptilum luteolum</i> (Müller, 1776)	58		(tp, ? hes)	L-TL, bt, ph	218, 258
Caenidae					
<i>Caenis horaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 77, 80		(tp)	L-TL, bt, ph	218, 258
<i>Caenis luctuosa</i> (Burmeister, 1839)	58, 59, 77, 80		(wcp, ? hoes)	L-TL, bt, ph	218, 258
<i>Caenis robusta</i> Eaton, 1884	58		(tp)	L-TL, bt, ph	218, 258
ODONATA					
Calopterygidae					
<i>Calopteryx splendens</i> (Harris, 1782)	65, 71, 73, 83, 84, *86, 91, 92		(wcp)	L-TL, ■, ◆	114, 216, 217
<i>Calopteryx virgo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	83, 91, 92, 94		(tp)	L-TL, ■, ◆	114, 216
Euphaeidae					
<i>Epallage fatime</i> (Charpentier, 1840)	92		(om)	L-TL, ■, ▲, ◆	114, 216, 217
Lestidae					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Lestes barbarus</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	58, 60, 61, 63, 70, 72, 74, 76-78, 80-82, 84-86, 88, 92, 95		(wpo)	L-TL, 13%	216, 217, 218, 258
<i>Lestes dryas</i> Kirby, 1890	58, 80, *86, 88		(h)	L-TL	215, 216, 217, 218
<i>Lestes macrostigma</i> (Eversmann, 1836)	76, 80		(mwca)	L-TL, 14% ₀₀ , ha	59, 119, 216, 217
<i>Lestes parvidens</i> (Artobolevski, 1929) [<i>Chalcolestes</i>]	71, 77, 78, 81, 83-85, 91, 94		(nemit)	L-TL	216, 217
<i>Lestes sponosa</i> (Hansemann, 1823)	58, 63, *78		(tp)	L-TL	59, 216, 217
<i>Lestes virens</i> (Charpentier, 1825)	77, 78, 81		(wp)	L-TL	216, 217, 258
<i>Lestes viridis</i> (Vander Linden, 1825) [<i>Chalcolestes</i>]	77, 86, 88, 90, 91		(hom)	L-TL, ▲, ◆	217, 258
<i>Sympetma fusca</i> (Vander Linden, 1820)	58, 60, *61, 69, 71, 80, 84		(omca)	L-TL	59, 215, 216, 218
Platycnemididae					
<i>Platycnemis pennipes</i> (Pallas, 1771)	60, 65, 68, 71-76, 78, 84, *86, 88, 90-92, 94, 95		(wces)	L-TL	59, 119, 216, 217
Coenagrionidae					
<i>Erythronema viridulum</i> (Charpentier, 1840)	58, 60, 63, 71, 73, *78, 80, 82, 83, 85, *86, 88, 92		(mca, ? wp)	L-TL	59, 215, 216, 218
<i>Pyrrhosoma nymphula</i> (Sulzer, 1776)	83, 89, 92		(wp)	L-TL	216
<i>Coenagrion ornatum</i> (Selys, 1850)	75, 76, 92, 95		(nm)	L-TL	59, 215, 216
<i>Coenagrion puella</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	60, 63, 70, 71, *78, 80, 82, 83, *86, 88, 91, 92, 95		(ena)	L-TL	59, 216, 217
<i>Coenagrion pulchellum</i> (Vander Linden, 1820)	60, 63, 70, 71, 75, 77, *78, 80, 82, 83, 90		(wes)	L-TL	59, 215, 216, 217, 218
<i>Coenagrion scitulum</i> (Rambur, 1842)	71, 80, 88, 91		(hom)	L-TL	59, 215, 216, 218
<i>Cercion lindenii</i> (Selys, 1840)	74, 78, 86, 92		(hom)	L-TL	216
<i>Enallagma cyathigerum</i> (Charpentier, 1840)	60, 61, 69, 74, 77, 78, 80		(h)	L-TL	216, 217, 218
<i>Ischnura elegans</i> (Vander Linden, 1820)	58, 60, 61, 63, 65, *68-86, 88, 89, 92, 95		(po)	L-TL	119, 215, 216, 217, 218, 258, 259

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Ischnura pumilio</i> (Charpentier, 1825)	58, 60, 63, 69-71, 77, 80, 92, 94		(wcp, wcpo)	215, 216, 217, 218, 258
Aeshnidae				
<i>Anax imperator</i> Leach, 1815	58, 60, 61, 63, *68, *69, 71, 73, 75, 77, 80, 83, 85, 86, 88, 92, 95		(wppt)	114, 215, 216, 217, 218, 258
<i>Anax parthenope</i> (Selys, 1839)	58, *68, *69, 73-80, 82-84, 86		(ptsp)	216, 217, 218, 258
<i>Hemianax ephippiger</i> (Burmeister, 1839)	58, 65, 77, 78, 80, 85		(ptm)	59, 216, 218, 258
<i>Brachytron pratense</i> (Müller, 1764)	86		(ean)	216
<i>Aeshna affinis</i> Vander Linden, 1820	69, 74, 78, 80, 81, 83, 84, 86, 88		(wcp)	216, 217, 218
<i>Aeshna isocetes</i> (Müller, 1767) [<i>Anaciaeschna isosceles</i>]	71, 76-78, 80, 83, 86, 89		(hom, ? wp)	119, 216, 258, 259
<i>Aeshna mixta</i> Latreille, 1805	72, 77, 80		(tpo)	215, 217, 218, 259
Corduliidae				
<i>Somatochlora meridionalis</i> Nielsen, 1935	69, 88, 89, 91		(nm)	59, 216
Libellulidae				
<i>Libellula depressa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	70, 80, 83, 84, 86, 88, 89, 91, 92, 94, 95		(esca)	216, 217
<i>Libellula fulva</i> Müller, 1764	77, 78, 80, 88, 89		(wesa)	216, 217, 218, 258
<i>Libellula quadrimaculata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	84, 88		(h)	216, 217
<i>Orthetrum albistylum</i> (Selys, 1848)	60, 61, 68, 69, 72, 75, 77, 78, 80, 86		(tp)	215, 216, 217, 218
<i>Orthetrum brunneum</i> (Fonscolombe, 1837)	63, 64, 68-72, 78, 79, 81, 83, 85, 88, 89, 91, 92		(omca)	216, 217
<i>Orthetrum cancellatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 60, 61, 63, 73-78, 80, 83, 84, 86, 88, 92, 94, 95		(wp)	59, 215, 216, 217, 218
<i>Orthetrum coerulescens</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	60, 61, 65, 68, 74, 76, 78, 83		(e)	119, 216, 217, 259

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Crocothemis erythraea</i> (Brullé, 1832)	58, 60, 61, 63, 69, 71, 72, 74, 76-86, 88, 89, 92, 94, 95		(ptmca)	L-TL	119, 217, 218, 259
<i>Sympetrum depressiusculum</i> (Selys, 1841)	81		(tp)	L-TL, ▲, ◆	216, 217
<i>Sympetrum fonscolombii</i> (Selys, 1840)	58, 60, 71, 77, 80, 83, 84, 86		(ptm, ptsp)	L-TL	216, 217, 218
<i>Sympetrum meridionale</i> (Selys, 1841)	58, 60, 61, 65, 68, 71, 72, 74-78, 80, 82, 83-86, 88, 92		(mca, omca)	L-TL	59, 119, 215, 216, 217, 218, 259
<i>Sympetrum pedemontanum</i> (Allioni, 1766)	58, 60, 77		(tp, ? dp)	L-TL	216, 217
<i>Sympetrum sanguineum</i> (Müller, 1764)	60, 63, 71, 77, 80-86, 92, 95		(wp)	L-TL	216, 217
<i>Sympetrum striolatum</i> (Charpentier, 1840)	*68, *69, 71, 74, 76-81, 83, 85, 86, 92, 93, 95		(tp)	L-TL, eh	119, 215, 216, 217, 218, 259
<i>Sympetrum vulgatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	60, 77, 80		(ewca)	L-TL, ▲, ◆	216, 217, 218
HETEROPTERA					
Corixidae					
<i>Corixa affinis</i> Leach, 1817	33, *69		(po)	L-TL, sp, ha	152, 252
<i>Sigara lateralis</i> (Leach, 1817) [s. <i>hieroglyphica</i>]	33, 41, 42, 59, 61		(ppt)	L-TL, sp ha-6.8‰	85, 158, 252, 389
<i>Sigara mayri</i> (Fieber, 1860)	33		(em)	L-TL, sp, ha-3.4‰	158, 252
<i>Sigara nigrolineata</i> (Fieber, 1848)	33		(hop)	L-TL, sp, ha-4.6‰	158, 252
<i>Sigara striata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	33		(tp, ? hop)	L-TL, sp, hs-3.4‰	158, 252
Notonectidae					
<i>Notonecta glauca</i> Linnaeus, 1758	58, 77		(hes, ? hop)	L-TL, sp, eu	206, 258
<i>Notonecta viridis</i> Delcourt, 1909	33, 44		(po)	L-TL, sp, ha-4.5‰	158, 252
Pleidae					
<i>Plea minutissima</i> Leach, 1817	80		(wcp)	L-TL, sp, eu	218
Naucoridae					
<i>Ilyocoris cimicoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	80		(tp)	L-TL, sp, eu	218
Nepidae					
<i>Nepa cinerea</i> Linnaeus, 1758	59		(hop)	L-TL, eu	206

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Ranatra linearis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	71		(hop)	L-TL, eu 374, 389
Belostomatidae				
<i>Lethocerus patruelis</i> (Stål, 1854) [<i>L. cordofanus</i> , <i>Belostoma niloticum</i>]	*78		(om, ? osp)	L-TL 79, 389
Hebridae				
<i>Hebrus pusillus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	80		(wp)	T, sp 218
Miridae				
<i>Deraeocoris serenus</i> (Douglas et Scott, 1868)	47, 76		(hom)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Teratocoris antennatus</i> (Boheman, 1852)	47		(e, ? hop)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Phytocoris insignis</i> Reuter, 1876	77		(e)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Lygus italicus</i> Wagner, 1950 [<i>L. maritimus</i>]	48, 77		(am)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Polymerus cognatus</i> (Fieber, 1858)	48		(h)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Orthotylus josifovi</i> Wagner, 1959	48, *69, 76		(Et)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Orthotylus parvulus</i> Reuter, 1879	47		(nem)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Orthotylus rubidus</i> Puton, 1874	47, 48, 76		(am)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Orthotylus schoberiae</i> Reuter, 1876	48, 76, *78		(nm)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Europiella albipennis</i> (Fallén, 1829) [<i>Plagiognathus lanuginosus</i>]	47		(et, ? mt)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Compsidolon pumilum</i> (Jakovlev, 1876) [<i>C. atomosum</i> , <i>Psallus</i>]	77		(hom)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
Nabidae				
<i>Nabis sareptanus</i> Dohrn, 1862 [<i>Halonabis</i>]	48		(omca, ? osp)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
Tingidae				
<i>Catoplatus carthusianus</i> (Goeze, 1778)	48		(csena)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Agramma atricapillum</i> (Spinola, 1837) [<i>Serenthia</i>]	48		(mca)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Agramma laetum</i> (Fallén, 1807) [<i>A. confusum</i> , <i>Serenthia</i>]	48		(wces)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
Saldidae				
<i>Salda adriatica</i> Horvath, 1887 [<i>S. littoralis</i> , <i>S. l. adriatica</i>]	47, 76		(nem)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Chartoscirta longicornis</i> (Jakovlev, 1882) [<i>Ch. elegantula longicornis</i>]	*69, 77		(pm)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Halosalda lateralis</i> (Fallén, 1807)	47		(wp)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Saldula arenicola</i> (Scholtz, 1847)	47, 76		(hat)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Saldula opacula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	32, 33		(ho)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Saldula pallipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	47		(hno)	T, sp, ha 158, 252
<i>Saldula pilosella</i> (Thomson, 1871)	47, 76		(tp)	T, sp, ha 158, 252

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Piesmatidae					
<i>Parapiesma salsolae</i> (Becker, 1867) [<i>Piesma</i>]	48		(wes)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
Lygaeidae					
<i>Cymus clavivulus</i> (Fallén, 1807)	48		(h)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Cymus grandicolor</i> Hahn, 1832	48		(tp)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Cymus melanocephalus</i> Fieber, 1861	48		(hom)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Henestaris halophilus</i> (Burmeister, 1835)	48		(hom)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Henestaris laticeps</i> (Curtis, 1836)	48		(atm)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Peritrechus meridionalis</i> Puton, 1877 [<i>P. ambiguus</i>]	47, *69, 77		(hom)	T, sp, ha	158
Pentatomidae					
<i>Anthemimia varicornis</i> (Jakovlev, 1876) [<i>Codophila</i>]	47		(tp)	T, sp, ha	158, 252
<i>Eurydema spectabilis</i> Horváth, 1882	48		(nem)	T, sps, ha	158, 159, 252
Cydnidae					
<i>Stibaropus henkei</i> (Jakovlev, 1874)	48		(emca)	T, sps	47, 57
COLEOPTERA					
Dytiscidae					
<i>Hydroglyphus geminus</i> (Fabricius, 1792) [<i>Bidessus</i> , <i>Guignotus pusillus</i>]	42		(po)	L-TL, sp, eu, sw	85, 389
<i>Hygrotus confluentis</i> (Fabricius, 1787) [<i>Coelambus</i>]	42		(wcp)	L-TL, sp, sw, th	85, 143, 389
<i>Hygrotus lernaeus</i> (Schaum, 1857) [<i>Coelambus</i>]	77		(hom)	L-TL, ha, sw	143, 184, 389
<i>Hygrotus pallidulus</i> (Aubé, 1850) [<i>Coelambus</i>]	48		(hom)	L-TL, sp, ha	143, 184, 389
<i>Hygrotus parallelogrammus</i> (Ahrens, 1812) [<i>Coelambus</i>]	48		(wcp)	L-TL, sp, ha	143, 184, 389
<i>Hydroporus jonicus</i> L. Miller, 1862	*69		(hom)	L-TL, sw	143, 184, 389
<i>Nebrioporus ceresyi</i> (Aubé, 1836) [<i>Deronectes</i> , <i>Potamonectes</i>]	76		(mca)	L-TL, 7%, ha, sw	85, 86, 184, 389
<i>Laccophilus minutus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>L. obscurus</i>]	42		(wpo)	L-TL, sp, sw	85, 184, 389
<i>Rhantus suturalis</i> (MacLeay, 1825) [<i>R. pulverosus</i>]	42		(poa, ? sk, R)	L-TL, sp, eu, sw	85, 184, 389
<i>Eretes sticticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	42		(k)	L-TL, sp, sw	85, 184, 389
<i>Dytiscus marginalis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	71, *78		(h)	L-TL, sw, eu	184, 374, 389
<i>Cybister lateralmarginalis</i> (DeGeer, 1774)	7, 59, 60		(wcp)	L-TL, sw, eu	184
Gyrinidae					
<i>Gyrinus distinctus</i> Aubé, 1836	7		(hop)	L-TL, eu	85, 184, 389
<i>Gyrinus suffriani</i> Scriba, 1855	7		(wp)	L-TL, eu, sw	85, 184, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Hydrophilidae					
<i>Helophorus aquaticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	42		(wp)	L-TL, sp, sw	85, 389
<i>Helophorus brevipalpis</i> Bedel, 1881	42		(wcp, ? h)	L-TL, sp, sw	85, 389
<i>Berosus bispina</i> Reiche et Saulcy, 1856	42		(mwca)	L-TL, sp, sw, ha	85, 389
<i>Berosus spinosus</i> (Steven, 1808)	*69		(tp)	L-TL, sw, eu	184, 389
<i>Cercyon arenarius</i> Rey, 1885	46		(se)	L-TL, sp	144
<i>Paracymus aeneus</i> (Germar, 1824)	33, 41, *69, 76		(tp)	L-TL, sw, ha	85, 86, 144, 184
<i>Laccobius gracilis</i> Motschulsky, 1855	42		(hom)	L-TL, sp, sw	85, 389
<i>Laccobius scutellaris</i> Motschulsky, 1855	42		(em)	L-TL, sp, sw	184, 389
<i>Enochrus bicolor</i> (Fabricius, 1792) [<i>Philydrus</i>]	*69, 76, 77, *78		(hop, ? h)	L-TL, sw, eu	85, 184
<i>Hydrophilus piceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	7, *78		(tpo)	L-TL, sw, eu	85, 374, 389
Hydraenidae					
<i>Ochthebius marinus</i> (Paykull, 1798)	33, 41, 42, 44, 76, 77, *78		(h)	L-TL, ha, sw, eu, sp	85, 144, 184, 389
<i>Ochthebius nanus</i> Stephens, 1829	41		(esena, hom)	L-TL, 23%, sp, sw	184, 389
<i>Ochthebius ponticus</i> Ienistea, 1956	41, 42, 43		(Er)	L-TL, l, sp	V. Guéorguiev
TRICHOPTERA					
Hydroptilidae					
<i>Stactobia caspersi</i> Ulmer, 1950	42		(em)	L-TL, sp, sw	84, 211, 389
DIPTERA					
Ceratopogonidae					
<i>Dasyhelea halophila</i> Kieffer, 1911	33		(se)	L-TL, 7-10%, sw, ha	386
Chironomidae					
<i>Tanytus punctipennis</i> Meigen, 1818 [<i>Pelopia</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, *79		(hno)	L-TL, 6%, sw	96, 249, 389
<i>Anatopynia plumipes</i> (Fries, 1823)	*69		(wces, ? wp)	L-TL, 1%, sw	96, 389
<i>Ablabesmyia monilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58		(hnoa, ? sk)	L-TL, sw	96, 389
<i>Thienemanimyia lentiginosa</i> (Fries, 1823) [<i>Ablabesmyia</i>]	*68		(wp, ? wcp)	L-TL, 1%, sw	96, 389
<i>Thalassomyia frauenfeldi</i> Schiner, 1856	2, 3, 7, 13, 14, 17, 32, 33		(ase)	M-TL, l-sp, lt	85, 249, 380, 389
<i>Clunio marinus</i> Haliday, 1855	7, 16		(ena)	M-TL, sl-l, ph, lt	84, 380
<i>Clunio ponticus</i> Michailova, 1980	5, 7, 11, 16, 20		(Er)	M-TL, sl-l, lt	249, 252, 267
<i>Cricotopus algarum</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	32, 33, 59, 60, *68		(eca, ? h)	L-TL, 1%, sw	96, 249, 337, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
? <i>Cricotopus intersectus</i> (Staeger, 1839) [? <i>Cryptochironomus conjugens</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68		(h)	L-TL, 6%, sw 96, 389
<i>Cricotopus ornatus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	32, 33, 59, 60		(ho)	L-TL, 0.8‰, sw 249, 337
<i>Cricotopus sylvestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	32, 33, 58-60, *68, *69, 80		(hno)	L-TL, 8‰, l, sw 96, 249, 337, 389
<i>Halocladius mediterraneus</i> Hirvenoja, 1973	76		(em)	M-TL, sw, ha 119, 398
<i>Halocladius varians</i> (Staeger, 1839) [<i>Cricotopus</i>]	32, 33		(ena, ? wp)	M-TL, sp, ha 249, 252, 266
? <i>Halocladius vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1818) [<i>Cricotopus</i> , <i>Trichocladius</i>], sp. dubia	2, 7, 32, 33		(e)	M-TL, l-sp, ph, lt 57, 85, 249, 266
? <i>Limnophyes minimus</i> (Meigen, 1818) [<i>Camptocladius exiguus</i> , <i>Tanytarsus</i>]	*68		(hptn, ? sk)	L-TL, 1.5‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Limnophyes pentaplastus</i> (Kieffer, 1921) [<i>L. prolongatus</i>]	*68		(h)	L-TL, 1‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Orthocladius fuscimanus</i> (Kieffer, 1908) [<i>O. bipunctellus</i>]	16		(ena, ? wp)	L-TL, l-sp 252, 268
<i>Orthocladius rubicundus</i> (Meigen, 1818) [<i>O. saxicola</i>]	58, 59, 60		(h)	L-TL, 1‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Propsolecerus lacustris</i> Kieffer, 1923	*68		(csee)	L-TL, 1‰, sw 353, 389
<i>Psectrocladius obivius</i> (Walker, 1856) [<i>P. dilatatus</i>]	*68		(h)	L-TL, 1‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Psectrocladius psilopterus</i> (Kieffer, 1906)	58, 59, 60, *68		(h)	L-TL, 1‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Rheocricotopus atripes</i> (Kieffer, 1913) [<i>R. foveatus</i>]	7, 11, 16, 32, 33		(wcp)	L-TL, sp 249
<i>Smittia duplicata</i> Strenzke, 1951	16, 24		(Er)	M-TL, sl, ph 249
<i>Baeotendipes noctivagus</i> (Kieffer, 1911) [<i>Haliella caspersi</i>]	76		(hom)	M-TL, 100‰, sw 86, 119, 249, 389
<i>Chironomus anchialticus</i> Michailova, 1974	76		(Ep)	M-TL, 80‰, sw 119, 252, 259, 265
<i>Chironomus aprilinus</i> Meigen, 1818 [<i>Ch. halophilus</i>]	33, 42, *69, 76, 80		(wcp)	M-B-TL, 12‰, l-sp 84, 119, 249, 389
<i>Chironomus plumosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	16, 20, 33, 58, *68, 76		(hno)	L-TL, 0-9‰, sw, sp 84, 97, 119, 249, 353, 374, 389, 396
<i>Chironomus riparius</i> Meigen, 1804 [<i>Ch. thummi</i>]	42, 58-60, *68, *69, *74, 76, 77, 80, 88		(hn)	L-TL, 0-16‰, sw, sp 85, 96, 337, 353, 374, 389, 396
<i>Chironomus salinarius</i> Kieffer, 1915	33, 58-60, *69, *66, 76, 77, *78, *79, 80, *86		(wcp)	M-TL, 15-60‰, sw, sp 84, 96, 119, 353, 259, 264, 374, 396
<i>Chironomus valkanovi</i> Michailova, 1974	76, 77		(Ep)	M-TL, 60‰, sw 252, 264, 265, 398
<i>Cryptochironomus defectus</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	58, 59, 60, *68, 76		(pa)	L-TL, 2‰, sw 96, 337, 389
<i>Dicrotendipes nervosus</i> (Staeger, 1839) [<i>Limnochironomus</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, *79		(h)	L-TL, 2‰, sw 96, 337, 389
? <i>Endochironomus signaticornis</i> Kieffer, 1913, nom. dubia	58, 60, 68		(e)	L-TL, 2‰, sw 96, 389
<i>Endochironomus tendens</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	59, 60		(tp, ? hop)	L-TL, 0.8‰, sw 337
<i>Glyptotendipes barbipes</i> (Staeger, 1839)	42, 46		(ho)	L-TL, sw, sp 131, 252
<i>Glyptotendipes caulicola</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	59, 60		(cse)	L-TL, 0.8‰, sw 337

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Glyptotendipes glaucus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	59, 60		(tp)	L-TL, 0.8‰, sw	337
<i>Glyptotendipes cauliginellus</i> (Kieffer, 1913) [<i>G. gripekoveni</i>]	58-60, *68, 76, *79, 80		(po)	L-TL, 2‰, sw	96, 119, 337, 396
<i>Glyptotendipes pallens</i> (Meigen, 1804) [<i>G. polytomus</i>]	58, 59, 60		(po)	L-TL, 2‰, sw	96
? <i>Parachironomus parastrostratus</i> Harnisch, 1923 [<i>Cryptochironomus</i>], sp. dubia	58, 60			L-TL, 2‰, sw	96, 389
<i>Polypedilum nubeculosum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	2, 7, 58, 59, 60, *68		(h)	L-TL, 1.5‰, l, sw	84, 96, 249, 337
<i>Polypedilum nubifer</i> (Skuse, 1889) [<i>P. aberrans</i> , <i>P. pharao</i>]	7, 24, 58-60, *68, 77		(poa)	L-TL, 1.5‰, l, ph	97, 249, 389
<i>Polypedilum scalaenum</i> (Schränk, 1803) [<i>P. brevi antennatum</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68		(ho)	L-TL, 2‰, sw	97, 389
<i>Cladotanytarsus mancus</i> (Walker, 1856) [<i>Tanytarsus</i>]	*68		(h)	L-TL, 1.5‰, sw	97, 389
<i>Stempellina bausei</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	*68		(wces)	L-TL, 1‰, sw	97, 389
<i>Tanytarsus gregarius</i> Kieffer, 1909	*69		(h)	L-TL, sw	84, 389
<i>Tanytarsus mendax</i> Kieffer, 1925 [<i>T. holochloris</i>]	32		(h)	L-TL, sp	249
Chaoboridae					
<i>Chaoborus crystallinus</i> (De Geer, 1776)	59, 60		(h)	L-TL, 0.8‰, ps, s, ro	337
Stratiomyidae					
<i>Stratiomys longicornis</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	59		(tp)	L-TL, 0.78‰, sw	206
Hybotidae					
<i>Chersodromia colliniana</i> Frey, 1936	47		(m)	T, sps, ha	46, 252
<i>Chersodromia curtipennis</i> Collin, 1950	47		(pm, Ep)	T, sps, ha	46, 252
Dolichopodidae					
<i>Aphrosylus fuscipennis</i> Strobl, 1909	45		(se)	M-TL, sl-l-sp, lt	50, 51, 249, 252
<i>Aphrosylus piscator</i> Lichtwardt, 1902	45		(Eb)	M-TL, sl-l-sp, lt, r	50, 249, 252
<i>Aphrosylus venator</i> Loew, 1857	45, 46		(hom)	M-TL, sl-l-sp, lt	46, 47, 50, 249, 252
Coelopidae					
<i>Malacomyia sciomyzina</i> (Haliday, 1833)	46		(e)	T, sp, ha	50, 54, 249, 252
<i>Coelopa frigida</i> (Fabricius, 1805) [<i>C. eximia</i> , <i>Fucomyia</i>]	46, 47		(h)	T, sp, ha	46, 50, 249, 252
Helcomyzidae					
<i>Helcomyza mediterranea</i> (Loew, 1854)	46		(sec)	T, sp, ha, ps	48, 53, 249
Tethimidae					
<i>Tethina albosetulosa</i> (Strobl, 1900) [<i>T. griseola</i>]	46, 47		(wpat)	T, l-sp, ha	46, 52, 62, 249
<i>Tethina czernyi</i> (Hendel, 1934)	46, 47		(mca)	T, l-sp, ha, r	58, 60, 62
<i>Tethina flavigenis</i> (Hendel, 1934)	47, 61, 62, 76		(am)	T, l-sp, ha, r	46, 58, 62

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Tethina grisea</i> (Fallén, 1823) [<i>T. cinerea</i>]	46, 47		(am)	46, 52, 62, 249, 252
<i>Tethina pallipes</i> (Loew, 1865)	46, 48, 59, 60, 73, 74, 85		(hpta, ? sk)	58, 62
<i>Tethina strobliana</i> (Mercier, 1923)	58		(wp)	58, 60, 62
Canacidae				
<i>Canace saloniata</i> Strobl, 1900	45, 50		(nem)	48, 52, 62, 249
Sphaeroceridae				
<i>Thoracochaeta brachystoma</i> (Stenhammar, 1855) [<i>Leptocera</i>]	46, 47		(k)	46, 50, 51, 249, 252
Ephydriidae				
<i>Hecamede albicans</i> (Meigen, 1830)	45, 46, 47		(hat)	46, 50, 51, 62, 249
<i>Ephydra attica</i> Becker, 1896	41, 44, 47, 76, 77		(dp, ? mca)	46, 62, 85, 249, 283
<i>Ephydra bivittata</i> Loew, 1860	33, 41, 44, 59, 60, 64, 76, 77		(hom)	49, 62, 249
<i>Ephydra flavipes</i> (Macquart, 1843)	33, 76, 77,		(ptm, ? atm)	62
<i>Ephydra murina</i> Wirth, 1975 [<i>E. macellaria</i>]	32, 47, 62, 64, 76, 77, 80, 92		(cseait)	62, 85, 389
<i>Ephydra riparia</i> Fallén, 1813	47, 58, 61, 77, 91		(h)	46, 62, 252
<i>Schema acrosticale</i> (Becker, 1903)	47, 48, 61, 76, 77		(wp)	62
<i>Chlorichaeta albipennis</i> (Loew, 1848)	47, 76, 91, 92, 95		(pata)	62, 63, 85
<i>Glenanthe nigripes</i> Czerny, 1909	47, 48, 61, 76, 77		(nm)	45, 50, 53, 54, 55, 56, 61, 62, 63
<i>Polytrichophora duplosetosa</i> (Becker, 1896)	47, 48, 58-60, 76, 91, 92-95		(wpat)	62, 63
Anthomyiidae				
<i>Fucellia maritima</i> (Haliday, 1838)	46		(ena)	46, 50, 51, 53,
<i>Fucellia tergina</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	46		(hnata, ? sk)	249
MOLLUSCA				
POLYPLACOPHORA (LORICATA)				
CHITONIDA (CHITONIFORMES)				
Lepidochitonidae (Tonicellidae, Ischnochitonidae)				
<i>Lepidochitona caprearum</i> (Scacchi, 1836) [<i>L. corrugata</i> , <i>Chiton poli</i> , <i>Middendorffia</i>]	13, 24	17	hom, ? lm	91, 249, 389
<i>Lepidochitona cinerea</i> (Linnaeus, 1767) [<i>Chiton marginatus</i> , <i>Ch. variegatus</i>]	7, 12, 16, 21, 24	0-30	clm	84, 91, 249, 295

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
Gastropoda						
Patellogastropoda (Archaeogastropoda, Docoglossa)						
Patellidae						
<i>Patella ulysipponensis</i> Gmelin, 1791 [<i>P. caerulea pontica</i> , <i>P. pontica</i> , <i>P. tarentina</i>]	3, 11, 14, 16, 17, 50	0-10		clm	M, bt, sep, lt-ro, l-sl, r, ■	31, 84, 91, 114, 249, 389
VETIGASTROPODA (ARCHAEOGASTROPODA)						
Phasianellidae (Tricoliidae)						
<i>Tricolia pullus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Phasianella pontica</i>]	1-22, 24	0-10, 50		eam	M, bt, ep, ph	84, 91, 249, 389
? <i>Tricolia tenuis</i> (Michaud, 1829) [<i>Phasianella</i>]	11			lmm	M, bt, ep, r	91, 389
Trochidae						
<i>Gibbula adriatica</i> (Philippi, 1844) [<i>G. euximica</i> , <i>G. deversa</i> , <i>Trochus</i>]	4, 24	-30, 50		lm	M, bt, ep, ro, mc, ph	67, 389
<i>Gibbula albida</i> (Gmelin, 1791) [<i>G. a. var. pontica</i> , ? <i>Trochus fermonii</i>]	24	0-15, 40		lm	M, bt, ep, ro, mc, ph	249
<i>Gibbula divaricata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Trochus</i>]	1-22, 24	0-10, 50		lm	M, bt, sep, ro, lt, ph	84, 91, 249, 389
Cycloneritimorpha (Archaeogastropoda)						
Neritidae						
<i>Theodoxus danubialis</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828) [<i>Neritina</i>]	*69			(seepc)	L, bt, 12‰, lt, pe	84, 389
<i>Theodoxus euxinus</i> (Clessin, 1887) [<i>Neritina</i>]	96	-10		Ep, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, bt, 5‰,	6, 126
<i>Theodoxus fluviatilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Neritina</i>]	58-60, *68, *69, 71, *78, *79, 84, *86, 88, 92, 94, 95, 96			(e)	L-B, bt, eh, 20‰, lt	84, 305, 374, 389
<i>Theodoxus pallasi</i> Lindholm, 1924 [<i>Neritina</i>]	*69	4-10		pc, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, eh-14‰, ro, EX, ▲	113, 164
<i>Theodoxus piliidei</i> (Tournouer, 1879) [<i>Neritina</i>]	28	65-		pc, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, bt, phs	249
Ectobranchia (Heterostrophia, Mesogastropoda)						
Valvatidae						
<i>Valvata cristata</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	*68, *69			(wes)	L, 0.5‰, bt, ph, s, r, ◆	118, 305, 374, 389
<i>Valvata piscinalis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) [<i>V. pulchella</i>]	*68, *69	3-10, 80		(wcp, i - h)	L, 0.4‰, bt, sw, ph, pe, x, ◆	84, 118, 305, 389
SORBEOCONCHA (NEOTAENIOGLOSSA, MESOGASTROPODA)						
Cerithiidae						
<i>Bittium reticulatum</i> (da Costa, 1778) [<i>Cerithiolum</i> , <i>Cerithium exile</i>]	7-22, 26, 27, 28, 69	2-14-111		clmm	M, bt, eb, ps, ps-s, pe	66, 84, 249, 389
<i>Bittium submamillatum</i> (de Reyneval et Ponzi, 1854) [<i>Cerithidium</i> , <i>C. pusillum</i>]	3, 26, 27, 28	20-140		lm	M, bt, eb, ps-s, pe	67, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Cerithium vulgatum</i> Bruguière, 1792 [<i>C. v. ponticum</i> , <i>C. ponticum</i>] HYPSOGASTROPODA (NEOTAENIOGLOSSA, MESO-, NEOGASTROPODA)	11, 13, 16	-15, 25	lm	M, bt, ep 91, 249, 389
Caecidae				
<i>Caecum armoricum</i> de Folin, 1869 [<i>C. tenue</i> , <i>Brochina</i>]	7	15-30	lmm	M, bt, ep 166, 249, 252
<i>Caecum trachea</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>C. elegans</i> , <i>C. rugulosum</i>]	7	5-15, 50	lm	M, bt, ep 166, 167, 249, 352
Calyptraeidae				
<i>Calyptraea chinensis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	7, 11, 13, 15, 16	40, 70	eam	M, bt, mb 84, 91, 249, 389
Cerithiopsidae				
<i>Cerithiopsis minima</i> (Brusina, 1865)	84	-30	lmm	M, bt, ep, zc 404, 405
<i>Cerithiopsis tubercularis</i> (Montagu, 1803)	6, 7, 8, 26, 27, 28	14-111	eamswi	M, bt, eb, pe 67, 249, 389
Cimidae (Acididae)				
<i>Graphis albida</i> (Kannacher, 1798)	84	0-50	clmm	M, bt, ep 404
Epitoniidae				
<i>Epitonium turtonis</i> (Turton, 1819) [<i>Scalaria communis</i> , <i>S. tenuicostata</i>]	7	13-36, 60	clm	M, bt, mb 84, 249, 389
? <i>Epitonium clathrus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Scalaria communis</i>]	7		clm, ce	M, bt, mb 84, 389
Eulimidae				
<i>Vitrolina incurva</i> (Bucquoy, Dautzenberg et Dollfus, 1883) [<i>Eulima</i>]	3, 26, 27, 28	15-100	clm	M, bt, eb, pe 67, 249, 389
Hydrobiidae				
<i>Hydrobia acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805) [<i>H. ventrosa</i>]	7, 23, 24, 43, *66, *68, *69, *78, *79, *86	0-22	lm, ? hm	B-M, eh-60%, bt, ep, sw, ph, ro, pe, ♦ 84, 118, 249, 305, 374, 389
? <i>Hydrobia ulvae</i> (Pennant, 1777)	76		clmm	M-B, bt, eh 119, 396
<i>Ventrosia ventrosa</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Hydrobia</i> , <i>H. acuta</i>]	13, 26-28, *66, *69, 76, 77-79, *86, 96	0-111, 20	clm	B, bt, eh, mb, ro, ph, zc, pe 166, 249, 374, 389
<i>Hauffenia lucidula</i> Angelov, 1967 [<i>Horatia</i>]	53		(EI)	L, 1%, bt, cr, ▲, ♦ 6, 118
<i>Lithoglyphus naticoides</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828)	*69	12	(seep, Rc)	L, 3%, bt, lt, po, ♦ 84, 118, 249, 389
<i>Lithoglyphus fuscus</i> (C. Pfeiffer, 1828) [? <i>L. pyramidatus</i> v. Mollendorf, 1873]	*69		(Eb)	L, bt, lt, rh, r 84, 389
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarum</i> (J. E. Gray, 1843) [<i>P. jenkinsi</i>]	? 96		(nz, sk, i)	B-L, 17%, po-sw, eu, is 118, 204
Bithyniidae				
? <i>Bithynia leachii</i> (Sheppard, 1823) [? <i>B. transsilvanica</i> (Bielz, 1853)]	*68	3	(wp, ? e, wes)	L, bt, 0.5%, ph 374, 389
<i>Bithynia tentaculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	60, *68, *69	5	(wp, ? h - i)	L, bt, ph, ro, s, ps, ♦ 84, 118, 305, 389
Pyrgulidae (Micromelaniidae)				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Turricaspia lintca</i> (Milaschewitch, 1908) [<i>Micromelania</i> , <i>Pyrgula</i>]	26, 28, *68, *79	24-148	pc, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, 8%, bt, s, sw, ♦	113, 166, 249
Littorinidae					
<i>Melrhaphe neritoides</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Littorina</i>]	2-22, 45		clmm	M, bt, lr-spr, lt	34, 84, 249, 389
Rissoidae					
<i>Alvania lactea</i> (Michaud, 1832) [<i>Massotia</i> , <i>Rissoa</i>]	3, 7, 24		clm	M, bt, ep, ph	84, 282, 389
<i>Rissoa membranacea</i> (J. Adams, 1800) [<i>R. oblonga</i> , <i>R. pontica</i> , <i>R. venusta</i>]	1-13, 23, 24	-10	clm	M, bt, ep, ph, zc	84, 91, 249, 282
<i>Rissoa parva</i> (da Costa, 1778) [<i>R. euxinica</i>]	3, 13, 24	-20, 80	clm	M, bt, ep-mb, ph	249, 282, 389
<i>Rissoa splendida</i> Eichwald, 1830	7-22, 23, 24	-12	m, hom	M, bt, sep, zc, ph, ro	84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Pusillina lineolata</i> (Michaud, 1832) [<i>Rissoa</i> , ? <i>R. membranacea</i>]	7, 16, 17, 24, *69	-47	lm	M, bt, mb, ph, pe	374, 389
<i>Setia pulcherrima</i> (Jeffreys, 1848) [<i>S. turriculata</i>]	17, 19, 24, 45		lm	M, bt, sep, lr	404, 405
<i>Pontiturbocella rufostriata</i> (Hesse, 1916) [<i>Assimineae</i> , <i>Paludimella</i>]	*69		• p, Er	M, bt	148
Tornidae					
<i>Tornus subcarinatus</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Adeorbis</i>]	14		clm	M, bt, ep	166, 249, 392
Triphoridae					
<i>Marshallora adversa</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Trifora obesula</i> , <i>T. perversa</i> var. <i>parva</i>]	16, 17, 19	-15, 80	clm, ? eam	M, bt, mb, phc	405
Muricidae					
<i>Rapana venosa</i> (Valenciennes, 1846) [<i>R. bezoar</i> , <i>R. thomasiana</i>]	1-22, 24, 25, 69, 76	-70	j, aminp, i	M, bt, mb-eb, eu, is	165, 249, 392
<i>Trophonopsis muricatus</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>T. breviatus</i> , <i>Trophon</i>]	3, 21, 22, 27, 28	36-138	clm	M, bt, shb, phs	67, 249, 389, 410
Buccinidae					
<i>Neptunea arthritica</i> (Valenciennes, 1858)	25, 26, 49		j, pnep, i	M, bt, r	355
Nassariidae					
<i>Cyclope neritica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Cyclonassa kamischiensis</i> , <i>Nassa brusinae</i>]	1-22, *69	-54	lm	M, bt, mb, ps-pe	67, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Nassarius reticulatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>N. nitidus</i> , <i>Nassa</i>]	1-22, 25, 36-40, *69, 76	-60	clmm	M, bt, mb, ps, ps-pe	84, 91, 249, 374
Conidae					
<i>Bela nebula</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Cythara fuscata</i> , <i>Mangelia</i> , <i>Raphitona</i>]	7, *69	-20	clm	M, bt, ep	91, 249, 389
<i>Mangelia costata</i> (Pennant, 1777) [<i>M. pontica</i> , <i>M. taeniata</i> , <i>Cythara</i>]	7, *69	-50	clm	M, bt, mb	84, 249, 389
HETEROSTROPHA					
Omalogyridae					
<i>Omalogyra atomus</i> (Philippi, 1841) [<i>Homalogyra</i> , <i>Truncatella</i>]	17, 84		aam	M, bt, ep	405
<i>Ammonicera fischeriana</i> (Monterosato, 1869) [<i>Homalogyra</i>]	17, 84		lm, ? Imm	M, bt, mb	405
Pyramidellidae (Ebalidae, Turbonillidae, Murchisonellidae)					

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Chrysallida emaciata</i> (Brusina, 1866) [<i>Parthenina</i> , <i>Turbonilla</i>]	17, 19, 84		lm	M, bt, ep	405	
<i>Chrysallida incerta</i> (Milaschewitsh, 1916) [<i>Ch. brusinai</i> , <i>Odostomia</i> , <i>Parthenina</i>]	17, 19, 69, 84	-18	m, ? lmmg	M, bt, ep	405	
<i>Chrysallida interstincta</i> (J. Adams, 1797) [<i>Ch. obtusa</i> , <i>Parthenina tenuistriata</i>]	12, 17, 19, 69, 84	6-80	clmm	M, bt, mb	164, 405	
<i>Chrysallida terebellum</i> (Philippi, 1844) [<i>Parthenina costulata</i> , <i>Odostomia</i>]	7, 69	-10, 42	lm	M, bt, ep, pe	166, 167, 249, 392	
<i>Eulimella acicula</i> (Philippi, 1836) [<i>E. laevis</i> , <i>Belonidium</i> , <i>Odostomia</i>]	17, 84	-18, -47	clm	M, bt, ep, r	405	
<i>Ebala pointeli</i> (de Folin, 1868) [<i>Anisocycla</i> , <i>Eulimella</i> , <i>Turbonilla</i>]	7, 69	-20	lm, ? lmm	M, bt, ep, ps, s	166, 167	
<i>Odostomia erjaveciana</i> Brusina, 1869 [<i>O. nitens</i>]	11, 17, 19, 84		lm	M, bt, ep	405	
<i>Odostomia eulimoides</i> Hanley, 1844 [<i>O. novegradensis</i> , <i>O. pallida</i>]	7, 16, 17, 19, 84	-70	clm	M, bt, mb	405	
<i>Odostomia plicata</i> (Montagu, 1803)	16, 17, 19, 84	-20	clm	M, bt, ep	405	
<i>Odostomia scalaris</i> MacGillivray, 1843 [<i>O. albella</i> , <i>O. rissoiformis</i>]	1-22	-15, 50	clm	M, bt, mb	166, 178, 249	
<i>Noemiamea doliiformis</i> (Jeffreys, 1848) [<i>Odostomia</i>]	17, 84		lm	M, bt, ep, r	405	
<i>Turbonilla delicata</i> Monterosato, 1874 [<i>Odostomia</i>]	7	-35	clm	M, bt, ep-mb	166, 249, 392	
<i>Turbonilla pusilla</i> (Philippi, 1844) [<i>T. elegantissima</i> , <i>T. pupaeformis</i>]	16, 17, 84		kelm	M, bt, ep, r	405	
CEPHALASPIDEA						
Retusidae						
<i>Cylichnina umbilicata</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>C. strigella</i> , <i>C. variabilis</i> , <i>Retusa</i>]	7, 11, 13, 16, 69	-50	clm	M, bt, mb, s, sg	91, 249, 389	
? <i>Cylichnina roboghiana</i> (Fischer, 1869) [<i>C. ovoides</i> , <i>Bulla</i> , <i>Retusa</i>]	7	-40	lm	M, bt, mb	84, 249, 389	
<i>Retusa truncatula</i> (Bruguière, 1792) [<i>R. t. opima</i> , <i>Bulla</i> , <i>Cylichna</i>]	7, 13, 17, 24, 26, 27, 28, *69	0-140	eam	M, bt, eb, pe, ph, mc	84, 249, 389	
SACOGLOSSA						
Stiligeridae (Hermacidae)						
<i>Calliopaea bellula</i> (Orbigny, 1837) [<i>Stiliger</i>]	7, 24, 34, *69		clm	M, bt, ep, slc	249, 374, 389, 392	
Limapontiidae (Stiligeridae)						
<i>Limapontia capitata</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	7, 24		clm, ce	M, bt, ep, slc	249, 392	
ACOCHLIDIIDA						
Microhedyliidae (Parhedyliidae)						
<i>Parahedyli tyrtowii</i> (Kowalewsky, 1901) [<i>Microhedyli</i> , <i>Hedyli</i>]	7, 11, 16, 25		m	M, bt, ep, ps	249, 392	
Nudibranchia						
Pseudovermidae						
<i>Pseudovermis paradoxus</i> Perejaslawtzeva, 1890	7, 11, 25		lm	M, bt, ep, ps	249, 392	
Tergipedidae						

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Embletonia pulchra</i> (Alder et Hancock, 1844) [<i>Aeolis, Eolis, Pterochtilus</i>]	23, 24, *69, *79	-40	clm	M, bt, mb, slc, zc	249, 374, 386, 389
Corambidae					
<i>Corambe obscura</i> (Verrill, 1870) [<i>Doridella</i>]	7, 13	-5	vck, i	M, bt, ep	328
Dorididae					
<i>Doris ocelligera</i> (Bergh, 1881)	7		lm	M, bt	358
EUPULMONATA					
Ellobiidae					
<i>Myosotella myosotis</i> (Draparnaud, 1801) [<i>Alexia, Aurricula, Ovtella</i>]	4, 45		amp	M-TL, spr, r	166, 249
BASOMMATOPHORA					
Acroloxiidae					
<i>Acroloxius lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 59, 60, 80		(wes, ? hoec)	L, bt, ph, sw, ♦	206, 218, 259
Lymnaeidae					
<i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	*68	0-4	(h)	L, 7%, bt, ph, pe, ♦	118, 305, 389
<i>Stagnicola corvus</i> (Gmelin, 1791) [<i>S. palustris</i> var. <i>corvus</i> , <i>Lymnaea, Galba</i>]	58, *68, *69	0-50	(hop, ? e)	L, bt, sw, ph, ♦	118, 206, 305, 389
<i>Radix auricularia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Lymnaea</i>]	58, *68, *69, 71	0.2-25	(h, ? hop)	L, 6%, bt, ph, rh, s, ♦	84, 118, 374, 389
<i>Radix balthica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>R. ovata, Lymnaea</i>]	59, 60, 80, 96		(hop)	L, 3-10%, bt, ph, eu, ♦	206, 218
<i>Galba truncatula</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774) [<i>Lymnaea</i>]	*68, *69	-6	(h)	L, bt, eu, pe, ph, ar	305, 389
Planorbidae					
<i>Ferrissia fragilis</i> (Tryon, 1862) [<i>F. wautieri, F. clessiniana</i>]	68, 83	0-8	(h, sk, i)	L, bt, eu, th, ph, r, is, ♦	6, 118
<i>Planorbis carinatus</i> O. F. Müller, 1774	77	-10, -18	(wes, ? h)	L, bt, sw, ph, pe, r, ♦	257, 258
<i>Planorbis planorbis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Tropidiscus umbilicatus</i>]	7, 58, 59, *68, *69, 70, 71, 77		(h)	L, bt, 2%, sw, ph, pe, ♦	6, 84, 258, 389
<i>Anisus septemgyratus</i> (Rossmässler, 1835) [<i>Paraspira</i>]	*68, *69, 71		(wes, ? e)	L, 8%, sw, ph, α-β, r, ♦	6, 305, 389
<i>Anisus vortex</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Planorbis, Spirulina</i>]	*68		(wces)	L, bt, 8%, ph, α-β, r, ♦	6, 374, 389
<i>Anisus vorticulus</i> (Troschel, 1834)	60, 83		(wces, ? wces)	L, bt, pe, ph, rh, sw, r, ♦, HD	6, 118
<i>Gyraulus crista</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Armiger, Planorbis</i>]	*68		(h)	L, 1.5%, eu, ph, α-β, ♦	6, 118, 374, 389
<i>Hippeutis complanatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Segmentina</i>]	59, 60		(wces, ? wcp)	L, bt, ph, s-at, sw, α, r, ♦	6, 118
<i>Segmentina nitida</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	*68, *69, 83		(wcp)	L, bt, sw, ph, α-β, ♦	6, 118, 305, 389
<i>Planorbarius corneus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Coretus corneus</i> var. <i>ammonoceras</i>]	*68, *69, 71, 77	-9	(wces)	L, 5%, sw, po, α-β, ♦	6, 305, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
Physidae					
<i>Physella acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	58, 75, 76, 77, 87, 90		(na, sk, i)	L, bt, eu, pe, ph, po, sw, tx, α-β, is, ♦	6, 118, 257, 259
<i>Physa fontinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	*68, *69		(tp, ? h)	L, bt, sw, po, cr, ph, ps-pe, β, r, ♦	6, 84, 389
BIVALVIA					
ARCOIDA					
Noetiidae					
<i>Striarca lactea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Arca, Arcopsis, Galactella</i>]	7, 16, 24	-20	eami, +	M, bt, ep, lt, r	84, 389
Arcidae					
<i>Anadara kagoshimensis</i> (Tokunaga, 1906) [<i>A. inaequivalvis, Cunearca, Scapharca</i>]	3, 6, 7, 12, 13, 25, 26, 69	-25, -40	miwp, i	M, bt, ep, ps, s, sg, is	183, 249, 255, 288
MYTILOIDA					
Mytilidae					
<i>Mytilaster lineatus</i> (Gmelin, 1791) [<i>M. l. pontica, M. minimus, M. monterosatoi</i>]	1-22, 24, 68, 69	0-30, 50	lm	M, bt, 5%, sep, lt-slc	61, 84, 91, 249, 295
<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i> Lamarck, 1819 [<i>M. edulis</i> var. <i>galloprovincialis</i>]	1-22, 24, 27, 68, 69, 76	0-80	eamp	M, bt, eb, lt, s, s-ps	84, 91, 389
<i>Gibbomodiola adriatica</i> (Lamarck, 1819) [<i>Modiola, Modiolus</i>]	7, 11, 13, 16, 25, 26	20-36, 75	lm, ? clm	M, bt, mb, pe, s-ps	91, 249, 389
<i>Modiolula phaseolina</i> (Philippi, 1844) [<i>Modiola, Modiolus</i>]	1-22, 28	30-140	clmm	M, bt, shb, pe, phs	249, 389, 410
OSTREOIDA					
Pectinidae					
<i>Flexopecten glaber</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Chlamys, Pecten glaber</i> var. <i>pontica</i>]	1-22, 25	3-40, 70	lm	M, bt, sep, ps, ps-s	84, 91, 249, 389
? <i>Pecten jacobaeus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	? 7		lmmg	M, bt	84, 389
? <i>Pecten maximus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	? 11		eam, ? clm	M, bt	84, 389
Anomiidae					
<i>Anomia ephippium</i> Linnaeus, 1758	7	-30	ami	M, bt, ep, ro	84, 389
Ostreidae					
<i>Ostrea edulis</i> Linnaeus, 1758 [<i>O. lamellosa, O. sublamellosa, O. taurica</i>]	3, 5, 7, 12, 16, 17, 24	7-23, 65	anamnep, i	M, bt, sep, ro, ■	67, 84, 91, 114, 249
UNIONOIDA					
Unionidae					
<i>Unio pictorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>U. p. gaudioni, U. gemtilis</i>]	*68, *69, 92	-11	(e, ? ena)	L, bt, 2%, pe-ar-ps, β	6, 84, 305, 374, 389
<i>Unio tumidus</i> Retzius, 1788	*69	-9	(e, ? wes)	L, bt, pe-ar, β	6, 84, 389
<i>Anodonta cygnea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>A. c. piscinalis, A. piscinalis</i>]	*68, 92	-17	(e)	L, bt, 2%, pe-ps, β	6, 84, 374, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
<i>Pseudanodonta complanata</i> (Rossmassler, 1835) [<i>Anodonta</i>]	92	-9	(e)	L, bt, ps-pe, β	6
VENEROIDA					
Lucinidae					
<i>Lucinella divaricata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Divaricella</i> , <i>Lucina commutata</i> , <i>Tellina</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 69	-30	clm, ? lm	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	84, 249, 389
<i>Loripes lacteus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758; Poli, 1791) [<i>L. lucinalis</i> , <i>Lucina leucoma</i> , <i>Tellina</i>]	3, 7, 11, 16, 17, 20, 25	-25	lmm, ? clmm	M, bt, sep, ps, zc	67, 84, 249, 389
Leptonidae					
<i>Hemilepton nitidum</i> (Turton, 1822) [<i>Kellia compressa</i> , <i>Erycina</i> , <i>Lepton</i>]	25, *69, 84	0-25, 34	clm	M, bt, ps, ep-mb	164, 403
? <i>Kellia suborbicularis</i> (Montagu, 1803) [? <i>Hemilepton nitidum</i>]	69	2	namnep	M, bt, eb, ps	356
Montacutiidae					
<i>Kurtiella bidentata</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Mysella</i>]	16, 17	-50	eam	M, bt, sg, ro	403
Cardiidae					
<i>Acanthocardia paucicostata</i> (G. B. Sowerby, 1834) [<i>Cardium p. var. impedita</i>]	3, 7, 13, 16, 17, 25-27, 69	15-100	lm	M, bt, mb-eb, pe, sg	67, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Cerastoderma glaucum</i> (Poiret, 1789) [<i>Cardium edule</i> , <i>C. clodiense</i> , <i>C. lamarcki</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 27, 68, *69, 76, 77, *78	-80	clm	M, bt, eh-3.9%, eb, ps, ps-s, pe	84, 91, 249, 295, 374, 389
<i>Parvicardium exiguum</i> (Gmelin, 1791) [<i>Cardium</i>]	3, 7, 13, 16, 25, 27, 69	10-120	clm	M, bt, eb, ps, ps-s, pe	67, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Papillicardium papillosum</i> (Poli, 1791) [<i>Cardium fasciatum</i> , <i>C. simile</i>]	3, 7, 17, 25, 27, 28	-30, 100	lm	M, bt, eb, pe, pe-ps	67, 84, 249, 389
<i>Monodacna colorata</i> (Eichwald, 1829) [<i>Didacna</i> , <i>Hypanis</i>]	3, 7, 25, 26, 27, 28	13, -148	pc, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, bt, ps-pe, s, ep	66, 68, 249, 389
<i>Hypanis plicatum</i> (Eichwald, 1829) [<i>Adacna relicta</i> , <i>H. p. relicta</i>]	3, 27, 28	35-90	pc, Rc, Sf, +	M-B, bt, pe, at, s-ps	68, 172, 249, 389
Macrtridae					
<i>Spisula subtruncata</i> (da Costa, 1778) [<i>Macra s. triangula</i> , <i>M. triangula</i>]	1-22, 25-28, 69	5-140	clmm	M, bt, eb, pe, ps-s, sg	67, 84, 249, 389
Mesodesmatidae					
<i>Donacilla cornea</i> (Poli, 1795) [<i>Mesodesma</i>]	1-22, 51	0.2, -2	lm	M, bt, sep, ps, ■	114, 166, 249, 389
Solenidae					
<i>Solen marginatus</i> Pulteney, 1799 [<i>S. vagina</i>]	1-22, 25	0-10	clmm	M, bt, sep, ps, ■	84, 91, 114, 249
Tellinidae					
<i>Gastrana fragilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Psammobia</i> , <i>Tellina</i>]	1-22, 25	-36	clm	M, bt, ep, ar, ar-ps, sg	84, 249, 389
<i>Tellina donacina</i> Linnaeus, 1758 [<i>Angulus</i> , <i>Moerella</i>]	1-22, 25, 26	-20, 30	clmm	M, bt, sep, ps-pe	84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Tellina fabula</i> Gmelin, 1791 [<i>Angulus</i> , <i>Fabulina</i> , <i>Moerella</i>]	7, 25	-10, 40	clm	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	84, 249, 389
<i>Tellina tenuis</i> da Costa, 1778 [<i>T. exigua</i> , <i>Angulus exiguus</i> , <i>Moerella</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 77, *79	0.2-24	clm	M, bt, sep, ps, ps-s	84, 91, 249, 389
Donacidae					
<i>Donax trunculus</i> Linnaeus, 1758 [<i>D. t. julianae</i> , <i>D. julianae</i>]	1-22, 25	2-15	clm	M, bt, sep, ps	84, 91, 249, 295

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
<i>Donax semistriatus</i> Poli, 1795 [<i>D. fabagella</i> , <i>D. venustus</i>]	16, 25	10-15, 20	lm	84, 249, 389
Semelidae				
<i>Abra alba</i> (W. Wood, 1802) [<i>A. a. pontica</i> , <i>Syndesmya</i>]	1-22, 26, 27, 28, 69	-135, 170	clmm	84, 249, 389
<i>Abra prismatica</i> (Montagu, 1808) [<i>A. fragilis</i> , <i>A. milashevichi</i> , <i>A. nitida</i>]	1-22, 26, 27, 69	5-90	clm, ? clmm	67, 84, 249, 389
<i>Abra segmentum</i> (Récluz, 1843) [<i>A. ovata</i> , <i>Syndesmya</i>]	7, 13, 23, 26, *66, 68, *69, 76, 77, *79, 85, *86	-15, 40	ml	84, 91, 249, 374, 389
Dreissenidae				
<i>Dreissena polymorpha</i> (Pallas, 1771) [<i>D. (Dreissena) polymorpha polymorpha</i>]	58, 59, 60, *68, *69, 71, 76, 92, 96	-20	(h - i), Rc	84, 91, 152, 249, 305, 374, 375, 389
<i>Dreissena rostriformis</i> (Deshayes, 1838) [<i>D. (Pontodreissena) r. distincta</i>]	1-22, 27, 28	50-200	pc, Rc, Sf, +	166, 172, 178, 249
Pisidiidae				
<i>Sphaerium corneum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	*67		(h)	6, 305, 389
<i>Musculium lacustre</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)	42, 43, *67, 92		(tp)	4, 6, 305, 389
Veneridae				
<i>Gouldia minima</i> (Montagu, 1803) [<i>Circe</i> , <i>Venus</i>]	5, 16, 25, 26, 27	-25, 70	clm	67, 91, 249, 389
<i>Pitar rudis</i> (Poli, 1795) [<i>Meretrix</i> r. var. <i>ochropicta</i> , <i>Cytherea</i> , <i>Venus ochropicta</i>]	3, 7, 13, 16, 17, 25, 26, 27	-40, 200	lmmg	67, 84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Irus irus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Venerupis</i>]	3, 7, 24	0-10	eamiswp	67, 84, 249, 389
<i>Chamelea gallina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Chione gallina corrugata</i> , <i>Venus</i>]	1-22, 25, 69	-30, 90	clm, ce	84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Politiapes aureus</i> (Gmelin, 1791) [<i>P. petalima</i> , <i>T. rugata</i> , <i>T. discrepans</i> , <i>T. lineatus</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 27	2-65	clm	67, 84, 91, 249, 389
Petricolidae				
<i>Petricola lithophaga</i> (Philippson, 1788)	7, 11, 12, 13, 24	-10, 26	lmi	84, 91, 249, 389
Myoida				
Myidae				
<i>Mya arenaria</i> Linnaeus, 1758 [<i>M. truncata</i>]	1-22, 25, 26, 68, 69	0.30-12	cbm, i	175, 249, 252, 253
Corbulidae				
<i>Lentidium mediterraneum</i> (O. G. Costa, 1829) [<i>Corbulomya maeotica</i> , <i>Corbula</i>]	7, 25, 69	2-20	m, ? lm	84, 249, 389
Pholiadidae				
<i>Pholas dactylus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	5, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 24	-15	eamrs, amrs	84, 91, 249, 389
<i>Barnea candida</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) [<i>Pholas</i>]	7, 24	-15	namnei, ami	84, 249, 389
Teredinidae				

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Zoogeographical	Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)				
<i>Teredo navalis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1-22, 69	-70		amip, K, i	M, bt, ep-me, c, is	84, 91, 249, 374,
<i>Nototeredo norvegica</i> (Spengler, 1792) [<i>Teredo utriculus</i>]	10, 17	-70		bam	M, bt, ep-me	75, 252
Anomalodesmata (Pholadomyoidea)						
Thraciidae						
<i>Thracia papyracea</i> (Poli, 1791)	7, 25	0.2-22		clm, ? nam	M, bt, ep, ps, ps-pe	84, 249, 389
BRYOZOA					plankton larvae	
GYMNOLAEMATA						
CHEILOSTOMATIDA						
Membraniporidae						
<i>Membranipora tenuis</i> Desor, 1848	7, *69			nap	M, bt	84, 249, 389
<i>Conopeum reticulum</i> (Linnaeus, 1767) [<i>Membranipora denticulata</i>]	3	-40		ham	M, bt, eh, mb	67, 249, 389
<i>Conopeum seurati</i> (Canu, 1928)	84			neamswp	M-B, bt, eh, 8-10%	141, 249, 252
Electridae (Membraniporidae)						
<i>Einhornia crustulenta</i> (Pallas, 1766) [<i>Electra, Membranipora</i>]	*69, 96			abapbp	M-B, bt, eh, 3%	84, 249, 389
<i>Electra monostachys</i> (Busk, 1854)	13	0-60		ham	M, bt, ro, sg	252, 330
<i>Electra pilosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1767) [<i>Membranipora</i>]	7	10-50		namswp	M, bt, mb	84, 249, 389
<i>Electra pontica</i> Gruncharova, 1980	2, 84	0.2-0.7		● p, Er	M, bt, ep	142, 252
Tendridae (Membraniporidae)						
<i>Tendra zostericola</i> Nordmann, 1839 [<i>Electra, Membranipora</i>]	7, 11, 12, 13			adp	M, bt	67, 91, 249, 389
Cryptosulidae (Smittinidae)						
<i>Cryptosula pallasiana</i> (Moll, 1803) [<i>Lepralia</i>]	3, 7, 11, 16, *69			amp	M, bt, ep	66, 67, 91, 249, 389
Bitectiporidae (Schizoporellidae)						
<i>Schizomavella linearis</i> (Hassall, 1841) [<i>Schizoporella</i>]	7	10-		clm, bamnep	M, bt, mb-hb	84, 249, 389
CTENOSTOMATIDA						
Vesiculariidae						
? <i>Bowerbankia caudata</i> (Hincks, 1877)	*69, *79, 84, *86			aamp	M, bt, ep, 6%	141, 249, 374, 384
<i>Bowerbankia gracilis</i> Leidy, 1855 [? <i>B. caudata</i>]	*69, *79, 84, *86	-10		amp	M, bt, ep, 6%	141, 249, 374, 384
<i>Bowerbankia imbricata</i> (Adams, 1798)	84			amp	M, bt, eh, 10%	141, 249, 252
Victorellidae						
<i>Victorella pavida</i> Saville Kent, 1870	*68, 71, *78, *79, 84, *86, 88, 90, 93, 94	5		pc, amp, Rc	M, bt, ep, eh, 0.4-20%	141, 249, 374, 389

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			Ecological data	References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical		
PHYLACTOLAEMATA					
PLUMATELLIDA					
Fredericellidae					
<i>Fredericella sultana</i> (Blumenbach, 1779)	84, 96		(k)	L, bt, 0-10‰	141, 249, 252
Plumatellidae					
<i>Plumatella casmiana</i> Oka, 1907	84, 96		(hptn, ? sk)	L, bt, 3-6‰	141, 249, 252
<i>Plumatella emarginata</i> Allman, 1844	84, 96		(k)	L, bt, 3-6‰	141, 249, 252
<i>Plumatella fungosa</i> (Pallas, 1768)	60, *68, *79, 84, *86, 88		(h)	L, bt, 1‰	141, 249, 374, 389
<i>Plumatella repens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	60, *68, 84, 92, 96		(k)	L, bt, 3-6‰	141, 249, 374, 389
PHORONIDA					
Phoronidae					
<i>Phoronis psammophila</i> Cori, 1889 [<i>Ph. euxinicola</i>]	1-22, 25-28, 35, 51, 69	0-100	amp, ? K	M-B, bt, eb, ps-pe, s	247, 249, 252
ENTOPROCTA (CAMPTOZOA)					
COLONIALES (URNATELLIDA)					
Barentsiidae					
<i>Barentsia benedeni</i> (Foettinger, 1886) [<i>Arthropodoria kowalewskii</i>]	*69, *79, 84, *86, 88		bapp	M-B, bt, 8-16‰	249, 374, 389
CHAETOGNATHA					
SAGITTOIDEA					
APHRAGMOPHORA					
Sagittidae					
<i>Parasagitta setosa</i> (Müller, 1847) [<i>Sagitta euxinica</i>]	7, 11, 12, 17, 29, *69		bam	M, p, 12‰	91, 198, 319, 374
ECHINODERMATA					
HOLOTHUROIDEA					
DENDROCHIROTIDA					
Cucumariidae					
<i>Stereoderma kirchbergii</i> (Heller, 1868) [<i>Cucumaria</i> , ? <i>C. orientalis</i> - n. nudum]		30-70	m, hom, ? lm	M, bt, hb, pe	198, 249
APODIDA					
Synaptidae					
<i>Leptosynapta inhaerens</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776) [<i>Synapta hispida</i> - n. nudum]	1-22, 27, 28	60-100	anamnp	M, bt, hb, pe	223, 249, 392
<i>Labidoplax digitata</i> (Montagu, 1815) [<i>Ostergrenia adratrica</i>]		-70	ncamal	M, bt, eb, ps, pe	198, 249
? <i>Labidoplax thompsoni</i> (Herapath, 1865) [<i>Ostergrenia</i>]		-70	lm	M, bt, eb, ps	198, 249

Table 2. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Horizontal	Depth (m)	Zoogeographical	
OPHIUROIDEA				
Ophiurida				
Amphiuridae				
? <i>Amphipholis squamata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828) [<i>Amphiura</i>]	11, 13, 21, 22		K	91, 389, 410
<i>Amphiura stepanovi</i> Djakonov, 1954	1-22, 27, 28	20-175	● p	198, 249
CHORDATA				
ASCIDIACEA				
STOLIDOBRANCHIA				
Molgulidae				
<i>Eugyra adriatica</i> Drasche, 1884	26, 27, 28	25-100	m, hom	198, 249
<i>Molgula appendiculata</i> Heller, 1877 [<i>Ctenicella</i>]	7, 25, 26, 27, 28	20-120	lm	198, 249, 358
<i>Molgula euprocta</i> Drasche, 1884 [<i>M. impura</i> , <i>M. ompura</i> ?]	5, 7, 69, *79		lm	67, 84, 249, 374
Styeliidae (Botryllidae)				
<i>Botryllus schlosseri</i> (Pallas, 1766)	1-22, 24	0-60	namp, ? SK	84, 91, 249, 295, 298, 374
Enterogona				
Ascidiidae				
<i>Ascidiella aspersa</i> (O. F. Müller, 1776)	3, 7	20-50	amiswp	67, 249, 295, 298
Cionidae				
<i>Ciona intestinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2, 3	15-100	antamp	67, 249, 389
LARVACEA (APPENDICULARIA)				
COPELATA				
Oikopleuridae				
<i>Oikopleura dioica</i> Fol, 1872 [<i>O. cophocerca</i>]	7, 11, 13, 29, 69		amip, ? SK	91, 198, 319, 389
LEPTOCARDII				
AMPHIOXIFORMES				
Branchiostomidae				
<i>Branchiostoma lanceolatum</i> (Pallas, 1774) [<i>Amphioxus</i>]	6-8, 11, 13, 16-21, 25	17, 21	amip	84, 91, 249, 389

Species, which are distributed either in the northern or in the southern part of the coast (with 1 to 3 localities), number 20-25%. Most of them are benthic forms that belong to poorly explored or rare taxa. A part of recently reported Black Sea endemics could be added to this group as well. In most cases, the species distribution is related to the level of study of the corresponding coastal region. It can be seen under juxtaposition of the found species in localities (Table 1). Three areas of good research are outlined (over 200 species established). Firstly are the vicinities of Varna (601 species) where the investigations of the Black Sea began a century ago. The popular resort centers – Nesebar, Pomorie, Burgas and Sozopol (220 to 274 species) form an area of good research. Owing to Bulgarian and Romanian specialists, the region of Kaliakra Cape (230 species) is also well studied. Of coastal basins, the most studied (about 100 species recorded) are the lakes Durankulak, Ezerets-Shabla, Beloslav, Varna, Pomorie, Atanasovsko, Burgas, Mandra and the firth of Ropotamo River. The rich species composition of the lakes Varna and Beloslav is changed after the connection with sea (1909 and 1923) and their transformation into ports (after 1976). Fauna of the lakes Burgas (anthropogenic impact after 1960) and Mandra (dam since 1963) became considerably poor.

The Black Sea below the depths of 180-200 m is enriched with released H_2S , which makes the real deep-sea life impossible. The groups of **steno-** (epi- and hypo-), **meso-**, and **eurybathic** species are presented. The vertical distribution is analyzed for 800 species (75.9%) – marine and marine-brackish forms, according to available data (Table 4). Most species are found from 0 to 25 m on sand (396 species) and rocky (257 species) bottom.

The most numerous are the **stenoepibathic** species (465 species – 58.1%). The inhabitants of the supralittoral zone, shallow coastal zone (to 5-10 m), as well as species, which reach the depth of 15-30 m and approach to mesobathic forms, belong to this group. An intermediate niche, closer to mesobathic forms, is occupied by some representatives of the group, which reach higher depths. They are presented in 16 types, of which the most numerous are the representatives of Arthropoda, Annelida and Mollusca.

The group of **Eurybathic** (168 species – 21.0%) species includes Black Sea species, which are found in both little and great depths. Most eurybathic forms reach the depth of 130-150 m. They are presented in 12 types, of which the representatives of Arthropoda, Nematoda, Annelida and Mollusca predominate.

Table 3. Taxonomic diversity of the invertebrate animals from the Bulgarian Black Sea

Types	Classes	Orders	Families	Species
Porifera	2	6	13	23
Cnidaria	3	10	25	38
Ctenophora	2	3	3	4
Plathelminthes	1	5	16	29
Nemertini	2	3	9	26
Gastrotricha	1	2	6	13
Nematoda	2	8	34	112
Cephalorhyncha	1	2	3	4
Rotifera	1	4	22	121
Annelida	5	16	49	173
Tardigrada	2	3	5	5
Arthropoda	4	28	199	802
Mollusca	3	20	65	152
Bryozoa	2	3	9	19
Phoronida	1	1	1	1
Entoprocta	1	1	1	1
Chaetognatha	1	1	1	1
Echinodermata	2	3	3	6
Chordata	3	4	6	8
Total	39	123	470	1537

Table 4. Distribution of the invertebrate animals by categories according to depth (Note. Only marine and brackish species, for which data are available, are included.)

Types	Epi-bathic	Hypo-bathic	Meso-bathic	Eury-bathic
Porifera	2		4	9
Cnidaria	7	1	2	10
Ctenophora	1			1
Plathelminthes	13			
Nemertini	5	4	6	5
Gastrotricha	4			
Nematoda	21	14	11	29
Cephalorhyncha		1	1	1
Rotifera	12			
Annelida	79	3	16	19
Tardigrada	5			
Arthropoda	239	21	36	74
Mollusca	69	2	33	15
Bryozoa	5	1	3	
Phoronida				1
Entoprocta	1			
Chaetognatha	1			
Echinodermata		3		3
Chordata	1	2	3	1
Total	465	52	115	168

The **Mesobathic** (115 species – 14.4%) species reach the depth over 40 m in the Black Sea. Some species could be considered stenomesobathic forms. They are presented in 10 types, of which the representatives of Arthropoda and Mollusca prevail.

The **Stenohypobathic** species are the smallest group (52 species – 6.5%). They rarely could be found at smaller depth up to 25 m and usually reach highest density below 60-120 m. They are presented in 10 types, of which the representatives of Arthropoda and Nematoda predominate. Recently some species of Nematoda, Polychaeta and Harpacticoida have been established in hypoxic habitats at depth below 200-250 m (SERGEEVA & ZAIKA, 2013).

FORMATION OF THE BLACK SEA FAUNA is connected with the origin of the Black Sea basin itself. The Upper Miocene Sarmatian Sea (18-30‰, a descendant of Tethys) gave rise to the Pontian Sea-Lake, from which two separate basins were formed later, the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea. Initially, the Black Sea basin had been inhabited by fauna similar to the Caspian one [Chaudian Sea (12-14‰) and Paleoeuxinian Sea (6-8‰)]. Then, it had been connected with the Mediterranean Sea and became saline, so the Mediterranean fauna penetrated into it, whereas the Caspian fauna retreated to the brackish coastal parts [time of Uzunlar Sea (16‰) and Karangat Sea (22-30‰)]. Later, the connection with the Mediterranean Sea had been severed, and the brackish basin [the New Euxinian Sea (7‰)] originated, where the Mediterranean fauna disappeared. Recently, 7000-8000 years ago, this basin had been again connected with the Mediterranean Sea and its level increased. The marine fauna invaded it and the current Black Sea had been formed (MISCHEV & POPOV, 1978; SHOPOV, 1993; DIMITROV et al., 1998; EVLOGIEV, 2009; STUDENCKA & JASIONOWSKI, 2011).

Then, before the last glaciation, a connection with the Caspian basin arose (via Manych channel), and Caspian interglacial immigrants invaded the Black Sea (MORDUKHAY-BOLTOVSKOY, 1960; NEVESSKAYA, 1965; STAROBOGATOV, 1970; SHOPOV, 1996). Most authors accept these species as Caspian relicts (known also as Sarmatian, Pontian, Pontian-Caspian, or autochthonous faunal elements). They are concentrated mainly in the coastal lakes-firths and the mouths of the Black Sea rivers and inhabit the freshwater and brackish basins. Part of them is subfossils for the sea itself. The Caspian relicts usually have Pontian or Pontian-Caspian ranges. Some of them have entered the river systems of Central and Western Europe (spread to other continents) where

they are considered invasive species. According to MORDUKHAY-BOLTOVSKOY (1960) the evolution of the Caspian fauna gave rise to the origin of eurybiontic oligohaline and freshwater forms, which began to acquire new habitats with their pervasion in Black Sea. The “relicts” *Dreissena polymorpha* Pallas and *D. bugensis* – one of the most invasive recent mollusk, are a typical example. Recent data for the distribution of many relict taxa (mainly in the latest electronic editions) contradict their relict nature. It has been established that these taxa are widespread outside the Pontian-Caspian region. These may be invasive relict forms (a small number of species) or species with unclear distribution, accepted as relicts. The main portion of the Caspian relicts (41 species, or 3.9%) is benthic brackish forms (38 species, or 92.7%).

THE MARINE AND MARINE-BRACKISH FORMS are divided into 162 zoogeographical (areographical) categories, combined into 4 main groups and 16 subgroups (Table 5).

The main portion of the Black Sea fauna (740 species, or 70.2 %) has an Atlantic-Mediterranean origin and represents the impoverished Atlantic-Mediterranean fauna. As this fauna was becoming impoverished, the stenobiotic Lusitanian-Mediterranean species were eliminated, so this category is defined by the eurybiontic forms, often distributed along the European coast up to Scotland, North Sea and Scandinavia. Thus an impression is created of the atlantization of this fauna, manifested differently in the various taxonomic groups, benthic and planktonic forms. The atlantization is poorly presented in the planktonic forms (50 species, or 42.4%) and most presented in the benthic forms (712 species, or 72.8%). There is no a considerable difference (in percentages) in the atlantization of the marine (716 species, or 69.9%) and the brackish (101 species, or 65.6%) species.

A portion of the Arctic- and Antarctic-Atlantic (high-latitude boreal and antiboreal) species (43 species, or 4.1%) is not presented in the Mediterranean Sea. Its percentage varies slightly as their number is insignificant in the brackish and planktonic forms. The Arctic-North-Atlantic-, Arctic-Boreal-Atlantic-Mediterranean and circumeuropean species predominate (total of 26 species, or 2.5%). Not all of the Holatlantic and North Atlantic species (99 species, or 9.4%) are presented in Mediterranean Sea. The marine and benthic forms prevail, of which the North-Atlantic-, Boreal-Atlantic- and Holatlantic-Mediterranean and Boreal Atlantic-Pontian species (total of 76 species, or 7.2%) predominate. Between the tropical- and subtropical Atlantic species (109

species, or 10.3%), the Lusitanian-Mediterranean forms (79 species, or 7.5%) predominate. The East and Northeast Atlantic species are most numerous (251 species, or 23.8%). The main portion of them is the Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (148 species, or 14.1%) and Celtic-Pontian (44 species, or 4.2%) forms. The Mediterranean species (90 species, or 8.5%) are poorly presented in the planktonic and brackish communities. Almost all Pontian-Caspian species (28 species, or 2.7%) are benthos and brackish (27 species, or 17.5%) forms.

The Pontian species (Black Sea endemics) are 118 (11.2%). The benthic (115 species, or 97.5%) and marine (114 species, or 96.6%) forms predominate. The brackish species (11 species, or 9.3%) most often are Caspian relicts. Some of the Pontian species is likely to be found in other seas under better research. This refers mainly to the groups of Nematoda, Ostracoda and Copepoda which are well-studied in the Black Sea. The most Black Sea endemic species are concentrated in several groups – Porifera, Nemertini, Nematoda, Rotifera, Ostracoda and Copepoda. Many endemic forms, known from previous data, are brought to synonyms or downgraded to subspecies today. Thus there are no data on the Black Sea endemic species in the recent malacological literature, of which there were more in the old literature [KANEVA-ABADJIEVA (1960a) recorded 24 species endemic mollusks from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast]. Many species have changed after their penetration into the Black Sea; they are described as new taxa. An interesting example is the hermit-crab *Clibanarius erythropus*. Because of the lack of large mollusks in the Black Sea, it was forced to use the shells of snails of the genus *Gibbula* and greatly reduces its size (became known as *C. misanthropus*). With the appearance of *Rapana venossa* in Black Sea, the crab begins to use large shells and again reaches the normal size for crabs in Mediterranean Sea.

The number of forms with Cosmopolitan (121 species – 11.5%), Atlantic-Pacific (120 species – 11.4%) and Atlantic-Indian (72 species – 6.8%) type of distribution is considerably smaller than the forms of Atlantic type. They predominate as species composition in the marine and benthic species but their percentage is highest in the plankton forms (from 8.5 to 28.0%). The differences in the percentages are not big for the benthic, marine and brackish forms (from 5 to 11%) with the exception of the brackish Atlantic-Pacific species (18.2%). Most Cosmopolitan forms (2/3) have Atlantic-Indian-Pacific distribution. The Holatlantic- and East Atlantic-Indian-Pacific species (58 species, or 5.5%) predominate, of which the

Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific forms are the most numerous (37 species). The number of North Atlantic-Indian-Pacific (15 species) and the tropical and subtropical Atlantic-Indian-Pacific (6 species) species is smaller. About 1/3 of the Cosmopolitan forms have Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Indian-Pacific distribution as the typical Cosmopolitans and Subcosmopolitans (a total of 25 species, or 2.4%) predominate. About 1/4 of the species with Atlantic-Pacific type of distribution belong to Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Pacific forms (23 species – 2.2%). The Atlantic-Pacific species (97 species, or 9.2%) predominate, the main parts of which are with North and South Atlantic-, Hol- and North Atlantic- and North Atlantic-Pacific distribution (a total of 73 species, or 6.9%). The Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific species (14 species) are the most numerous. A small number of Hol- and South Atlantic-, East and West Atlantic- and Tropical and Subtropical Atlantic-Pacific species (a total of 24 species, or 2.3%) occur as well. Most forms with Atlantic-Indian type of distribution include Hol- and North Atlantic-Indian and East and Northeast Atlantic-Indian species (a total of 61 species, or 5.8%). The North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian and Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Indian species (7 species each) are the most numerous. Seven tropical and subtropical Atlantic-Indian and 4 Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Indian forms occur as well.

THE FRESHWATER-BRACKISH, FRESHWATER AND TERRESTRIAL FORMS, connected with water, recorded from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, are divided into 80 zoogeographical categories, combined into 2 main groups and 5 subgroups (Table 6).

Species distributed in Palaearctic and beyond it. This group (296 species, or 58.3%) includes 36 zoogeographical categories, of which 29 combine species of **Northern type** (widely distributed in Holarctic or Palaearctic) and 7 – species of **Southern type** (distributed only in southern Palaearctic). This group is important for the zoogeography of the coastal fauna because of its great species diversity. It is connected with the typical for the sea coasts natural habitats, optimum for the development of its representatives and is poorly presented in the interior. The difference among the brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms is from 8.7% to 37.0% (from 74 to 271 species). The species of northern type have vast areas and ecological flexibility. The Cosmopolitan, Subcosmopolitan and Holarctic species (a total of 184 species, or 36.2%) are the most numerous. These species, except the Holarctic forms, are almost not presented in the terrestrial forms. In the brackish

Table 5. Zoogeographical characteristic of the marine and brackish Invertebrate fauna from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brackish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
COSMOPOLITAN TYPE	121	11.48	105	10.74	25	21.19	119	11.63	18	11.69
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Indian-Pacific	42	3.98	36	3.68	7	5.93	42	4.10	7	4.54
Cosmopolitan (K)	15	1.42	10	1.02	5	4.24	15	1.47	5	3.25
Subcosmopolitan (SK)	10	0.95	10	1.02	1	0.85	10	0.98	2	1.30
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (aanamp)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (aamp)	6	0.57	6	0.61			6	0.59		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific (aainp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (anamp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific (anaminp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (antamp)	2	0.19	1	0.10	1	0.85	2	0.19		
Antarctic-Pontian-Indo-Pacific (anpip)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Indian-Pacific	79	7.49	69	7.05	18	15.25	77	7.53	11	7.14
HOL- AND EAST ATLANTIC-INDIAN-PACIFIC	58	5.50	49	5.01	15	12.71	57	5.58	10	6.49
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (amp)	37	3.51	31	3.17	12	10.17	36	3.52	7	4.54
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific (amiwp)	4	0.38	2	0.20	2	1.69	4	0.39	1	0.65
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Southwest Pacific (amiswp)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand (aminz)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39	2	1.30
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-North Pacific (aminp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Northwest Pacific (aminwp)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea-Pacific (amrsp)	2	0.19	1	0.10	1	0.85	2	0.19		
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (eamip)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Southwest Pacific (eamiswp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
TROPICAL AND SUBTROPICAL ATLANTIC-INDIAN-PACIFIC	6	0.57	5	0.51	2	1.69	6	0.59		
Circum[sub]tropical (cst)	3	0.28	2	0.20	1	0.85	3	0.29		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indo-West Pacific (lmwiwp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific (miwp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Pontian-Indo-New Zealand (pinz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
NORTH ATLANTIC-INDIAN-PACIFIC	15	1.42	15	1.53	1	0.85	14	1.37	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Pacific (namp)	3	0.28	3	0.31	1	0.85	2	0.19	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-West Pacific (namiwp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-Malayan (namim)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand (naminz)	5	0.47	5	0.51			5	0.49		

Table 5. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brakish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea-Northeast Pacific (namrsnep)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indo-New Zealand (neaminz)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
ATLANTIC-INDIAN TYPE	72	6.83	67	6.85	10	8.47	70	6.84	7	4.54
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Indian	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian (aami)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian (aamni)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea (anamrs)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian (antami)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Indian	68	6.45	63	6.44	10	8.47	66	6.45	7	4.54
TROPICAL AND SUBTROPICAL ATLANTIC-INDIAN	7	0.66	5	0.51	2	1.69	7	0.68	2	1.30
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Indian (lmi)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian-West Indian (lmmwi)	1	0.09			1	0.85	1	0.09		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indian (lmwi)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09	1	0.65
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian (lmnei)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19	1	0.65
Mediterranean-North Indian (mni)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Mediterranean-Red Sea (mrs)	1	0.09			1	0.85	1	0.09		
HOL- AND NORTH ATLANTIC-INDIAN	36	4.42	33	3.37	5	4.24	34	3.32	3	1.95
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian (ami)	6	0.57	6	0.61			5	0.49	1	0.65
Atlantic-Pontian-Indian (api)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian (amni)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian (amnei)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian (amwi)	2	0.19	2	0.20	1	0.85	2	0.19		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea (amrs)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian (nami)	7	0.66	7	0.72	3	2.54	6	0.59		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Indian (namni)	6	0.57	5	0.51	1	0.85	6	0.59		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian (namnei)	5	0.47	5	0.51			5	0.49	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Indian (napnei)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian (namwi)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea (namrs)	2	0.19			2	1.69	2	0.19		
EAST AND NORTHEAST ATLANTIC-INDIAN	25	2.37	25	2.56	3	2.54	25	2.44	2	1.30
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Indian (eami)	4	0.38	4	0.41	1	0.85	4	0.39	1	0.65
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Indian (eamwi)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		

Table 5. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brakish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Indian (eamswi)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Red Sea (eamrs)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Indian (clmi)	7	0.66	7	0.72			7	0.68	1	0.65
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Indian (clmwi)	5	0.47	5	0.51	2	1.69	5	0.49		
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northwest Indian (clmnwi)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Northeast Indian (clmnei)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Celtic-Pontian-Northeast Indian (cpnei)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
ATLANTIC-PACIFIC TYPE	120	11.38	94	9.61	33	27.97	118	11.53	28	18.18
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Pacific	23	2.18	20	2.04	4	3.39	23	2.25	3	1.95
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific (aanamp)	1	0.09	1	0.10	1	0.85	1	0.09		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific (anamp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific (anamp)	5	0.47	4	0.41	1	0.85	5	0.49		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific (anamp)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Pacific (anapnep)	1	0.09			1	0.85	1	0.09	1	0.65
Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific (abamp)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Boreal Pacific (abapbp)	3	0.28	2	0.20	1	0.85	3	0.29	2	1.30
Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Northeast Pacific (abapnep)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific (aamswp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Celtic-Mediterranean-New Zealand (acmnz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Antarctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific (antamp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Pacific	97	9.20	74	7.57	29	24.58	95	9.27	25	16.23
HOL- AND NORTH ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	26	2.47	22	2.25	6	5.08	26	2.54	3	1.95
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific (amp)	14	1.33	13	1.33	3	2.54	14	1.37		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific (amnp)	1	0.09			1	0.85	1	0.09		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific (namp)	6	0.57	4	0.41	2	1.69	6	0.59	2	1.30
Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Pacific (bapp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09	1	0.65
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Japonic (amj)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific (amnep)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
TROPICAL AND SUBTROPICAL ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	7	0.66	6	0.61	1	0.85	7	0.68		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-West Pacific (lmwp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Mediterranean-Japonic (mji)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Mediterranean-Mauritanian-Guinean-Tasmanian (mmgt)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		

Table 5. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brackish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-New Zealand (lmnz)	2	0.19	1	0.10	1	0.85	2	0.19		
Mediterranean-New Zealand (mnz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
NORTH ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	19	1.80	19	1.94	18	1.76	1	0.65		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific (namnp)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Boreal Pacific (bamnp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Boreal Atlantic-Pontian-Boreal Pacific (bapbp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Circumboreal-Mediterranean (cbm)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific (namnep)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Northeast Pacific (bamnep)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-North Pacific (neamnp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Aleutian (neamal)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Japonic (neamj)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Celtic-Pontian-Japonic (cpj)	1	0.09	1	0.10					1	0.65
Pontian-Northeast Pacific (pnep)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
NORTH AND SOUTH ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	28	2.66	17	1.74	12	10.17	27	2.64	15	9.74
Circumboreal-Mediterranean-Australian (cbma)	1	0.09	1	0.10	1	0.85	1	0.09	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-South Pacific (namsp)	2	0.19	1	0.10			2	0.19	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southeast Pacific (namsep)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific (namswp)	3	0.28	2	0.20	2	1.69	3	0.29	2	1.30
Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific (bamswp)	4	0.38	2	0.20	2	1.69	4	0.39	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand (namnz)	9	0.85	4	0.41	5	4.24	8	0.78	6	
Carolinian-Celtic-Pontian-New Zealand (cacpnz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09	1	0.65
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific (neamswp)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19	1	0.65
Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand (neamnz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-New Zealand (clmnz)	3	0.28	1	0.10	2	1.69	3	0.29	2	1.30
Celtic-Lusitanian-Pontian-New Zealand (clpnz)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
HOL- AND SOUTH ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	9	0.85	4	0.41	6	5.08	9	0.88	5	3.25
Atlantic-Mediterranean-Southwest Pacific (amswp)	4	0.38	2	0.20	3	2.54	4	0.39	2	1.30
Atlantic-Pontian-Southwest Pacific (apswp)	1	0.09			1	0.85	1	0.09	1	0.65
Atlantic-Mediterranean-New Zealand (amnz)	4	0.38	2	0.20	2	1.69	4	0.39	2	1.30
EAST AND WEST ATLANTIC-PACIFIC	8	0.76	6	0.61	4	3.39	8	0.78	1	0.65
East Atlantic-Mediterranean-Pacific (eampp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		

Table 5. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brakish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
	Northeast Atlantic-Mediterranean-East Pacific (neamep)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09	
Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Pacific (amwp)	4	0.38	2	0.20	3	2.54	4	0.39	1	0.65
North Atlantic-Mediterranean-West Pacific (namwp)	2	0.19	2	0.20	1	0.85	2	0.19		
ATLANTIC TYPE	740	70.20	712	72.80	50	42.37	716	69.99	101	65.58
Arctic-Antarctic-Atlantic	43	4.08	41	4.19	7	5.93	42	4.11	5	3.25
Arctic-Antarctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean (annam)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Atlantic-Mediterranean (aam)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	4.11		
Arctic-North Atlantic-Mediterranean (anam)	12	1.14	11	1.12	2	1.69	11	1.07	1	0.65
Arctic-North Atlantic-Pontian (anap)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean (abam)	7	0.66	7	0.72	1	0.85	7	0.68	3	1.95
Arctic-Boreal Atlantic-Pontian (abap)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29	1	0.65
Arctic-Circumeeuropean-Mauritanian (acem)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Arctic-Circumeeuropean (ace)	4	0.38	3	0.31	2	1.69	4	0.39		
Arctic-Celtic-Pontian (acp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Circumeeuropean-Mauritanian (cem)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Circumeeuropean (ce)	7	0.66	7	0.72	2	1.69	7	0.68		
Antarctic-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (anclm)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Atlantic	697	66.13	671	68.61	43	36.44	674	65.88	96	62.34
HOL- AND NORTH ATLANTIC	99	9.39	95	9.71	8	6.78	98	9.58	13	8.44
Holatlantic-Mediterranean (ham)	13	1.23	12	1.23	2	1.69	12	1.17	5	3.25
Atlantic-Mediterranean (am)	5	0.47	5	0.51			5	0.49		
Atlantic-Pontian (ap)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
North Atlantic-Mediterranean (nam)	27	2.56	25	2.56	3	2.54	27	2.64	3	1.95
North Atlantic-Pontian (nap)	5	0.47	5	0.51			5	0.49	1	0.65
Boreal-Antiboreal Atlantic-Pontian (baap)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Boreal Atlantic-Mediterranean (bam)	23	2.18	22	2.25	2	1.69	23	2.25	3	1.95
Boreal Atlantic-Pontian (bap)	13	1.23	13	1.33	1	0.85	13	1.27	1	0.65
Virginian-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (vclm)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Carolinian-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (cclm)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39		
Carolinian-Celtic-Pontian (ccp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Caribbean-Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (kclm)	4	0.38	4	0.41			4	0.39		

Table 5. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Benthos		Plankton		Marine		Brakish	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
TROPICAL AND SUBTROPICAL ATLANTIC	109	10.34	99	10.12	8	6.78	108	10.56	9	5.84
Tropical Atlantic-Mediterranean (tam)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Virginian-Carolinian-Caribbean (vck)	2	0.19	1	0.10	1	0.85	2	0.19		
Carolinian-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (calm)	2	0.19	2	0.20			2	0.19		
Carolinian-Lusitanian-Pontian (calp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Caribbean-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (klm)	5	0.47	4	0.41			5	0.49		
Caribbean-Mediterranean-Mauritanian (kmm)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian-Guinean (lmmg)	5	0.47	5	0.51			5	0.49		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian (lmm)	11	1.04	8	0.82	2	1.69	11	1.07		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean-South African (lmsa)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
Lusitanian-Mediterranean (lm)	79	7.49	74	7.57	5	4.24	78	7.62	9	5.84
Lusitanian-Pontian (lp)	1	0.09	1	0.10			1	0.09		
EAST AND NORTHEAST ATLANTIC	251	23.81	244	24.94	16	13.56	247	24.14	32	20.78
East Atlantic-Mediterranean (eam)	10	0.95	10	1.02			10	0.98		
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean-Mauritanian (clmm)	26	2.47	26	2.66	1	0.85	26	2.54	1	0.65
Celtic-Lusitanian-Mediterranean (clm)	148	14.04	147	15.03	7	5.93	147	14.37	21	13.64
Celtic-Lusitanian-Pontian (clp)	15	1.42	12	1.23	4	4.24	13	1.27	5	3.25
Celtic-Mediterranean (cm)	6	0.57	6	0.61			6	0.59		
Celtic-Pontian-Caspian (cpc)	2	0.19	1	0.10	1	0.85	2	0.19	2	1.30
Celtic-Pontian (cp)	44	4.17	42	4.29	3	2.54	43	4.20	3	1.95
MEDITERRANEAN-PONTIAN-CASPIAN	238	22.58	233	23.82	11	9.32	221	21.60	42	27.27
Holomediterranean (hom)	23	2.18	22	2.25	1	0.85	23	2.25	3	1.95
Mediterranean (m)	28	2.66	28	2.86			28	2.74		
East Mediterranean (em)	9	0.85	9	0.92	1	0.85	9	0.88		
North Mediterranean (nm)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Adriatic-Aegean-Pontian (adep)	3	0.28	3	0.31			3	0.29		
Adriatic-Pontian (adp)	10	0.95	10	1.02			10	0.98		
Aegean-Pontian (ep)	14	1.33	14	1.43	1	0.85	13	1.27		
Pontian-Caspian-Aral (pca)	2	0.19	2	0.20	1	0.85	2	0.19	1	0.65
Pontian-Caspian (pc)	28	2.66	27	2.76	2	1.69	16	1.56	27	17.53
Pontian (p)	118	11.19	115	11.76	5	4.24	114	11.14	11	7.14
CASPIAN RELICT	41	3.89	39	3.99	4	3.39	21	2.05	38	24.67
Total	1054		978	92.88	118	11.21	1023	97.15	154	14.62

communities, the Holarctic species are poorly represented (17 species). The species of southern type are best represented in the terrestrial forms (11 species, or 5.5%). The presence of this group in different taxa depends on whether they include highly mobile and widely distributed forms or combine less mobile and more closely connected with certain conditions species. In the latter case, more important are the specific natural habitats to which species are adapted.

Species distributed only in Palaearctic but in more than one subregion (Palaearctic type). A total of 79 species (15.5%) that belong to this group, combined into 11 zoogeographical categories, has been established along the coast. The group includes from 8.1% to 25.9% (from 14 to 65 species) of the brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms. Its character is determined by Transpalaearctic, West Palaearctic, West and Central Palaearctic and Holopalaearctic species (a total of 63 species, or 12.4%) that are the most numerous. This correlation remains almost the same and varies from 1.9% to 8.5% (from 4 to 18 species) in the freshwater and terrestrial forms. In brackish forms the group is poorly presented – from 0.6% to 2.3% (from 1 to 4 species). The number of the European-North African species (from 3 to 5 species in the group) varies insignificantly. Two species have a longitudinal disjunction of their areas that includes parts of Siberia and Central Asia (Table 2).

Species distributed within one subregion of Palaearctic. This group (126 species, or 24.8%) includes species with **Eurosiberian** and **Mediterranean type** of distribution. The Mediterranean-Central Asian species are also included here according to many authors who combine Mediterranean and Central Asian subregions. The species with Mediterranean type of distribution are accepted in a general way and include elements (Submediterranean, Subiranian, and Pontian), that could be considered separately as well (GRUEV & KUSMANOV, 1994, 1999; GRUEV 1995, 2000). The **Eurosiberian species** are 55 (10.8%), of which the European species (31 species, or 6.1%) are the most numerous. They are combined into 9 zoogeographical categories and include from 6.9% to 11.5% (from 12 to 48 species) of the brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms. The Eurosiberian species are best represented in freshwater forms and poorly represented in brackish forms. Thirty-six species have European distribution only, of which 31 are wide-spread in Europe and 5 – in its separate regions (Central and South Europe). The **Mediterranean species** are 71 (13.9%), of which the Holomediterranean species (19 species – 3.7%) are most numerous. This group combines 24 zooge-

ographical categories with different origin, distribution and ecological peculiarities. It includes from 7.7% to 28.4% (19-57 species) of the brackish, freshwater and terrestrial forms. The group is best represented in terrestrial forms and poorly represented in freshwater forms. The endemics (11 species – 2.2%) are poorly represented – their number varies from 4 to 7 species. More are the regional endemics that have been found in the terrestrial forms. The specific conditions along the coast do not favor the formation of endemic taxa, which mostly are newly described forms or rare species with unclear distribution. The only local endemic (*Hauffenia lucidula*) is a crenobiotic species of the family Hydrobiidae – 95.5% of the species of this group are freshwater endemic forms.

ZOOPLANKTON. It includes representatives of Protozoa, Coelenterata, Ctenophora, Rotifera, Annelida (larvae), Arthropoda, Mollusca (larvae) and Chordata (VALKANOV, DIMOV & NAIDENOV, 1978; KONSULOV, 1991, 1998; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998). In regard to species diversity, the Black Sea zooplankton is characterized as poor (in comparison with the Mediterranean Sea). According to thermal conditions in the water mass the zooplankton is divided to thermophilic, eurythermic and cryophilic. The thermophilic representatives are found mainly in surface water layers to 25 m. The cryophilic and eurythermic forms dominate below the zone of thermowedge. The vertical distribution depends on the oxygen penetrating in the depth (100-175 m). The zooplankters have a specific distribution according to seasons and depth, which is determined by their temperature and trophic requirements. The eurythermic forms occur throughout the year as they are not influenced by temperature. The cryophilic forms occur in all depths in winter and fall below 50-60 m in summer. The thermophilic forms are found mainly in summer and disappear in winter. The bottom larvaton (meroplankton) is of great importance for species diversity of the benthic fauna. It is represented by Mollusca – veliger, Cyripedia – nauplius and cypris, Polychaeta – larvae, Pisces ova and larvae. The average annual biomass of the zooplankton in front of the Bulgarian coast is 74.25 mg/m³ and varies by seasons: in winter – 27 mg/m³, in spring – 77 mg/m³, in summer – 135 mg/m³ and in autumn – 48 mg/m³ (VALKANOV, DIMOV & NAIDENOV, 1978). After 10 years, these values are lower. The average annual spring biomass of zooplankton in the coastal zone is highest in front of Cape Galata (72.58 mg/m³), lower in front of Cape Kaliakra (58.79 mg/m³) and the lowest in front of Cape Emine (35.39 mg/

Table 6. Zoogeographical characteristic of the brackish, freshwater and terrestrial Invertebrate fauna from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Brackish (rare marine)		Freshwater		Terrestrial	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Species distributed in Palaearctic and out of it	296	58.27	127	73.84	271	65.14	74	36.81
NORTHERN TYPE	282	55.51	126	73.25	262	62.98	63	31.34
Cosmopolitan (k)	75	14.76	54	31.40	74	17.79	2	0.99
Subcosmopolitan (sk)	41	8.07	22	12.79	39	9.37		
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical (hptn)	5	0.98	2	1.16	4	0.96	1	0.50
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian (hpta)	2	0.39			1	0.24	1	0.50
Holarctic-Paleotropical (hpt)	3	0.59	2	1.16	3	0.72		
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental-Australian (hnoa)	3	0.59	1	0.58	3	0.72	1	0.50
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental (hno)	8	1.57	4	2.32	7	1.68	4	1.99
Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical-Australian (hnata)	3	0.59			2	0.48	1	0.50
Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical (hnat)	6	1.18	3	1.74	5	1.20	1	0.50
Holarctic-Neotropical-Australian (hna)	5	0.98	2	1.16	4	0.96	1	0.50
Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian (hata)	3	0.59	1	0.58	3	0.72		
Holarctic-Oriental-Australian (hoa)	3	0.59	1	0.58	3	0.72		
Holarctic-Neotropical (hn)	5	0.98	3	1.74	5	1.20	1	0.50
Holarctic-Afrotropical (hat)	7	1.38	3	1.74	5	1.20	2	0.99
Holarctic-Oriental (ho)	8	1.57	2	1.16	7	1.68	4	1.99
Holarctic-Australian (ha)	2	0.39	1	0.58	2	0.48		
Palaearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (ppta)	3	0.59			3	0.72		
Palaearctic-Afrotropical-Australian (pata)	2	0.39			1	0.24	1	0.50
Palaearctic-Oriental-Australian (poa)	2	0.39			2	0.48	2	0.99
Palaearctic-Paleotropical (ppt)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24	1	0.50
Palaearctic-Afrotropical (pat)	8	1.57	2	1.16	8	1.92	1	0.50
Palaearctic-Oriental (po)	9	1.77	3	1.74	9	2.16	6	2.98
West Palaearctic-Paleotropical (wppt)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
Transpalaearctic-Oriental (tpo)	2	0.39			2	0.48	2	0.99
West and Central Palaearctic-Oriental (wcpo)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
West Palaearctic-Afrotropical (wpat)	3	0.59			1	0.24	2	0.99
West Palaearctic-Oriental (wpo)	2	0.39	1	0.58	2	0.48	2	0.99
Holarctic (h)	68	13.39	17	9.88	63	15.14	23	11.44

Table 6. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Brakish (rare marine)		Freshwater		Terrestrial	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
European-Australian (ea)	1	0.20					1	0.50
SOUTH TYPE	14	2.76	1	0.58	9	2.16	11	5.47
Paleotropical-South Palearctic (ptsp)	2	0.39			2	0.48	1	0.50
Paleotropical-Mediterranean-Central Asian (ptmca)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
Paleotropical-Mediterranean (ptm)	2	0.39			1	0.24	2	0.99
Afrotropical-Mediterranean (atm)	3	0.59			1	0.24	2	0.99
Oriental-Mediterranean-Central Asian-Australian (omcaa)	1	0.20	1	0.58				
Oriental-Mediterranean-Central Asian (omca)	3	0.59			2	0.48	3	1.49
Oriental-Mediterranean (om)	2	0.39			2	0.48	2	0.99
Species with Palearctic distribution	205	40.35	45	26.16	145	34.85	127	63.18
PALAEARCTIC TYPE	79	15.55	14	8.14	65	15.62	52	25.87
Holopalaearctic (hop)	10	1.97	1	0.58	10	2.40	4	1.99
Transpalaearctic (tp)	21	4.13	1	0.58	18	4.33	17	8.46
West and Central Palearctic (wcp)	14	2.76	2	1.16	13	3.12	11	5.47
West Palearctic (wp)	18	3.54	2	1.16	14	3.36	10	4.97
Disjunct Palearctic (dp)	2	0.39	1	0.58	1	0.24	1	0.50
Euroiberian-Central Asian (esca)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
European-Central Asian (eca)	3	0.59	1	0.58	2	0.48	1	0.50
European-West Central Asian (ewca)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
European-Iran-Turanian (eit)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24		
European-Turanian (et)	2	0.39	1	0.58	1	0.24	1	0.50
European-North African (ena)	6	1.18	4	2.32	3	0.72	5	2.49
EUROSIBERIAN TYPE	55	10.83	12	6.98	48	11.54	18	8.95
Holoeuroiberian (hoes)	2	0.39	1	0.58	3	0.72	3	1.49
West and Central Euroiberian (wces)	7	1.38			5	1.20	2	0.99
West Euroiberian-Anatolian (wesa)	2	0.39			2	0.48	1	0.50
West Euroiberian (wes)	6	1.18			5	1.20	2	0.99
European-Anatolian (ean)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24		
Central and Southeast European-Anatolian (cseca)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24		
European (e)	31	6.10	9	5.23	26	6.25	8	3.98

Table 6. Continued

Zoogeographical scheme of the used categories and main taxa	Total		Brakish (rare marine)		Freshwater		Terrestrial	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Central and South European (cse)	2	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
Central and Southeast European (csee)	4	0.79			4	0.96	1	0.50
MEDITERRANEAN TYPE	71	13.98	19	11.05	32	7.69	57	28.36
Mediterranean-Central Asian (mca)	5	0.98	1	0.58	3	0.72	5	2.49
Mediterranean-West Central Asian (mwca)	3	0.59	2	1.16	2	0.48	2	0.99
North Mediterranean-West Central Asian (nmwca)	1	0.20			1	0.24		
East Mediterranean-Central Asian (emca)	1	0.20					1	0.50
Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian (nemit)	1	0.20			1	0.24	1	0.50
Central and Southeast European-Iran-Turanian (cseeit)	1	0.20					1	0.50
Central and South European-North African (csena)	2	0.39			1	0.24	2	0.99
Holomediterranean (hom)	19	3.74	3	1.74	10	2.40	16	7.96
Atlantomediterranean (am)	3	0.59					3	1.49
North Mediterranean (nm)	4	0.79			1	0.24	4	1.99
Atlantic-South European (ase)	1	0.20	1	0.58			1	0.50
South European (se)	3	0.59	1	0.58	2	0.48	3	1.49
Southeast European-Pontian-Caspian (seepc)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24		
Southeast European-Pontian (seep)	1	0.20			1	0.24		
Southeast European-Anatolian (seea)	1	0.20			1	0.24		
Southeast European (sec)	1	0.20					1	0.50
East Mediterranean (em)	4	0.79	2	1.16	3	0.72	4	1.99
Northeast Mediterranean (nem)	5	0.98	1	0.58			4	1.99
Pontomediterranean (pm)	3	0.59	1	0.58	1	0.24	2	0.99
Pontian endemic (Ep)	3	0.59	3	1.74			2	0.99
Balkan endemic (Eb)	2	0.39			1	0.24	1	0.50
Bulgarian endemic (Ebg)	1	0.20	1	0.58	1	0.24		
Regional Bulgarian endemic (Er)	4	0.79	2	1.16	1	0.24	4	1.99
Local Bulgarian endemic (El)	1	0.20			1	0.24		
Total	508		172	34.33	416	83.03	201	40.12

m³). In the autumn zooplankton, almost all summer zooplankters are established but with lower average value of the biomass (36.13 mg/m³) in comparison with the summer value (102.10 mg/m³). The highest average value of the autumn biomass (78.17 mg/m³) is recorded in coastal waters east of Cape Galata and the lowest one (16.76 mg/m³) – east of Cape Maslen Nos (KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998). The layer, richest in plankton, is at a depth to 23 m (31.1% of the total biomass). The layer up to 50 m depth contains plankton equivalent to 51.8% of the total biomass. The increase of biomass at a depth of 100-125 m is due to the accumulation of cryophilic plankters. With highest amounts in the period 1970-1988 are the species *Oithona minuta* (to 2813 ind/m³), *Acartia clausi* (to 2388 ind/m³), *Penilia avirostris* (2044 ind/m³) and *Pleopis polyphaemoides* (to 767 ind/m³) in summer and *Paracalanus parvus* (364 ind/m³) in autumn (KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998). Significant impact on the planktonic cenoses in the 80s and 90s has *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, with maximum numbers of 450 ind/m³ recorded (KONSULOV, 1989, 1990; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; KAMBURSKA, 2004). Maximum values of 12 kg/m³ are established in the shelf water areas in April of 1990 (BOGDANOVA & KONSULOV, 1993). As a determining factor for zooplankton development, the species has become an indicator of the pelagic ecosystem and threat to the species diversity of planktonic cenoses. After 2000 the number of *M. leidyi* decreased as a result of the predatory pressure of *Beroe ovata* and the structure of the dominant groups began to recover. Most appreciable are changes in the coastal zone. The Crustacea (predominantly Copepoda and Cladocera) usually comprise 70-80% of the zooplankton biomass. Of these crustaceans, about 11280 ind/m³ were established in the summer of 2005 in front of Cape Galata (SHIGALOVA et al., 2008).

ZOOBENTHOS. The number of zoobenthos species is about 1000 (1370 species with Protozoa and parasitic forms), belonging to 19 types. It is studied better in Bulgaria than in other Black Sea countries. Arthropoda, Annelida, Mollusca and Nematoda have the greatest species diversity. Since some taxonomic groups have not yet been sufficiently investigated, it could be accepted that the species composition is higher. Three main zones are established – **supralittoral**, **mediolittoral** (littoral, pseudolittoral) and **sublittoral** (infralittoral, circalittoral). In these zones 12 biocenoses and a great number of series are differentiated, which are characterized by definite species composition (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1960, 1962; VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1978; MARINOV, 1990;

KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; REVKOV et al., 2008).

Rocky supralittoral. A characteristic species are *Chthamalus stellatus*, *Melarhaphe neritoides* and *Ligia italica*, found up to 2-3 m above the water on the rocks. The highest settled specimens of *Ch. stellatus* and *M. neritoides* are active only during rough sea. The density of *Ch. stellatus* reaches thousands ind/m². *Myosotella myosotis* is found sometimes under the stones in that biocenosis and *Pachygrapsus marmoratus* temporarily goes out (VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1978; MARINOV, 1990).

Sandy supralittoral and washed out algae. The species of family Talitridae are typical forms, of which *Orchestia bottae* (to 3500 ind/m² and 90 g/m²) is a typical mass species (STOYKOV, 1975). Many insects, inhabiting the coast, of the orders Collembola, Heteroptera, Coleoptera and Diptera are presented. A part of their larvae grow up in washed out algae. Marine forms as *Orchestia gammarellus* (to 2831.7 mg/100 g algae), connected with algae and sea grass and other washed ashore species, are presented. The highest biomass (8661.6 mg/m²) is established in autumn (BESCHOVSKI, 1964a, 1975a, 1978; MARINOV, 1990).

Rocky mediolittoral (Enteromorpha zone). The most abundant species are *Spirorbis pussilla*, *Chthamalus stellatus*, *Balanus improvisus*, *Idotea balthica*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and the larvae forms of *Thalassomyia frauenfeldi*. The species *Patella ulysiponensis* is a typical inhabitant which is rare now but formerly it occurred in great quantity along the southern coastal zone, according to older literature (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1960a). *Eriphia verrucosa* and *Pachygrapsus marmoratus* are observed during the warm months (MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV, 1998).

Sandy mediolittoral. A very typical and abundant species is *Donacilla cornea*, the maximum density of which reaches 9800 ind/m² at Alepu. A comparatively high density is established at Stomoplo (6000 ind/m²) and Ahtopol (2000 ind/m²). *Ophelia bicornis* is also a mass species with density of 2000 ind/m²; it is found on the beach at Lozenetz Village. The Caspian relict *Euxinia maeoticus* occurs rarely. Over 60 species have been found in the subterranean beach waters, of which Harpacticoida (29 species), Polychaeta (10 species), Turbellaria and Halacaridae (7 species each) are best represented. The average density of the meiobenthos varies from 14552 to 74000 ind/m², as Oligochaeta and Harpacticoida predominate. The maximum density of Oligochaeta reaches 76760 ind/m² (MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998).

Cystoseira overgrowths. An exceptionally rich biocenosis, connected to the algae *Cystoseira barbata* and *C. crinita* that develop on the rocky bottom from 0.5 to 20 m of depth. Over 130 species have been established, of which Crustacea (68 species) and Polychaeta (31 species) are best represented. Characteristic species are *Caprella acanthifera*, *Palaemon adspersus*, *Clibanarius erythropus*, *Macropodia longirostris*, *Pilumnus hirtellus*, *Nereis zonata*, *Spirorbis pussilla*, etc.. Eight mollusk species develop on the thallus of the algae, the majority of which are *Tricolia pullus*, *Bittium reticulatum*, *Rissoa splendida* and *Mytilaster lineatus* (which densely overgrows the base of the thallus). Some Cnidaria (*Sarsia tubulosa*, *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Lucernariopsis campanulata*, etc.) and Bryozoa (*Electra pilosa*) are attached to the algae. The average density of the macro- and meiobenthos is 709424 ind/m², the average biomass – 20.9 g/kg algae. The maximum density reaches 1040000 ind/m², and the biomass – 400 g/m². Harpacticoida has a high density (113396 экз./kg algae). The density and biomass are highest in spring and summer (212668 ind/m² and 58.5 g/kg algae). The biomass is formed mainly from the mollusks (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1977; MARINOV, 1990).

Rocky sublittoral. This biocenosis spreads in depth from 0.5 to 30 m and comprises over 130 species with average density of 105105 ind/m². Representatives of Crustacea (40 species), Mollusca (36 species) and Polychaeta (31 species) predominate. Many Porifera (*Petrosia ficiformis*, *Dysidea fragilis*, genus *Haliclona*, etc.), cnidarians (*Aglaophenia pluma*, *Orthopyxis integra*, *Actinia aquina*, etc.), sedentary Polychaeta (*Sabellaria taurica*, *Spirobranchus triqueter*, *Vermiliopsis infundibulum* and *Spirorbis pussilla*), Bryozoa (*Membranipora* and *Cryptosula*) and Ascidiacea (*Botryllus schlosseri*) are presented. The decapods (*Palaemon adspersus*, *Palaemon elegans*, *Hippolyte sapphica*, *Clibanarius erythropus*, *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Pachygrapsus marmoratus*) are most represented. However, the mass species *Carcinus aestuarii* has declined sharply in numbers lately. The species *Lepidochitona cinerea* and *Rapana venosa* are permanent inhabitants of the rocky bottom. The most abundant snails are *Tricolia pullus*, *Gibbula divaricata* and *Rissoa splendida*. The mussels *Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Mytilaster lineatus* occur in large quantities. The karst and mergel rocks are pierced by the holes of *Petricola lithophaga*, *Pholas dactylus* and *Barnea candida* (MARINOV, 1990). Great aggregations of *Ostrea edulis* occurred in the past around Cape Maslen Nos – reef, made of oysters, but now

living forms there are not established (TODOROVA et al., 2008a).

Sandy sublittoral. Extends from 0 to 17-20 m depth and is the richest in terms of species biocenosis. Above 300 species have been established, some of which penetrated from neighboring biocenoses. Polychaeta (above 60 species), crustaceans (about 50 species), mollusks (above 30 species) dominate as well as great number of other groups, in which psammophilous and psammobiontic species are presented. The zoocenosis has been divided into 5 subcenoses according to the qualitative composition and ground characteristics (MARINOV, 1990). Some Polychaeta (*Scolelepis squamata*, *Glycera convoluta* and *Prionospio cirrifera*), crustaceans (*Bathyporeia guilliamsoniana*, *Ampelisca diadema*, *Diogenes pugilator*) and common mollusks (*Chamelea gallina*, *Lucinella divaricata* and *Bittium reticulatum*) are dominated forms. Characteristic psammophilous Polychaeta are *Arenicola marina*, *Pisione remota*, *Prionospio malmgreni* and *Polygordius lacteus*, some Cumacea from crustaceans (*Pseudocuma*, *Bodotria*, *Cumopsis* and *Cumella*) and many mollusks (*Loripes lacteus*, *Solen marginatus*, *Tellina donacina*, *T. tenuis*, *T. fabula*, *Donax trunculus* and *Gouldia minima*). *Actinothoe clavata* and *Branchiostoma lanceolatum* (related to a certain structure of the sand) are typical representatives. The density and biomass are determined by psammobiontic forms and as exception by some eurybionts (*Balanus improvisus* and *Ampelisca diadema*). The highest is the density of Polychaeta; Mollusca have the highest biomass. The average density varies from 1484 ind/m² to 2576 ind/m²; as Polychaeta comprise 55%, followed by crustaceans – 16%, mollusks – 27% and other groups – about 1.5-2%. The average biomass is 136.4 g/m² as the mollusks comprise 92.8% (126.5 g/m²) of it (VALKANOV et al., 1978; MARINOV, 1990). The average density of mollusks is 398 ind/m²; it is the highest for *Lentidium mediterraneum* (168 ind/m²) which can reach a maximum density up to 21000 ind/m². For Polychaeta, *Spio filicornis* reaches a maximum density of 8320 ind/m² (VALKANOV et al., 1978; MARINOV, 1990). The maximum biomass for mollusks, from 1542 to 1787 g/m² (density about 2700 ind/m²), is established for *Ch. gallina* (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1966; MARINOV, 1990). The invasive immigrants *Rapana venosa* (biomass up to 400 g/m²), *Anadara kagoshimensis* (biomass up to 4282 g/m²) and *Mya arenaria* (biomass up to 4596 g/m²) are also represented here.

Coastal silt. This zone begins from where the sandy bottom ends. It extends from 15-20 to 30-40 m

depth and is better developed in the northern coastal zone. Relatively poor biocenosis, in which about 50 species have been established. It can be divided into 2 subcenoses depending on the abundance of *Melinna palmata* (Polychaeta) – high occurrence of *M. palmata* and low occurrence of *M. palmata*. The former comprises 2/3 of the entire cenosis, has a richer species diversity, density and biomass. The maximum density of *M. palmata* reaches to 2010 ind/m² and the biomass – to 44.9 g/m² (NGUEN SUAN LI, 1984; MARINOV, 1990). The average density of the biocenosis is 564 ind/m² and the maximum one – 2543 ind/m². The average biomass is 76.3 g/m² and the maximum one – 280.7 g/m². Polychaeta comprises 82.4% of the density and Mollusca forms about 77.9% of the biomass of this zoocenosis. *Spisula subtruncata* and *Chamelea gallina* have the highest density. *Polititapes aureus* and *Ch. gallina* have the highest biomass, to 84.7 g/m² and 56.1 g/m² respectively. In some places the biomass is determined by the presence of *Mytilus galloprovincialis*. Of Crustacea, *Ampelisca diadema* and *Upogebia pusilla* have the highest density as the latter forms the biomass as well. Characteristic species of the sandy-ozy ground are *Actinothoe clavata*, *Lagis koreni*, *U. pusilla* and many mollusks of the orders *Caecum*, *Calyptrea*, *Cyclope*, *Nassarius*, *Lucinella*, *Spisula*, *Abra* and *Gouldia* (VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1978; NGUEN SUAN LI, 1984; MARINOV, 1990).

Mytilus silt. This zone begins to the north of Cape Kaliakra from the depth of 45 m and reaches the depth of about 70 m; at the Cape Emine – 80 m. The width of this zone varies from 2-3 miles to 10-15 miles. Ahead of Burgas Bay the zone is the widest and begins from the depth of 13-20 m. In the southern part of the Bulgarian coast (from Sozopol to Rezovo) this biocenosis begins very close to the shore. Typical for the Black Sea is a zone at a depth of 40 to 140 m, composed of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (to about 70 m) and *Modiolula phaseolina* (from 70 to 140 m). Nowhere *M. galloprovincialis* reaches such quantity as in the Black Sea. In the southern half of the Bulgarian shelf the higher biomass is concentrated to 50 m isobath, while the northern half of it reaches 80 m isobath. Whenever the biomass is over 500 g/m² it is caused by *Mytilus galloprovincialis* which is the main dominant. In front of Pomorie a biomass to 2694 g/m² is established, in front of Tsarevo – 3354 g/m², in front of Burgas – 4865 g/m² and in front of Krapets – 5900 g/m² (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1962; MARINOV, 1990; MARINOV & STOYKOV, 1995; STOYKOV & UZUNOVA, 1999). The biomass of *M. galloprovincialis* shows 3 maximums, of which the maximum at 45 m depth is

the biggest. The species composition (over 100 species) is represented by eurybathic as well as typical for this depth species. This biocenosis is considered one of the richest in species and also ranks highest in biomass. Polychaeta is best presented, followed by Crustacea and Mollusca. *Aglaophenia pluma*, *Sertularella polyzonias*, *Cerebratulus ventrosulcatus*, *Aricidea claudiae*, *Ciona intestinalis* and *Asciidiella aspersa* are characteristic inhabitants of this biocenosis. Of mollusks, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Abra alba* and *Polititapes aureus* have a very high density. Biomass of the zoocenosis is formed mainly by the mollusks (94.3%). *M. galloprovincialis* alone gives 63.6% from the biomass. However, as a result of its patchy distribution, the coefficient of permanency of this species is only 25.6%, followed by *S. subtruncata* with the coefficient of permanency 79.2% but with a twice less biomass. The average density is 666 ind/m²; the maximum one – 4185 ind/m². The average biomass is 134.4 g/m²; the maximum one – 3817 g/m². About 57.2% of the density is formed by Polychaeta as *A. claudiae* predominates (VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1978; MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; KONSULOV, 1998).

Phaseolina silt. This zone extends from 60-65 m to 184 m of depth. In the southern region, due to the larger slope of the bottom, the zone is narrower. *Modiolula phaseolina* is a dominant species, with the coefficient of permanency from 22.2% (south of Kamchiya River) to 96.5% (in the north). The higher biomass (200-900 g/m²) below 60 m isobath is due to this species. In the south *M. phaseolina* is poorly represented, therefore the average biomass is often below 50 g/m². Its density and biomass show many peaks, of which the density maximum (4963 ind/m²) is at 110-120 m of depth and the biomass maximum (389 g/m²) – at 65 m (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1960b). Recently, this species was recorded at the depth of 55 m in front of Cape Kaliakra, with a density up to 13040 ind/m² and biomass up to 995.6 g/m² (MARINOV & STOYKOV, 1995). The greater species diversity of this biocenosis (over 60 species) is up to 100 m depth. Below 150 m of depth occur only *Sycon ciliatum*, *Actinothoe clavata*, *Pachycerianthus solitarius*, *Nephtys hobergii* and *Leptosynapta inchaerens* (MARINOV, 1990). The average density is 853 ind/m² and the maximum one is 5125 ind/m². Mollusks comprise 81.7% of the density, and *M. phaseolina* alone, forms 79.9% of the total density. The average biomass is 44 g/m² and the maximum one is 394 g/m². The mollusks account for 86.5% of the whole biomass, and *M. phaseolina* alone, for 79.2% (MARINOV, 1990). Of Gastropoda,

Trophon muricatus is the only representative. This conspicuous predator feeds on the mussels with thinner shells, such as *M. phaseolina*, *Parvicardium exiguum*, *Papillicardium papillosum*, *Spisula subtruncata*, *Abra alba* and *A. Prismatica*. Characteristic of this biocenosis are *Suberites carnosus*, *P. solitarius*, *L. inchaerens*, *Amphiura stepanovi*, etc. The mass species *Terebellides stroemii* and *A. stepanovi* are widely distributed. (VALKANOV & MARINOV, 1978; MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV, 1998).

Meiobenthos in the sublittoral zone.

Nematoda, Polychaeta and Harpacticoida dominate on sand and silt bottoms from 5 to 150 m of depth. Cephalorhyncha, Chalacaridae, Cyclopoida are often found; Oligochaeta and Ostracoda are rarely found. Over 100 species have been established as the most representatives have a low frequency of occurrence. The total number is 164152 ind/m² and the maximum number reaches up to 1181000 ind/m². The density is formed mainly by Nematoda (77.5%); its maximum number reaches up to 1034000 ind/m². The maximum number of Oligochaeta and Harpacticoida is 65000 and 102000 ind/m² respectively. Ostracoda is rarely found; its number amounts to 1000-2000 ind/m². Due to the spotty distribution of meiobenthos depth is not always determinative for the number that decreases below 35 m (MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV, 1998).

COASTAL BASINS. There are about 40 lakes, marshes and areas, flooded by rivers along the Bulgarian coast (VARBANOV, 2002; HRISTOVA, 2012; Table 1). Most common are firth lakes (blocked estuaries) and lagoon lakes (areas separated from the open sea). The presence of brackish elements is a special feature of their fauna. A "saline wedge" is formed at the lower parts of the rivers, which is situated below the fresh waters. In this "wedge" the bottom inhabitants are marine or brackish, whereas those in upper water layers are freshwater species. A specific fauna inhabits the lakes, firths and marshes along the coast. The marine brackish species endure water down to 1 ‰ salinity and the freshwater forms withstand water salinization from 1.5 ‰ to 8 ‰. Many euryhaline sea species also take part in the formation of the coastal basins's fauna, which could vary from marine to freshwater, depending on the water salinity. Nineteen rivers enter the Bulgarian Black Sea (12 rivers enter the Black Sea and 8 rivers discharge into the coastal lakes). Their mouth areas have firth nature where oligo- or euryhaline forms are presented. It is therefore difficult the fauna of these rivers to be scrutinized separately from the coastal stagnant basins (VALKANOV, 1935, 1936; DRENSKY,

1947; PETRBOK, 1947; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1957, 1976; ZASCHEV & ANGELOV, 1959; MIHAILOVA-NEIKOVA, 1961; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1967; STOYKOV, 1979; MARINOV, 1990; TRAYANOVA, 2003, 2008).

The mass development of the mussel *Dreissena polymorpha* that reaches to 3-4 m depth and forms a ring around the shore is characteristic for the lakes **Durankulak**, **Ezerets** and **Shabla**. The Caspian relict *Hypania invalida* has a high density (thousands ind/m²) and in the zone of *D. polymorpha* Ostracoda reaches 8595 ind/m² (CVETKOV, 1958; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1967; VALKANOV et al., 1978; KOVACHEV & UZUNOV, 1981; MARINOV, 1990; NAIDENOV, 1998; STOICHEV, 1998; KOVACHEV et al., 1999, 2002; PETROVA & STOYKOV, 2002). *Cordylophora caspia*, many species of the families Coroppiidae and Gammaridae, *Astacus leptodactylus* and *Theodoxus fluviatilis* are common species. In Shabla Lake the average biomass is about 19.4 g/m² and the maximum biomass reaches 842 g/m². In Durankulak Lake the maximum biomass is 60 g/m² (VALKANOV et al., 1978). The lakes have been investigated recently as protected areas and have a rich fauna (from 101 to 137 species).

Fauna of the **Beloslav** Lake, before its transforming into port, was formed mainly by freshwater Crustacea and Chironomidae larvae (VALKANOV, 1935, 1936, 1937; CVETKOV, 1955a, 1955b, 1957). In the Chironomidae complex haloxenes are presented but there is a lack of typical halophils and halobionts. The freshwater species are best represented in most crustaceans as there are brackish and marine forms. Ostracoda comprises a significant percentage (15 species, or 35.7%). Copepoda includes more haloxenes and halobionts. All Amphypoda, Mysida, *Iera sarsi* and *Rhitropanopeus harrissi* are brackish forms. *Cordylophora caspia*, *Leander adpersus*, *Astacus leptodactylus*, *Potamon ibericum*, *Theodoxus fluviatilis*, *Unio pictorum* and *Dreissena polymorpha* occur. In quantitative terms Oligochaeta, Ostracoda and Chironomidae predominate (CVETKOV, 1957). After 1964-1966 the state of the lake got worse and it became to a chironomid type. Typical are periodic extinctions due to oxygen deficiency. In 1990-1991 the species composition is poor, there are lack of mollusks, dead zones and single species communities. After 2000 the species diversity increases, 5 mollusk species appear and there are no permanent dead zones (TRAYANOVA, 2003, 2008).

After the connection of **Varna** Lake with the sea, the freshwater species disappeared there and the fauna was formed by euryhaline marine and brack-

ish forms (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1957). The following species dominate: *Hydrobia ventrosa* (up to 24520 ind/m²), *Mytilaster lineatus* (up to 37400 ind/m² and 620 g/m²), *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (to 1837 ind/m² and 6023 g/m²), *Cerastoderma glaucum* (to 968 ind/m²) and *Abra segmentum* (to 1177 ind/m²). The reserves of *M. galloprovincialis* were estimated as ca. 5000 t and were of great economical importance. Mass overgrowths, causing problems of TPP Varna in the 70s, are *Ficopomaticus enigmaticus*, *Amphibalanus improvisus* and *M. galloprovincialis*. The maximum overgrowth reaches 39260 g/m² for 3 months (DIMOV et al., 1970). In the last decades, the lake underwent profound transformations and its fauna changed (MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998). In the 50s crustaceans and mollusks prevail. In the 90s the number of mollusks decreased, whereas Polychaeta increased and dominated in numbers (70.6%). In recent years, the number of species is increased (especially in crustaceans). An increase in numbers (from 5787 ind/m² to 18841 ind/m²) and a shift of Polychaeta (38%) by Crustacea (50.9%) was established. The biomass is formed mainly by mollusks (58.7%) and crustaceans (39.0%) (TRAYANOVA, 2003, 2008; TODODROVA et al., 2008b).

The halobionts *Artemia parthenogenetica* and *A. salina* are typical for the hyper-saline lagoon lakes **Pomorie** and **Atanasovsko** [salinity from 30-60‰ to 100-250‰ (IVANOV et al., 1964)]. Of marine forms, *H. ventrosa*, *Nassarius reticulatus*, *C. glaucum* and *A. segmentum* are presented. The density and biomass of *Cyprideis torosa* reach 312532 ind/m² and 37.1 g/m²; of *C. glaucum* – 3234 ind/m² (maximum to 134376 ind/m²) and 338.7 g/m² (CVETKOV, 1958). The number of *Acartia clausi* in the Pomorie Lake reaches 130000 ind/m³ (VASSILEV, 1994). The lakes are protected areas, recently explored in connection with the plans of their management (MICHEV, 1997, 2003; GEORGIEV & NIKOLOV, 2010; PECHLIVANOV, 2010; VARADINOVA et al., 2010). In these lakes specific rich fauna is stored (106-113 species).

In **Burgas** Lake, *A. segmentum* in 1954 reached average density 5544 ind/m² and biomass 790 g/m²; its total biomass was estimated as 16957 t (ZASCHEV & ANGELOV, 1959). The average density of *H. ventrosa* during the same period was 3256 ind/m², biomass – 10.4 g/m² and the total biomass – 216 t. For *C. glaucum* these data are, respectively: 1840 ind/m², 201.8 g/m² and 3081 t. Later, because the salinity decreased from 11‰ to 0.7-1.9‰ these mollusks completely disappeared and currently no living specimens have been found (PANDOURSKI, 2001). The density of the following crustaceans was high:

Crassicorophium crassicornes (10806 ind/m² – 31.1 g/m²) and *Gammarus subtypicus* (748 ind/m² – 3.7 g/m²), with total biomass 549 t and 41.1 t respectively (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1967; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1976; STOYKOV, 1979). Nowadays 93% of the total biomass of the zoobenthos (16.6 g/m²) is formed by Chironomidae larvae (VALKANOV et al., 1978).

In **Mandra** Lake, before the dam construction, many marine forms (*Hediste diversicolor*, *Corophium volutator*, *Palaemon adspersus*, *Upogebia pusilla*, *Liocarcinus vernalis*, *H. ventrosa*, *C. glaucum* and *A. segmentum*) have been recorded, which can be found now in the lakes **Uzungeren** and **Poda**, remaining outside of the dam (VALKANOV, 1936; MIHAILOVA-NEIKOVA, 1961; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1967; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1976). Over 100 species benthos forms have been found, which average biomass is 14 g/m² (57.5% Chironomidae). After the dam construction, the zoobenthos (11.8 g/m²) is formed mainly by Oligochaeta and Chironomidae (60%). Changes in biomass (2.4-4.2 g/m² to 10.7-15.7 g/m²) and a dominance of Chironomidae larvae are observed (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1976; STOYKOV, 1979).

The firth of **Ropotamo River** is well-studied and over 100 species have been established there (VALKANOV, 1934, 1935, 1936; CVETKOV & GRUNCHAROVA, 1976, 1979; GRUNCHAROVA, 1977). It is abundant in the invasive forms *Ficopomaticus enigmaticus* (up to 18400 ind/dm² – 360 g/dm²), *Amphibalanus eburneus* and *Rhithropanopeus harrisi*. The following species are often found: *Blackfordia virginica*, *Cordylophora caspia*, some Chironomidae larvae, *Palaemon adspersus*, *Hydrobia acuta*, *Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Mytilaster lineatus*, *Cerastoderma glaucum*, *Abra segmentum*, *Barentsia benedeni* (to 8000 zooids/dm²) and many Bryozoa.

In the firth of **Veleka River**, *Dreissena polymorpha* covers the shells of *Anodonta cygnaea*, *Pseudanodonta complanata* and *Unio pictorum*. A significant number have the populations of *Astacus leptodactylus*, *Potamon ibericum* and *T. fluviatilis* (often and *P. planorbis*); of the marine forms *H. ventrosa*, *C. glaucum* and *A. segmentum* are presented.

Some coastal basins were explored comparatively long ago and the investigations do not reflect the recent condition of their fauna (Shabla Tuzla, Nanevska Tuzla, Balchishka Tuzla, Batovsko Swamp, Nesebarsko Swamp, the swamps Alepu, Arkutino, Stomoplo and Dyavolsko, the firths of the rivers Batova, Kamchiya, Dvoynitsa, Dyavolska, Karaagach, Veleka, Silistar and Rezovska). Furthermore, the

Table 7. Alien invertebrate animals, recorded from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast (Note. The years in brackets show finding of the species in Bulgaria, * – invasive species)

Taxa	Year of introduction or finding	Donor region
Coelenterata		
<i>Blackfordia virginica</i> Mayer, 1910	1925 (1935)	North Atlantic and North America
<i>Garveia franciscana</i> (Torrey, 1902)	1933 (1933)	North Atlantic and North America
<i>Rathkea octopunctata</i> (Sars, 1835)	(1957)	Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean Sea
<i>Diadumene lineata</i> (Verrill, 1869)	(1960)	Northwest Pacific Ocean
Ctenophora		
* <i>Mnemiopsis leidyi</i> Agassiz, 1865	1982 (1986)	Western Atlantic Ocean
* <i>Beroe ovata</i> Bruguère, 1789	1997 (1997)	North Atlantic Ocean
<i>Bolinopsis vitrea</i> (L. Agassiz, 1860)	2010 (2010)	Tropical and Subtropical
Annelida: Polychaeta		
* <i>Ficopomatus enigmaticus</i> (Fauvel, 1923)	1929 (1935)	Indian Ocean
<i>Hesionides arenaria</i> Friedrich, 1937	1950-re (1954)	Pacific Ocean or Atlantic Ocean
<i>Streblospio shrubsolii</i> (Buchanan, 1890)	1957 (1957)	North Atlantic Ocean
<i>Streptosyllis varians</i> Webster & Benedict, 1887	1966 (1966)	North Atlantic or Pacific Ocean
* <i>Polydora cornuta</i> Bosc, 1802	2005 (2008)	North and West Atlantic Ocean
* <i>Dipolydora quadrilobata</i> (Jacobi, 1883)	(1990)	Atlantic Ocean and Pacific Ocean
Arthropoda: Crustacea		
<i>Acartia tonsa</i> Dana, 1849	1976 (2000)	Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean
<i>Oithona davisae</i> Ferrari F. D. & Orsi, 1984	2001 (2009)	Northwest Pacific Ocean
<i>Triconia minuta</i> (Giesbrecht, 1893 [1892])	(2000)	Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean
<i>Amphibalanus eburneus</i> Gould, 1841	1892 (1933)	North America
* <i>Amphibalanus improvisus</i> Darwin, 1854	1844 (1912)	North America
<i>Palaemon macrodactylus</i> Rathbun, 1902	(2009)	Pacific Ocean and Southeast Asia
<i>Rhithropanopeus harrisi</i> (Gould, 1841)	1937 (1934, 1953)	North America
<i>Callinectes sapidus</i> Rathbun, 1896	1967 (1968)	North Atlantic Ocean
<i>Eriocheir sinensis</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1854)	2006 (2005)	East and Southeast Asia
Mollusca		
<i>Potamopyrgus antipodarium</i> (J. E. Gray, 1843)	1952 (2008)	coast of New Zeland
* <i>Rapana venosa</i> (Valenciennes, 1846)	1946 (1956)	Sea of Japan
<i>Neptunea arthritica</i> (Valenciennes, 1858)	(2000)	Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean
<i>Corambe obscura</i> (Verrill, 1870)	1980 (1986)	North Atlantic Ocean
<i>Ferrissia fragilis</i> (Tryon, 1862)	(1983)	North America
<i>Physella acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	(1927)	North America
* <i>Anadara kagoshimensis</i> (Tokunaga, 1906)	1982 (1984)	Indian Ocean and Pacific Ocean
* <i>Mya arenaria</i> Linnaeus, 1758	1966 (1973)	Circumboreal
<i>Teredo navalis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	750-500 B.C.	Atlantic Ocean and Pacific Ocean

coast is exposed to strong anthropogenic presence and changes that require a continuous update of the information.

ALIEN IMMIGRANTS. The penetration of alien species through ballast waters and/or as fouling organisms on ship hulls is one of the greatest threats for the world's oceans. The assessment whether a certain species is invasive and harmful to the Black Sea ecosystem is complex. During a certain point of time the species may be harmful and subsequently to get a positive effect – food base for other species, an

element for increasing the diversity or resource. Lists of species, introduced in the Black Sea, have been published by several authors (CVETKOV & MARINOV, 1986; GOMOIU & SCOLKA, 1996; KONSULOV, 1998; SHADRIN, 2000; ZAITSEV & ÖZTÜRK, 2001; GOMOIU et al., 2002; MONCHEVA & KAMBURSKA, 2002; KAMBURSKA & MONCHEVA, 2003; ZAITSEV et al., 2004; KONSULOVA & STEFANOVA, 2007). Thirty-one invertebrate species are known from the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, occurring at different times (Table 7). The most significant changes in the Black Sea

communities are caused by 5 species, introduced in the last 60 years – *Mnemiopsis leidyi*, *Beroe ovata*, *Rapana venosa*, *Anadara kagoshimensis* and *Mya arenaria* (CVETKOV & MARINOV, 1986; MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOVA & STEFANOVA, 2007; TODOROVA & MONCHEVA, 2013).

The introduction of the ctenophore *Mnemiopsis leidyi* in the Black and Azov Seas in the 1980s caused the decline of anchovies' and sprat' stocks, estimated at 200 millions USD per year (ZAITZEV & MAMAEV, 1997). This species becomes a determinative factor for the development of zooplankton and indicator of the pelagic community. *M. leidyi* is a self-fertile hermaphrodite with broad food spectrum (from microzooplankton to crustaceans, eggs and fish larvae) and a high tolerance to temperature and salinity. It is reproductively mature 12 days after hatching and produces over 2000-3000 eggs. In the 80s *M. leidyi* caused a drop in pelagic fish reserves, by competing for the same food resources. A maximum number of *M. leidyi* (450 ind/m³) was recorded in Varna Lake in 1986 (KONSULOV, 1986; KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; KAMBURSKA, 2004). After 2000 the number of *M. leidyi* decreases, affected by the predatory pressure from *B. ovata*.

Beroe ovata is known to feed on planktivorous ctenophores and, in particular, on *M. leidyi*. There is a trophic type predator-prey relationship between *B. ovata* and *M. leidyi*. The development of *B. ovata* depends on the seasons; the species occurs mostly in summer and autumn. Its reproductive potential is closed to the potential of *M. leidyi*. The dynamics of *B. ovata*, its seasonal and annual variations, development and survival depend on *M. leidyi* (KONSULOV & KAMBURSKA, 1998). Like *M. leidyi*, this species was transported in ships ballast waters from the Northwest Atlantic. The arrival of *B. ovata* appears to have stabilized the Black Sea ecosystem, leading to a reduction in *M. leidyi* populations and subsequent recovery of plankton and fish populations.

The first specimen of *Rapana venosa* in the Bulgarian aquatory was found in 1956 in Varna Bay, near Cape Galata (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1958). Development of this snail in the rocky sublittoral has a substantial impact on *Mytilus* and *Ostrea*, and in the sand sublittoral – on *Chamelea gallina*. The great eurybiontness, high fecundity and lack of competitors allowed this predator to reach mass development in the Black Sea and aroused discussion for eventual measures for a struggle with it. In a single trawling, up to 1500 specimens have been caught, and in some regions between Balchik and Kavarna the entire bottom was covered with Rapa whelks.

Very high numbers was observed in Byala, in the region of Cape Cherni Nos (KLISUROV, 2008). During the last 20 years, the snail was gathering for food with all possible means. After conquest of the Black Sea the species penetrated the Aegean, Adriatic and Mediterranean Seas, Atlantic coast of France, North Sea, East coast of USA, the mouth of the Rio de la Plata River between Uruguay and Argentina and around New Zealand. The way how the species was transported in the Black Sea is unclear. *R. venosa* is an eurythermal and euryhaline species that develops in the coastal zone on solid substrate and sandy and silty bottom at a depth to 30-40 m. The snail withstands temperature changes (from 0 to 30°C), water pollution and reduced oxygen content. There is a huge fertility (a snail delayed approximately 220000 eggs) which compensates its exploitation by man. It lives about 10 years. There are no precise data on the population of Rapa on the Bulgarian coast (KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; KONSULOV, 1998).

Mya arenaria has been first reported for the Bulgarian coast in the Bay of Burgas in 1973 (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA, 1974). The mussel inhabits the sandy sublittoral and reaches the wash zone. It has a high ecological plasticity and easy endures variations of the salinity and temperature, and oxygen deficiency. It reaches a high density (over 300-400 to 4862 specimens/m²) in the bays in front of the river mouths. *M. arenaria* is found along the beaches all over the Bulgarian coast but the greatest number of it occurs in front of Durankulak and Albena, in the Varna Bay, Varna Lake, at the influx of the Kamchiya River and Burgas Bay (STOYKOV, 1983; CVETKOV & MARINOV, 1986; MARINOV, 1990). Spawning by eggs thrown straight into the water during the summer months (rarely re-spawning in autumn). From fertilized eggs planktonic larvae develop which 5-6 days after egg hatching convert to mussels. In the 1970s, this mussel is a dominant species in the Romanian coastal zone as 4-5 years after its appearance reaches biomass 16 kg/m² and numbers more than 8000 ind/m² (GOMOIU & PORUMB, 1969). In many areas of the Black Sea shelf *M. arenaria* is a dominant species in new zoocenosis, called her name.

The first specimens of *Anadara kagoshimensis* for the Bulgarian coast were found in 1982 in Varna Bay (MARINOV et al., 1983; KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1984). Much later, a high density of the species has been found in Burgas Bay (up to 400 specimens/m² and biomass 4280 g/m²). This mussel is a eurythermal and euryhaline species that endures very low oxygen concentrations in the water due to

Table 8. Conservation status of invertebrate animals of the Bulgarian Black Sea coast

Taxa	Black Sea Red Data Book	Ecological data, Bulgarian Red Data Book, IUCN and European category	Distribution (area and depth)
<i>Halichondria panicea</i> (Pallas, 1766)	VU	M, bt, eb, lt	K, 2-65
<i>Odessia maeotica</i> (Ostroumoff, 1896)	VU	M-B, 25%, bt-p	lm, ? Rc
<i>Hesionides arenaria</i> Friedrich, 1937	EN, VU	M, bt, sep, sls, ps, gw	aminwp, 0-10
<i>Ophelia bicornis</i> Savigny, 1918	EN	M, bt, sep, l-sl, ps	bam, 0.5-1.5
<i>Hirudo verbana</i> Carena, 1820		L, bt, ph, 10%, ▲-VU	(cse)
<i>Halacarellus procerus</i> (Viets, 1927)	EN	M-B, bt, l-sl, ps, gw	bam
<i>Branchinella spinosa</i> (H. Milne Edwards, 1840)	EN	B-M, 30%, p	lm, (atm)
<i>Centropages ponticus</i> Karavaev, 1895	EN	M, p	mrs
<i>Anomalocera patersoni</i> Templeton, 1837	EN	M, p, et	amip
<i>Labidocera brunescens</i> (Czerniavsky, 1868)	EN	M, p, eh, th	lmm
<i>Pontella mediterranea</i> (Claus, 1863)	EN	M, p	lmm
<i>Oithona minuta</i> (Krichagin, 1877; Scott, 1894)	EN	M-B-L, p, eh	amip, 20
<i>Hemimysis anomala</i> G. O. Sars, 1907	EN	B-L, bt, ep, lt	pc, clm, (h), -20
<i>Chaetogammarus ischnus</i> (Stebbing, 1899)	VU	M-B, eh, sep, ro, l-sl	pc, cpc, Rc
<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i> (Sowinsky, 1894)	VU	B-L, bt, ep, ro, ph	pc, cpc, Rc, (ean)
<i>Iphigenella andrussowi</i> (G. O. Sars, 1896)	LR	B-L, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	pc, Rc
<i>Shablogammarus shablensis</i> (Carausu, 1943)	VU	B-L, bt, ep, ps, ps-s	pc, Rc
<i>Apeudopsis ostroumovi</i> Bacescu & Carausu, 1947	LR	M, bt, sg, ms, phs	p, 27, -100
<i>Upogebia pusilla</i> (Petagna, 1792)	EN	M, bt, ep (p), ps-pe	clmm, -22
<i>Diogenes pugilator</i> (Roux, 1829)	EN	M, bt, mb, ps, sg	eam, ? eami, 0-40
<i>Carcinus aestuarii</i> Nardo, 1847	VU	M, bt, ps, zc, ro, r	lm, ? amp, 0-70
<i>Liocarcinus navigator</i> (Herbst, 1794)	VU	M, bt, eb, ps, sg, s	acem, 3-80
<i>Eriphia verrucosa</i> (Forskål, 1775)	EN	M, bt, ep, sp-l-sl, lt, ▲-VU	lmm, ?lmmg, 0-30
<i>Pilumnus hirtellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	VU	M, bt, mb, ph, mc, lt	clmm, 0-40
<i>Xantho poressa</i> (Olivi, 1792)	VU	M, bt, eb, ro	lmm, 1-15, 100
<i>Potamon ibericum</i> (Bieberstein, 1808)	DD, EN	L, eu	(nmwca)
<i>Pachygrapsus marmoratus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	VU	M, bt, sep, spr-sl, lt	cmm, 0-7
<i>Calopteryx splendens</i> (Harris, 1782)	LR, VU	L-TL, ◆-LC	(wcp)
<i>Calopteryx virgo</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	VU	L-TL, ◆-LC	(tp)
<i>Epallage fatime</i> (Charpentier, 1840)	NE, DD, VU	L-TL, ▲-VU, ◆-NT	(om)
<i>Lestes viridis</i> (Vander Linden, 1825)		L-TL, ▲-VU, ◆-LC	(wp)
<i>Anax imperator</i> Leach, 1815	NE, DD, VU	L-TL, ◆-LC	(wppt)
<i>Sympetrum depressiusculum</i> (Sélys, 1841)		L-TL, ▲-VU, ◆-VU	(tp)
<i>Sympetrum vulgatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L-TL, ▲-VU, ◆-LC	(ewca)
<i>Patella ulyssiponensis</i> Gmelin, 1791	EN	M, bt, sep, lt-ro, l-sl, r	clm, 0-10
<i>Theodoxus pallasi</i> Lindholm, 1924		M-B, eh-14%, ro, ▲-EX	pc, Rc, Sf, +, 4-10
<i>Hauffenia lucidula</i> Angelov, 1967		L, bt, cr, 1%, ▲-CR, ◆-CR	(El)
<i>Valvata cristata</i> O. F. Müller, 1774		L, 0.5%, bt, ph, s, r, ◆-LC	(wes)
<i>Valvata piscinalis</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)		L, 0.4%, bt, sw, ph, pe, x, ◆-LC	(wcp, i - h), 3, 80
<i>Hydrobia acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)		B-M, 60%, bt, ep, sw, ph, ro, s, ◆-LC	lm, ? hm, 0-22
<i>Bithynia tentaculata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, ph, ro, s, ps, ◆-LC	(wp, ? h - i), 5
<i>Turricaspia linctia</i> (Milaschewitch, 1908)		M-B, 8%, bt, s, sw, ◆-LC	pc, Rc, Sf, +, -148
<i>Acroloxus lacustris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, ph, sw, ◆-LC	(wes, ? hoes)
<i>Lymnaea stagnalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, 7%, bt, ph, pe, ◆-LC	(h), 0-4
<i>Stagnicola corvus</i> (Gmelin, 1791)		L, bt, sw, ph, ◆-LC	(hop, ? e), 0-50
<i>Radix auricularia</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, 6%, bt, ph, rh, s, ◆-LC	(h, ? hop), 0.2-25

Table 8. Continued

Taxa	Black Sea Red Data Book	Ecological data, Bulgarian Red Data Book, IUCN and European category	Distribution (area and depth)
<i>Radix balthica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, 3-10%, bt, ph, eu, ◆-LC	(hop)
<i>Ferrissia fragilis</i> (Tryon, 1862)		L, bt, eu, th, ph, r, is, ◆-DD	(h, sk - i), 0-8
<i>Planorbis carinatus</i> O. F. Müller, 1774		L, bt, sw, ph, pe, r, ◆-LC	(wes, ? h), -10, -18
<i>Planorbis planorbis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, 2‰, sw, ph, pe, ◆-LC	(h)
<i>Anisus septemgyratus</i> (Rossmassler, 1835)		L, 8‰, sw, ph, α-β, r, ◆-LC	(wes, ? e)
<i>Anisus vortex</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, 8‰, ph, α-β, r, ◆-LC	(wces)
<i>Anisus vorticulus</i> (Troschel, 1834)		L, bt, pe, ph, rh, sw, r, ◆-NT, HD	(wces, ? wes)
<i>Gyraulus crista</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, 1.5‰, eu, ph, α-β, ◆-LC	(h)
<i>Hippeutis complanatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, ph, s-ar, sw, α, r, ◆-LC	(wces, ? wcp)
<i>Segmentina nitida</i> (O. F. Müller, 1774)		L, bt, sw, ph, α-β, ◆-LC	(wcp)
<i>Planorbarius corneus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, 5‰, sw, po, α-β, ◆-LC	(wces), -9
<i>Physella acuta</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)		L, bt, pe, tx, α-β, is, ◆-LC	(na, sk - i)
<i>Physa fontinalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)		L, bt, sw, po, ph, β, r, ◆-LC	(tp, ? h)
<i>Ostrea edulis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	EN, VU	M, bt, sep, ro	anamnep, i, 7-65
<i>Donacilla cornea</i> (Poli, 1795)	EN	M, bt, sep, ps	lm, 0.2, -2
<i>Solen marginatus</i> Pulteney, 1799	EN	M, bt, sep, ps	clmm, 0-10
<i>Pholas dactylus</i> Linnaeus, 1758		M, bt, sep, lt, BA, BC	eamrs, amrs, -15
<i>Branchiostoma lanceolatum</i> (Pallas, 1774)	VU	M, bt, ep, ps	amip, 17, 21

the presence of hemoglobin in the haemolymph. It has a long life cycle and low coefficient of mortality. In a short time, *A. kagoshimensis* became a significant element of psammo- and pelophilous zoocenoses, and started to displace some local species. Thus the „*Chamelea gallina*” group in front of Balchik, Varna and Burgas transforms into „*A. kagoshimensis*” group. The distribution of this species in the Bulgarian part of the Black Sea is restricted from Balchik to the south part of Burgas Bay (CVETKOV & MARINOV, 1986; MARINOV, 1990; KONSULOV, 1998).

RESOURCE SPECIES AND OVERGROWERS. In 1978 a decline in the population of *Mytilus galloprovincialis* was found although the harvesting was gradually halted. The main reasons for mass mortalities appear to have been the eutrophication and destruction of natural mussel fields by trawling and predatory pressure from *Rapana venosa*. A decrease in predatory pressure in deeper waters and stopping of trawling has resulted in a progressive restoration of mussel resources. In 1990s, the commercial farming of *M. galloprovincialis* on artificial substrata was mostly near the town of Sozopol, where the harvest had reached 150 tons per year (KONSULOV & KONSULOVA, 1993, 1998; KONSULOV, 1998). In 2009, the harvest reached 812 t. Today the number of mussel farms is 17; the farm near Kavarna alone has the capacity of 2000 t per year. Industrial catch

of *Rapana venosa* in Bulgaria began in 1991 when to 500 t of meat were exported. In the following years the catch increased and during 1992-1994 period was about 27000 t (weight with shells). The maximum was reached in 2004 (1195 t meat of Rapa), then a decrement of catches was observed (KONSULOVA & STEFANOVA, 2007). According to Ministry of Agriculture and Food, in 2012 the harvest reached 3100 t, and the export of Rapa meat is 1000-1500 t. There is an interest in the populations of *Mya arenaria* and *Chamelea gallina* but it is not clear how much their exploitation is realized. The foreign interest in these mussels is great.

Essential roles as overgrowers along the Bulgarian Black Sea coast have *Ficopomatus enigmaticus*, *Amphibalanus improvisus* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis* (MARINOV, 1990). These species cause problems to port facilities, craft and TPP Varna (DIMOV et al., 1970). Surveys conducted in the old channel connecting Varna Lake with the sea show that for six months *A. eburneus* and *M. galloprovincialis* give 8205 g/m² (KANEVA-ABADJIEVA & MARINOV, 1965, 1977). In spring the biomass reaches 3357.5 g/m² and is composed mostly by *A. improvisus* and *M. galloprovincialis*. In summer the total biomass reaches 17504 g/m² and is composed mainly by *F. enigmaticus* and *A. improvisus*. For a year, the total overgrowth (and other overgrowers as well) can reach 84 kg/m²

(MARINOV, 1990). The total biomass of the overgrowers in the region of TPP Varna in June reaches 6480 g/m²; in August the overgrowth is mainly of *F. enigmaticus*. The number of attached specimens of this species reaches 3000000 ind/m² for 15 days (DIMOV et al., 1970). In 2 months the overgrowth by *F. enigmaticus* exceeds a thickness of 15 cm. In the 90s, the species mass developed in the Varna Bay.

The first reported problems with *Dreissena polymorpha* in the country is related to the glass factory, located by the canal between Beloslavsko Lake and Varna Lake (RUSSEV, 1965). Since 90 years the mussel invades freshwater basins inside the country and now is presented almost in all river systems (TRICHKOVA et al., 2009). There are problems in TPP Maritsa Iztok 2 where losses of several million leva are registered. Temperature conditions in Ovcharitsa dam created by this plant are optimum for the mussel development which reaches from 300000 to 500000 ind/m².

CONSERVATION SIGNIFICANCE of the fauna. A total of 35 species from the Bulgarian Black Sea invertebrates are included in the Black Sea Red Data Book (1 of Porifera, 1 of Cnidaria, 2 of Annelida, 26 of Arthropoda, 4 of Mollusca and 1 of Chordata); of which 7 are included in the European Red List as well (Table 8). *Pholas dactylus* is included in the international conventions for European and Mediterranean fauna. There are differences in the levels of threat of the species in the separate Black Sea countries (DUMONT et al. 1999). Most species (34 species) belong to the categories endangered (EN) and vulnerable (VU). Five species have a Pontian-Caspian distribution, the Caspian relicts also are 5 species and *Apsudopsis ostroumovi* is a Black Sea (Pontian) endemic. Most often the species are widely distributed as *Halichondria panicea* is a Cosmopolitan spe-

cies. Some taxa, included in the Black Sea Red Data Book, have stable populations along the Bulgarian coast and are not threatened at this stage. Red Data Book of the Republic of Bulgaria includes 8 species invertebrate animals from the Bulgarian Black Sea (*Hirudo verbana*, *Eriphia verrucosa*, *Epallage fatime*, *Lestes viridis*, *Sympetrum depressiusculum*, *S. vulgatum*, *Theodoxus pallasi* and *Hauffenia lucidula*). The species *T. pallasi* – Pontian-Caspian brackish relict species, is accepted as extincted. The species *Carcinus aestuarii* and *Pholas dactylus* which are exceptionally rare recently are not included. Twenty species of freshwater Gastropoda with Eurosiberian, Palaearctic or Holarctic distribution, included in the European Red List and IUCN Red List are known from the coastal brackish basins (Table 8). These include the North American invasive species *Physella acuta* and *Ferrissia fragilis*, which until recently were considered European forms. The snail *Turricaspia lincta*, a Caspian subfossil relict, established only by shells, has a Pontian-Caspian area. A total of 118 Black Sea endemic forms have been found along the Bulgarian coast, of which 12 species are accepted as regional endemics (Table 2). The local endemics are an exception in the marine forms and usually are newly described taxa with unclear distribution. A total of 98 rare species and 41 Caspian relict forms have been established. The number of rare species depends on the level of study of the respective groups. Some relicts are eurybiontic invasive forms with secondary anthropogenic areas.

In Bulgaria the Kaliakra Reserve and protected area Sand Bank Kokestrays are marine protected areas. These include 0.2% of the territorial waters of Bulgaria, 0.1% of the shelf zone to 100 m depth and 0.2% of the protected areas of the country (TODOROVA et al., 2008a).

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Received: 19.03.2014

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Видов състав на свободно живеещите многоклетъчни безгръбначни животни (Metazoa: Invertebrata) от българския сектор на Черно море и крайбрежните бракични водоеми

Здравко ХУБЕНОВ

(Резюме)

От българското Черноморие са известни 19 типа, 39 класа, 123 разряда, 470 семейства и 1537 вида. Те включват 1054 вида (68.6%) морски и морско-бракични форми и 508 вида (33.0%) сладководно-бракични, сладководни и сухоземни форми, свързани с водата. Високо видово богатство (над 100 вида) имат 5 типа (Nematoda, Rotifera, Annelida, Arthropoda и Mollusca). Най-много видове включват Arthropoda (802 вида – 52.2%), Annelida (173 вида – 11.2%) и Mollusca (152 вида – 9.9%). Останалите 14 типа съдържат от 1 до 38 вида. Има няколко добре проучени райони (известни над 200 вида). На първо място са околностите на Варна (601 вида), където изследванията продължават над 100 години. Акваторията на градовете Несебър, Поморие, Бургас и Созопол (от 220 до 274 вида) и районът на нос Калиакра (230 вида) са добре проучени. От крайморските водоеми най-изследвани (известни към 100 вида) са езерата Дуранкулашко, Езерецко-Шабленско, Белославско, Варненско, Поморийско, Атанасовско, Бургаско, Мандренско и лиманът на р. Ропотамо. Вертикалното разпространение е анализирано при 800 вида (75.9%) – морски и морско-бракични форми. Най-много видове са намерени от 0 до 25 m на пясъчно (396 вида) и скално (257 вида) дъно. Представени са групите на стенохипо- (52 вида – 6.5%), стеноепо- (465 вида – 58.1%), мезо- (115 вида – 14.4%) и еврибатите (168 вида – 21.0%). Морските и морско-бракичните форми са разпределени в 162 зоогеографски категории, обединени в 4 основни групи и 16 подгрупи. Основната част от черноморската фауна има атланти-медитерански произход и представлява обеднена атланти-медитеранска фауна (740 вида – 70.2%). Представени са космополитни, атлантииндийски, атлантипацифични, ендемични и каспийски реликтни форми. От черноморските ендемити (118 вида – 11.2%) преобладават бентосни (115 вида – 97.5%) и морски (114 вида – 96.6%) форми. Бракичните ендемити (11 вида – 9.3%) най-често са каспийски реликти. Основната част от каспийските реликти (41 вида – 3.9%) са бентосни бракични форми (38 вида – 92.7%). Сладководно-бракичните, сладководните и сухоземните форми, свързани с водата, са разпределени в 80 зоогеографски категории, обединени в 3 групи и 5 подгрупи. Типично за крайбрежието е преобладаването на видове, разпространени в Палеарктика и извън нея (296 вида – 58.3%). Представени са видове, разпространени само в Палеарктика, но в повече от една подобласт (79 вида – 15.5%) и видове, разпространени в една палеарктична подобласт (126 вида – 24.8%) – евросибирски (55 вида – 10.8%) и медитерански (71 вида – 13.9%). Направена е кратка характеристика на планктонните и бентосните ценози и са разгледани някои крайморски водоеми. Отделено е внимание на инвазивните имигранти, които са променили черноморските съобщества през последните 60 години. Разгледани са видовете с икономическо и консервационно значение.